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Who was done what?

A parser-based study of passive voice constructions in media
discourse on the Russo-Ukrainian War

Master's Programme in Linguistic Diversity and Digital Humanities
General Linguistics
Master's Thesis

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2024-07-31
Helsinki

Faculty: Faculty of Arts

Degree programme: Linguistic Diversity and Digital Humanities

Study track: General Linguistics

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Title: Who was done what? A parser-based study of passive voice constructions in media discourse on the Russo-Ukrainian War

Level: Master's degree

Month and year: July 2024

Number of pages: ix + 88 + 25 (Appendices)

Keywords: passive voice, corpus linguistics, parser, NLP, news media, Russia-Ukraine War

Supervisor: Chingduang Yurayong

Where deposited: Helda (Digital Repository of the University of Helsinki)

Abstract:

The Russo-Ukrainian War is considered the biggest attack to Europe and the first full-scale war in Europe since the Second World War. Media and press do not merely serve the purpose of communicating events, but they have been used as the tool to propagate agenda and play a vital role in shaping the perspectives of the audience towards the events. This prompts scholars to investigate language use in news to examine linguistic phenomena underlined by political and ideological currents.

This project analyzes subject-verb pairs occurring under passive voice constructions in news corpora. Passive voice constructions play a crucial role in revealing how agency and responsibility are represented, especially in the discourse surrounding war and conflict, and this aspect has been underexplored in previous studies. Datasets used in this study include the Ukraine War corpus (170K), Leipzig news corpora (17M), and English speaking Russian news corpora (210K). Examining passive pairs, proper noun subjects, by-agent phrases, as well as conducting diachronic analysis on active and passive voice, short and long passive, and be- and get-passive, the study aims to answer the following research questions: i) How Russia and Ukraine are represented in the Western news media compared to the Russian news media? ii) How their agency and responsibility are delegated, and iii) How the usage of passive voice changes over time?

A combination of theoretical linguistic frameworks on passive voice and semantic roles, corpus linguistic methodologies, statistical measures, as well as natural language processing (NLP) methods, are employed. SpaCy parser is used to extract passive subject-verb pairs. Semantic map aids the categorization of words. Topic modeling reveals different topics within a corpus, and t-score and p-value are used as the measurements of collocational strengths.

The main findings include the representation of Russia as a malevolent actor in Western media both towards its own people and foreign citizens while Ukraine is represented as victims. The use of euphemism with Russia signals mechanistic dehumanization. In the Russian news, Russia is found to be associated with neutral and positive verbs. Regarding the assignment of responsibility, weapons are found to be used to perform violent actions while human agents are more often associated with restrictive or non-violent actions. The diachronic analysis indicates an increased usage of short and get passives but a gradual decrease of passive voice in general.

Acknowledgements

Upon the completion of my master's thesis, I would like to express my gratitude to my family and friends who gave moral support and useful comments. I feel thankful for the help of professors Miestamo Matti and Sinnemäki Kaius, as well as my supervisor, Yurayong Chingduang, who guided me through this extensive journey and contributed to vast improvements in many core aspects of my thesis. I would also like to thank academic advisors from Language Technology track that helped to refine the programming codes.

I am particularly grateful to the University of Helsinki for providing the resources, facilities, and a tuition fee scholarship that made this academic pursuit possible. My thesis would not have been completed without CSC's supercomputer Puhti (<https://www.puhti.csc.fi/>), which allowed me to experiment and run complex NLP analyses on large datasets almost without any limitations.

Last but not least, a special thanks to my colleagues at the university who introduced me to Overleaf, which made organizing and formatting this extensive work much smoother.

Thank you all.

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1 Introduction

Throughout history, we have witnessed the power of media wielded as a weapon in the hands of those seeking control. From the propaganda machines of totalitarian regimes to the carefully curated narratives of colonial powers, the manipulation of media has long been a tool for shaping public opinion. Take for example, the fervent propaganda campaigns of World War II, where governments from both sides utilized newspapers, radio broadcasts, and even film to sway hearts and minds. Whether it was the *demonization* of enemies or the *glorification* of national heroes, the media served as a conduit, molding perspectives and rallying support for war efforts.

PASSIVE VOICE constructions are a subtle yet potent instrument in this manipulation as [Kress & Hodge \(1979: 16\)](#) call it a tool to “transform the reality”. Unlike ACTIVE VOICE, where the SUBJECT performs an ACTION, PASSIVE VOICE often obscures the AGENT behind the ACTION, focusing instead on the ACTION itself or the RECIPIENT of the action. This syntactic choice can significantly influence how information is perceived, particularly in the context of CONFLICT AND WAR. For instance, the statement *Civilians were killed* does not specify “who” committed the act, thereby potentially downplaying the “perpetrator’s responsibility”. Conversely, an ACTIVE construction like *Soldiers killed civilians* assigns clear AGENCY and CULPABILITY. Literature review in the following chapter, however, entails more complex and nuanced distinctions between PASSIVE and ACTIVE VOICE affected by myriad of factors.

In the discourse surrounding the Russo-Ukrainian War, the deployment of PASSIVE VOICE constructions plays a crucial role in shaping narratives and influencing public perceptions. The media’s portrayal of events, actors, and actions through PASSIVE VOICE can either obscure or highlight RESPONSIBILITY and AGENCY, thus impacting the audience’s understanding of the conflict. This linguistic phenomenon warrants a detailed examination to uncover the underlying political and ideological currents that drive such representations.

This thesis is composed of the seven components: Theoretical Background, Datasets, Methods, Results and Analysis, Conclusion, and Discussions. The structure of the thesis is designed to explore various facets of PASSIVE VOICE usage and its implications on media representation. Given the extensive use of tables and visualizations to support the analysis, some have been moved to the appendices to ensure smoother reading. Links are provided to direct back and forth between the content and the relevant appendices. The details of the chapters are as follow.

The THEORETICAL BACKGROUND section establishes the foundation for the study by defining PASSIVE VOICE and examining the types of PASSIVE VOICE constructions, specifically distinguishing between BE-PASSIVE and GET-PASSIVE forms. It delves into the methodologies for counting frequencies, understanding terminologies, and identifying semantic roles. Additionally, it explores the FOCUS, USAGE, and TREND of passive constructions over time, providing a comprehensive understanding of their role in media discourse.

The DATASETS section describes the three main corpora used in the study in terms of their collection and preprocessing methods, as well as the statistics, including a number of sentences, words, and characters. The three corpora consist of the Ukraine War corpus, the Leipzig corpora, and selected Russian sources. Each corpus offers a unique perspective on the conflict, enabling a comprehensive analysis across different contexts.

The METHODS section explains the main methodologies employed to analyze the datasets. The NLP methods include using the spaCy parser to extract passive constructions, creating SEMANTIC MAP, and performing TOPIC MODELING to identify prevalent themes. Corpus linguistics methods involve COLLOCATION ANALYSIS and STATISTICAL ASSOCIATION MEASURES to examine the significance of word occurrences in the corpora.

The RESULTS AND ANALYSIS section is divided into four subsections. The “*Comparative Studies: Ukraine War Corpus vs. Leipzig Corpora*” subsection identifies significant passive subject-verb pairs and categories, comparing the categorization of subjects and verbs between the two corpora and examining the proportion of passive constructions in each. In this subsection, the proper nouns are also categorized and analyzed. The usage of these proper nouns over time are examined in the Leipzig corpora.

The “*Examination of Passive Voice in the Leipzig Corpora*” subsection seeks to understand the general trends of passive voice usage in news reporting, comparing ACTIVE and PASSIVE constructions, SHORT and LONG passives, BE and GET PASSIVE, and the main topics in news reports.

The “*Conceal and Highlight: BY-AGENT and MODIFIER Analysis*” subsection is dedicated to examining AGENCY AND RESPONSIBILITY through the analysis of the semantic roles of BY-AGENT and how RUSSIA and UKRAINE are used as a MODIFIER, SUBJECT, and AGENT.

Lastly, the “*Perspectives from Another Side: Russian News Sources*” subsection extends the analysis to Russian news sources, identifying popular topics and investigating BY-AGENT and MODIFIER.

The CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS sections discuss the findings, limitations of the spaCy parser, and the dominance of Anglo-Saxon media. It also reflects on the contributions of this study and proposes future research directions.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Definition

With its long history and popularity in the usage, PASSIVE VOICE carries a clear picture in its form and meaning. [Homan \(1989\)](#) provides a definition of PASSIVE VOICE as a clause that the logical object or affected entity is placed in the SUBJECT position while the LOGICAL SUBJECT or agentive entity is placed in the object position, as a pre-positionally linked noun occurring later in the sentence, i.e. after the VERB. This definition is comprehensive in that it includes two unique characteristics of PASSIVE VOICE after being transformed from an active voice. The first one is when the object of the active voice sentence is moved to the SUBJECT position of PASSIVE VOICE. The second one involves an optional agentive prepositional phrase, which refers to the SUBJECT of the active voice usually preceded by prepositions BY or WITH and placed after the VERB. See [Example 1a](#) and [Example 1b](#) below.

- (1) a. The flood destroyed the bridge. [ACTIVE VOICE]
b. The bridge *was destroyed* (by the flood). [PASSIVE VOICE]

One last distinct yet commonly known property of PASSIVE VOICE is the use of VERB TO BE and PAST PARTICIPLE as in [BE + V3]. This is the “core” of passive construction where the connotation of a SUBJECT in a PASSIVE VOICE clause being a RECIPIENT or an UNDERGOER of an action emerges. VERB TO BE in PASSIVE VOICE constructions can be replaced with certain copula or linking verbs, such as *get*, *remain*, and *stay*, which are syntactically equivalent to *verb to be*. (We will see in [Section 2.3](#) that BE and GET PASSIVE are semantically different.) See [Example 2](#) below.

- (2) a. The house was damaged.
b. The house remained damaged.

The use of copula verbs in [Example 2b](#) denotes a changing state or a condition with only a sheer level of action. The level of action in these non-typical passive constructions is less condensed than in BE PASSIVE ([Example 2a](#)) where a final state or an action *damaged* is more prominent. This is a semantically overlapping area where the two usages glide. The other end is where PAST

PARTICIPLES (V3) are perceived as adjectives either with COPULA VERBS or VERB TO BE as shown below.

- (3) a. The car remained broken.
- b. The car was broken.

In this context, *broken* is perceived more as a condition or a state while the sense of action *to break* barely exists. This subtly different interpretation can be attributed to the frequencies in usage that shape the sense perceived in each context.

2.2 Types of passives

Although it is clear what a PASSIVE VOICE entails and looks like, its structure can be varied. [Di Ferrante \(2023\)](#) classified PASSIVE VOICE into four categories based on syntactic and grammatical properties.

1. The first type of passive is BE PASSIVE. As the names suggest, BE PASSIVE has VERB TO BE as the main verb. According to [Leong \(2014\)](#), BE PASSIVE can be divided into seven subtypes: *basic*, *progressive*, *perfective*, *modal*, *modal perfective*, *to-infinitive*, and *non-finite -ing*. The seven subtypes are different in their forms. The details of each subtype are shown below.

1.1 BASIC (BE + V3)

- (4) The study also found that a positive chatbot experience was associated with customer loyalty.¹

1.2 PROGRESSIVE (BE + BEING + V3)

- (5) Lee and her colleagues set out to understand how they were being deployed throughout the social media universe.

1.3 PERFECTIVE (HAVE + BEEN + V3)

- (6) The report says that since 1970, large areas of land have been urbanized [...]

1.4 MODAL (MODAL + BE + V3)

- (7) It can be used to clean car headlights.

1.5 MODAL PERFECTIVE (MODAL + HAVE + BEEN + VEN)

- (8) Future studies could also investigate how materialistic values may have been affected [...].

1.6 TO-INFINITIVE (TO + BE + V3)

Types of passives

- (9) Temperature anomalies have also been found to be associated with moderate stunting in Ethiopia.

1.7 NON-FINITE -ING (BEING + V3)

- (10) [...] being exposed to more opposing views can actually increase political polarization.

2. The second type is GET PASSIVE, which are passive voices formed with get used as an auxiliary verb.

- (11) Uninsured children are still less likely to get vaccinated.

3. The third type of passives is BARE PASSIVES or passives without AUXILIARY VERB. This type is an abbreviated form of subordinating clause keeping only PAST PARTICIPLE as shown below.

- (12) a. The house flooded is on the mountain.
b. The house (*which was*) flooded is on the mountain.

The traction of transformability varies among different verbs when used in BARE PASSIVES. While most verbs can be converted back and forth naturally between FULL and ABBREVIATED forms, certain verbs, such as *involve*, *use*, *associate*, and *relate*, are more commonly found in an ABBREVIATED form.

- (13) a. The other attributes associated with customer satisfaction were through the same procedure as used in experiment 3.
b. The other attributes (?*which are*) associated with customer satisfaction were through the same procedure as (they are) used in experiment 3.

(A comment on the use of the ? symbol: This symbol is used to mark sentences that sound unnatural and inappropriate in a normal context. This symbol is not used to label incorrect grammar.)

[Hiltunen \(2016\)](#) refers to passive constructions that have an AUXILIARY VERB as VERBAL PASSIVE, in contrast to BARE PASSIVE that lacks AUXILIARY VERB.

4. The last type of passives is CONJOINED PASSIVES ([Leong 2014](#)). CONJOINED PASSIVES or COMPOUND PASSIVES are the PAST PARTICIPLE component that comes after a COORDINATING CONJUNCTION, and its AUXILIARY VERB is omitted.

- (14) When consumers *are* either *primed* with a general sense of nontraditional product functionality... or explicitly fixated on the traditional functionality of a product...

In this example, the COMPOUND PASSIVE construction is fixed, which is linked to the main BE-PASSIVE *are primed* by the CONJUNCTION *or*.

A less typical passive is MIDDLE VOICE or MEDIOPASSIVE (also referred to as MIDDLE by Keenan & Dryer (2007: 352) and ANTICAUSATIVE by Zúñiga & Kittilä (2019: 41)). MIDDLE VOICE conveys the sense of PASSIVE VOICE in that the action is done by an external entity, not the SUBJECT of the sentence, but MIDDLE VOICE lacks the PASSIVE VOICES [BE+V3] component. MIDDLE VOICE clause is, therefore, expressed in the ACTIVE VOICE form but with the sense of PASSIVE VOICE.

- (15) a. The car won't start. [MIDDLE VOICE]
 b. The car cannot be started. [PASSIVE VOICE]

In the examples above, the car cannot *start* itself, so the sense of the sentence is in PASSIVE [THE CAR CANNOT BE STARTED]. However, it becomes common to say *the car won't start* in a simpler ACTIVE VOICE structure.

Zúñiga & Kittilä (2019) propose the motivation of using MIDDLE VOICE that a writer or a speaker may use it to escape one's own responsibility for a given event or to avoid accusing someone else directly for something that has happened. This proposal does not separate MIDDLE VOICE from PASSIVE VOICE (as Zúñiga & Kittilä also note) because both constructions can leave out AGENT (optional in PASSIVE VOICE). In other words, as we will see in Section 2.8 about the usage, one of the motivations of using PASSIVE VOICE is when a speaker or a writer desires to omit the AGENT. The point that actually differentiates MIDDLE VOICE from PASSIVE VOICE mentioned by Haspelmath et al. (2004: 1132-3) is that MIDDLE VOICE completely eradicates AGENT (syntactically and semantically) but PASSIVE VOICE implies the existence of AGENT even though not being stated. However, only the verbs that refer to the actions performed without any specific instruments or methods can be used in middle voice, so that they can be thought of as happening spontaneously, without a (human) agent's intervention (Haspelmath et al. 2004).

I also propose that whenever possible, MIDDLE VOICE is chosen (rather than PASSIVE VOICE) out of the EASE OF USE criteria. Being an unmarked feature, MIDDLE VOICE is easier to produce as in *The ship sank*. and *The vase broke*. rather than *The ship was sunk*. and *The vase was broken*.

Di Ferrante (2023) considers MIDDLE VOICE and GET PASSIVE to be less typical passive from the BE PASSIVE. In fact, the previous examples show that GET PASSIVE is more similar to BE PASSIVE than MIDDLE VOICE both grammatically and semantically.

2.3 Be passive and get passive

The unique properties of GET PASSIVE attract many scholars to examine them. There are three main views towards GET PASSIVE. Firstly, they are seen as informal, colloquial, and inelegant. Secondly, they cannot be used entirely interchangeably with BE PASSIVE. Lastly, they portray distinctive connotations.

2.3.1 Informality

GET PASSIVE is seen as a trait of spoken language that are found to be used in colloquial and informal texts (Biber & Gray 2016; Xiao et al. 2006; cited in Plecháčková, Jana 2007; Leech & Svartvik 2002: 346; Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019: 100). On these grounds, Di Ferrante (2023) posits that GET PASSIVE does not substitute BE PASSIVE.

Example 16 and Example 17 below prove that GET PASSIVE cannot be used interchangeably with BE PASSIVE in a formal context (Example 17), but the choice becomes arbitrary in an informal environment (Example 16). CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTION: GET/HAVE SOMETHING DONE, where GET is used with PAST PARTICIPLE with the sense of PASSIVE VOICE, helps to illustrate this observation.

(16) [INFORMAL]

- a. A car was washed by a man.
- b. A man got a car washed.
- c. A car got washed by a man.

(17) [FORMAL]

- a. A law was passed by the Cabinet.
- b. ?The Cabinet got a law passed.
- c. ?The law got passed by the Cabinet.

The examples above demonstrate the transformation between BE PASSIVE, GET CAUSATIVE, and GET PASSIVE in order to examine the use of GET PASSIVE in a FORMAL and INFORMAL contexts. Even though GET CAUSATIVE carries a little different sense than BE- and GET-PASSIVE in that CAUSATIVE CONSTRUCTION presume the action to be executed by someone else rather than the SUBJECT, Example 16 is totally interchangeable due to the informality of language use. However, among Example 17 with a formal context, GET PASSIVE sounds unnatural and incompatible. This proves that GET PASSIVE is commonly and naturally used in an INFORMAL context and cannot substitute BE PASSIVE in a FORMAL context.

Chappell (1984: 169) offers a historical and more complex analysis. Chappell speculates that earlier grammarians in the 19th and early 20th century tend to view GET PASSIVE as vulgar and colloquial (see Rice 1932 cited in Chappell 1984). Later grammarians, such as Jespersen and Curme, start to characterize the difference between GET- and BE-PASSIVE, though the colloquial sense still persisted.

2.3.2 Functional properties

2.3.2.1 Dynamic-stative contrast

Jespersen (1949) and Curme (1931) find that GET PASSIVE encodes a shift of state while BE PASSIVE simply entails a state or condition. In other words, GET PASSIVE is used to express a DYNAMIC-STATIC contrast between PAST PARTICIPLE and ADJECTIVE. Outside of this usage, Jespersen and Curme conclude, GET PASSIVE carries a colloquial sense. Jespersen (1949 cited in Chappell 1984) provides an example where GET is able to distinguish STATE from TRANSITION.

- (18) a. At that time, he was not married. [BE PASSIVE]
b. He got married in 1920. [GET PASSIVE]

In Example 18, auxiliary GET is able to distinguish *married* used as ADJECTIVE signifying a STATE in the first sentence from *married* as PAST PARTICIPLE in Example 18a marking a TRANSITION from being *unmarried*.

2.3.3 Semantic connotations

Scholars often associate GET PASSIVE with good or bad reflection, emotional involvement, sympathy, and agency. The first three connotations can be grouped as PERSONAL connotations.

2.3.3.1 Good or bad reflection

Hatcher (1949 cited in Chappell 1984) posits that GET is used in only two circumstances: to signify the feeling of having either fortunate or unfortunate consequences for the subject. Lakoff (1971 cited in Chappell 1984) has a similar view that GET is frequently used to reflect the ATTITUDE whether the events are ‘good or bad’ or reflect ‘well or poorly’ on the subject. This connotation can also be called EVALUATIVE ATTITUDE. This type of connotation may be transferred from the use of GET TO BE in ACTIVE voice.

- (19) a. We are here. [BE ACTIVE VOICE]
b. We get to be here. [GET ACTIVE VOICE]

- (20) a. Jane was invited to the party. [BE PASSIVE VOICE]
b. Jane got invited to the party. [GET PASSIVE VOICE]

Example 19b uses GET TO BE in ACTIVE VOICE to reflect that *get to be here* is either good or bad for a speaker or a writer while BE PASSIVE in **Example 19a** is more neutral and declarative. This EVALUATIVE ATTITUDE connotation of GET PASSIVE is carried through to PASSIVE VOICE as seen in **Example 20b**, where the fact that *Jane got invited to the party* is either good or bad for a speaker or a writer. BE PASSIVE in **Example 20a**, on the other hand, does not carry such connotation.

2.3.3.2 Emotional involvement

In addition, **Hatcher** and **Lakoff** also discover an interesting property of GET PASSIVE that it conveys the notion of ‘responsibility’ or ‘active involvement’ of the subject. **Lakoff** points out the OBJECTIVE-AFFECTIVE contrast between BE and GET PASSIVE as follows:

“If we think of... an item on a news program... (where a reporter will at least try to present the appearance of (the) objectivity toward the news being reported), GET will be very odd, and BE normal, indicating that the speaker has no feelings about what took place...”

- (21) a. My cache of marijuana got found by Fido the police dog.
b. A cache of Marijuana was found by Fido the police dog.

In **Example 21a**, the sense of the speaker’s involvement in the action and his unhappiness with it are very clear.

Lakoff concludes that GET PASSIVE often suggests the active involvement, emotional, or otherwise, of the superficial subject... (1971:160). Therefore, it can be assumed that GET PASSIVE is used to convey SUBJECTIVITY.

2.3.3.3 Sympathy

The first two connotations – reflective attitude and emotional involvement – assumes that something is either good or bad for a writer or a speaker, but when they feel bad about something, GET PASSIVE is used to convey SYMPATHY.

Chappell (1984) uses the following example to explain this distinction and not included in **Lakoff (1971)**’s terminology.

- (22) Che Guevara got assassinated.

In [Example 22](#) and [Example 23](#), a subject and a speaker are not the same person, so subject's EMOTIONAL INVOLVEMENT cannot be assumed. In this case, [Chappell](#) proposes that GET PASSIVE allows a speaker to make an INFERENCE of a NEGATIVE nature about the subject, and this links back to the good and bad reflection mentioned in [Section 2.3.3.1](#) but on the subject, instead of the speaker.

Some similar examples can be commonly found in news media as follow:

- (23) a. People got killed.
b. People got injured.

Alternative views see GET PASSIVE convey only NEGATIVE connotations in the written language ([Xiao et al. 2006](#)) or are NEUTRAL with no adversitive effect on the SUBJECT in a spoken data ([Villalibre 2015](#)).

2.3.3.4 Agency

In GET PASSIVE, SUBJECT is perceived as having more “control, instigation or responsibility” in the “resulting situation” than BE PASSIVE where SUBJECT is purely an UNDERGOER ([Chappell 1984](#); [Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019](#): 100). GET PASSIVE, therefore, implies that SUBJECT has a certain level of AGENCY that can affects the end result. Consequently, [Chappell](#) suggests that if the speaker [or the writer] considers the subject an “innocent victim” of circumstances, and if the subject is thought of as “completely” under the control of another person, and consequently has no choice but to do whatever is desired by AGENT, then GET PASSIVE is NOT appropriate, and BE PASSIVE must be used instead.

- (24) a. Half of the population of [Cambodia] WAS / ?GOT systematically annihilated under the Pol Pot regime.
b. Vietnamese women and children WERE / ?GOT massacred in the My Lai offensive.
c. Seven slaves WERE / ?GOT bought.
d. Germany WAS / ?GOT forced to surrender.

The use of BE PASSIVE in [Example 24](#) is more appropriate as the sentences suppose the subjects *Half of the population of Cambodia* and *Vietnamese women and children* are innocent victims, and *Seven slaves* and *Germany* do not have any control over the outcomes.

However, it can be observed that this connotation only applies to ANIMATE or, more strictly, HUMAN entities because INANIMATE entities do not have AGENCY in the first place.

By looking back together with the first three connotations, if GET PASSIVE is used in [Example 24](#), it can mean that a speaker or a writer intends to express the FEELING of sorrow and the SYMPATHY that the situations are unfortunate.

2.4 Counting frequencies

Many previous studies on PASSIVE VOICE have been conducted to observe the frequencies of its usage, either by counting manually or using part-of-speech taggers like CLAWS (Garside & Smith 1997). Di Ferrante (2023) recognizes the challenges in extracting all types of passives, which lead many linguists to resort to manual counting methods, resulting in a limited corpus size and generalizability issue of the findings. More robust and customizable modern tools, such as text parsers, enable more flexibility to capture various types of PASSIVE based on POS (part-of-speech) and dependency tagging features; however, these tools do require a certain level of a programming skill. Another robust and effective method may involve using machine learning to train a model to classify PASSIVE VOICE constructions.

The counting of PASSIVE VOICE frequencies varies in terms of types, units, and measurements. More typical passives like the BE-PASSIVE are generally included, while less typical forms like BARE PASSIVE and COMPOUND PASSIVE are often excluded due to challenges in extracting. Some studies analyze the total number of clauses or only the past participles in passive constructions, while others consider the entire passive verbal phrases. Units of measurement, even normalized ones, can cause difficulties in cross-study comparisons. While ‘*per million*’ is widely recognized as the standard measurement of word frequencies, many scholars prefer ‘*per 100k*’ or ‘*per thousand*’ for their datasets.

2.5 Terminologies

In the past studies of passives, several related terms are used, and it is necessary to explore these terms and set the understanding for the later usage throughout this study. There are two main groups of passive-related terms: BY-AGENT, as well as GRAMMATICAL and LOGICAL SUBJECT and OBJECT.

2.5.1 By-agent

The most diverse term in the grammatical division refers to BY-AGENT used by Hundt (2004), for example. BY-AGENT consists of preposition BY + AGENT or DOER. AGENT denotes “the source of action” (Anderson 1998) and comes after BY in a BY-AGENT prepositional phrase.

(25) The man was injured by the police.

Comrie (1988) and Keenan & Dryer (2007: 342) call this component AGENT PHRASE while Katz (2006) comes up with more details as PROPOSITIONAL AGENT PHRASE. The most detailed terminology could be WITH- or BY-AGENTIVE PREPOSITIONAL PHRASE.

When BY-AGENT is present, the whole clause is called AGENTFUL PASSIVE by [Anisfeld & Klenbort \(1973\)](#) and AGENTIVE CLAUSE by [Areibi & Al-Mijrab \(2012\)](#). This links to the length-based terminology: FULL PASSIVE and LONG PASSIVE ([Miller 2016](#)).

On the contrary, in a similar manner, when BY-AGENT is not present, [Miller](#) uses SHORT PASSIVE. This AGENTLESS PASSIVE CLAUSE is called TRUNCATED PASSIVE or DELETED AGENT STRUCTURE by [Homan \(1989\)](#), NON-AGENTIVE constructions by [Chappell \(1984\)](#), and AGENTLESS PASSIVE by [Comrie \(1988\)](#) and [Areibi & Al-Mijrab \(2012\)](#).

2.5.2 Grammatical and logical subject and object

SUBJECT and OBJECT in PASSIVE clauses can be categorized based on grammatical and semantic criteria. LOGICAL SUBJECT and OBJECT are identified by their semantic roles, while GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT and OBJECT are identified by their syntactic positions within the clause. Consider the following examples:

- (26) a. The army destroyed *the bridge*. [ACTIVE VOICE]
 b. *The bridge* was destroyed by the army. [PASSIVE VOICE]

In ACTIVE clause, such as [Example 26a](#), there is no repositioning of the SUBJECT and VERB, making the terms straightforward: *the army* is both GRAMMATICAL and LOGICAL SUBJECT, and *the bridge* is both GRAMMATICAL and LOGICAL OBJECT. However, in [Example 26b](#), *the bridge* becomes GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT while remaining to be LOGICAL OBJECT, and *the army* is LOGICAL SUBJECT. PASSIVE clauses do not have GRAMMATICAL OBJECT because they do not follow the SUBJECT-VERB-OBJECT (SVO) structure typical of ACTIVE clauses.

2.6 Semantic roles

LOGICAL SUBJECT and GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT in passive voice clauses can have different semantic roles. Three similar pairs of semantic roles are presented: AGENTIVE and INSTRUMENTAL, UNDERGOER and EXPERIENCER, and RECEIPIENT and BENEFICIARY.

2.6.1 Agentive VS Instrumental

The most typical semantic role of LOGICAL SUBJECT of passive clauses are AGENTIVE and INSTRUMENTAL. The semantic roles of the component in PREPOSITIONAL PHRASE in PASSIVE clauses, which follow the propositions BY or WITH, can be classified into two main types: AGENTIVE and INSTRUMENTAL. [Quirk et al. \(1989\)](#) offer the definitions that AGENTIVE refers to the

ANIMATE being instigating or causing the happening denoted by VERB, and INSTRUMENT represents the entity, generally INANIMATE, which an AGENTIVE uses to perform or investigate a process. With the creative and figurative style, many language users may argue with [Quirk et al.](#)'s (1989) definitions that AGENT can also be INANIMATE entities as in *The paper is burnt with fire*. [Anderson \(1998\)](#) provides a concise yet accurate description of AGENT as “a source of the action”.

- (27) a. A man was arrested by an authority.
b. A man was arrested with a cuff.

An *authority* in [Example 27a](#) has an AGENTIVE semantic role as a performer of action *arrest*, and *a cuff* in [Example 27b](#) takes an INSTRUMENTAL semantic role because it is used as a tool to perform the action.

A PASSIVE clause can have both AGENTIVE and INSTRUMENTAL prepositional phrases as in:

- (28) A man was arrested by an authority with a cuff.

The order of an AGENTIVE before an INSTRUMENTAL is more sensible than the other way round as DOER is mentioned before TOOL. It can be observed from [Example 28](#) that AGENTIVE are used with the preposition BY, and INSTRUMENTAL follows the preposition WITH.

AGENTIVE in many cases can also be an INANIMATE entity that carries the semantic role as the source of action as in the example below.

- (29) The remains were brought ashore by the waves.

The waves is not a living entity but is the one that brought *the remains* to the shore.

The choice to use BY or WITH often depends on the intended meaning or the norm, which can differ from the typical use of BY for AGENTIVE and WITH for INSTRUMENTAL criteria.

- (30) The remains were brought ashore with the waves.

In this example, using the preposition WITH shifts the semantic meaning of *the waves* away from the typical AGENTIVE role towards a more LOCATIVE role, specifying the location or means. [Keenan & Dryer \(2007: 342\)](#) note that the agent phrase marker [“by”] in English is independently used with LOCATIVE force.

The prepositions BY and WITH can be used to indicate other semantic roles, such as locative, as seen in [Example 30](#). These uses may be less related to passive voice constructions, which typically focus on the action or the source of the action.

2.6.2 Undergoer VS Experiencer

Another pair of semantic roles highly related to passive voice are UNDERGOER and EXPERIENCER. UNDERGOER denotes an entity affected by the action, also commonly referred to as PATIENT, while EXPERIENCER is an entity that feels or perceives something. UNDERGOER is inherent to the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT of PASSIVE clauses. EXPERIENCER, on the other hand, can be found in both GRAMMATICAL and LOGICAL SUBJECT.

- (31) a. The decision was made.
 b. The sound waves were felt by all residents.
 c. Villagers were frightened by the storm.

In [Example 31a](#), *the decision* is UNDERGOER affected by the action *to make*. The latter two examples show demonstrate EXPERIENCER in two positions. The EXPERIENCER in [Example 31b](#) is *all residents* who feels *the sound waves*, and it is *villagers* in [Example 31c](#) who feel *frightened*. EXPERIENCER in [Example 31b](#) falls on BY-PHRASE while in [Example 31c](#), it pertains to GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT.

The third scenario where the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT is EXPERIENCER occurs when SPECIAL VERBS are used. This group of verbs includes verbs like *tire*, *bore*, *embarrass*, *disturb*, *scare*, *convince*, *disappoint*, and *satisfy*, which can manifest in three ways:

1. In an ADJECTIVAL GERUND form functioning as COMPLEMENT encoding STATE, QUALITY, or CONDITION, of an entity as in *It is interesting*. and *The food is satisfying*.
2. In an PAST PARTICIPLE form signifying FEELING or EMOTIONAL STATE of an entity as in *I was impressed by the show*. and *There is a frightened child in the room*.
3. As a TRANSITIVE VERB as in *The story convinced me*. and *The audience excites my speech*.

When used in passive voice, SPECIAL VERB assigns EXPERIENCER semantic role to the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT.

- (32) All residents were *disturbed* by the sound waves.

Similar to [Example 31b](#), *all residents* in [Example 32](#) above is also an EXPERIENCER, but the semantic role is assigned to SUBJECT position, instead of OBJECT, due to the use of SPECIAL VERB *to disturb*.

EXPERIENCER can be identified with PERCEPTION VERB like *hear*, *see*, *feel*, and *enjoy*; however, PERCEPTION VERB can be used figuratively, and the context needs to be taken into account when determining a semantic role.

- (33) a. Economic benefits will be felt by *all Brazilian society*.

- b. The higher balances were predominantly enjoyed by *mid- and high-income families*.

In [Example 33](#), PERCEPTION VERB *feel* and *enjoy* are used metaphorically to actually signify that an entity is benefited from *the economic event*. Therefore, *all Brazilian society* and *mid- and high-income families* are considered BENEFICIARY, not EXPERIENCER.

BENEFICIARY, together with its similar role, RECIPIENT, is explained in the following section.

2.6.3 Recipient VS Beneficiary

RECIPIENT is semantically close to BENEFICIARY, but both have a slightly different property. [Kittilä \(2005\)](#) describes the distinction between the RECIPIENT and BENEFICIARY as follows:

“The role of RECIPIENT was defined on the basis of events which inherently involve an entity that receives a thing transferred to its sphere of control. BENEFICIARIES, in turn, benefit from events without receiving anything concrete.”

Take for example:

- (34) a. A family was offered a house.
b. A family was granted asylum status.

A *family* in [Example 34a](#) is a RECIPIENT because it was given a CONCRETE entity, *a house*, but in [Example 34b](#), *a family* has a BENEFACTIVE semantic role as it benefits from receiving *asylum status*, which is not a CONCRETE entity.

2.7 Focus

There are three main perspectives regarding what PASSIVE clauses focus on differently compared to the ACTIVE ones: verbs, last element, and GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT.

2.7.1 Focus on verbs

The first viewpoint sees that passive voice emphasizes VERB but as a RESULTATIVE STATE, not the ACTION itself. [McKerrow \(1978 cited in Homan 1989\)](#) makes an interesting statement about the use of passive voice in everyday language as follows:

“If in ordinary conversation we use the phrase *the boy was kicked by a horse*, we are not thinking, as a rule, of the action of *kicking*, but of the hurt done to the boy. In fact, consideration will show that the use of the PASSIVE construction in ordinary speech is almost

restricted to occasions when what really concerns us is the condition of something or other due to something else, and not the action itself.”

On these grounds, [Homan](#) concludes that ACTIVE and PASSIVE representations of a proposition do not mean the same thing; if the passive voice approximates any other GRAMMATICAL FORM, it is more likely an ADJECTIVAL STATE of being.

[Haspelmath et al. \(2004\)](#) and [Zúñiga & Kittilä \(2019: 43\)](#) specifically refer to this type of passive where AGENT is completely backgrounded as AGENTLESS RESULTATIVE constructions.

[Berry \(1975: 160\)](#) provides a more nuanced distinction that if a speaker decides to leave the ACTOR implicit, the PROCESS or the VERB is emphasized. Conversely, if an ACTOR is made explicit by the use of AGENTIVE phrase, a speaker or a writer intends to emphasize the ACTOR.

2.7.2 Focus on the last element

Actually, according to the second group of scholars, the sentence *The boy was kicked by a horse*, that [McKerrow](#) uses may not be the best example to exemplify the FOCUS of passive voice because this group of scholars sees that the emphasis of PASSIVE clauses, in fact, of any sentences, is “at the end”. Therefore, for a PASSIVE clause that ends with BY-AGENT, the FOCUS should fall at the BY-AGENT.

[Anisfeld & Klenbort \(1973\)](#) analyze passive voice sentences based on the PRESUPPOSITION PRINCIPLE ([Halliday & Matthiessen 2013](#); [Chomsky 1972](#)) and the intonation of speech of passive voice. [Anisfeld & Klenbort](#) come to the same conclusion that the emphasis of an AGENTFUL passive sentence is on the BY-AGENT. The example sentence is as follow:

(35) The principal had been angered by the parent.

In this sentence, the FOCUS is at *by the parent*, and the rest that comes before is PRESUPPOSITION. Regarding the intonation, [Anisfeld & Klenbort](#) observe that under normal circumstances, the last word in each of these PASSIVE sentences receives major phonetic stress.

This observation conforms to what [Chomsky \(1972\)](#) proposes that the phrase containing the intonation center (which usually receives major phonetic stress) be considered the assertional FOCUS of the sentence and PRESUPPOSITION of the sentence be defined as the proposition resulting from the replacement of the FOCUS by a variable. [Chomsky](#) uses two sentences below to further illustrate.

- (36) a. Did John give the book to Bill?
 b. Did John give Bill the book?

The PRESUPPOSITION of [Example 36a](#) would be that John gave the book to *someone* and that of [Example 36b](#) would be that John gave Bill *something*.

With the same point of view, [Gopen \(2014\)](#) states that the stress position of a sentence happens at every PERIOD and any properly used COLON or SEMICOLON. The example from [Chomsky](#) urges that the punctuation list include also a QUESTION MARK.

[Miller \(2016\)](#), on the other hand, looks at FULL PASSIVE and observes that FULL PASSIVE pushes BY-AGENT to be peripheral and more distant.

2.7.3 Focus is on subject of passive sentences

The last group of stances advocates that the FOCUS of PASSIVE clauses is on the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT. [de Bourbon et al. \(2022\)](#) agree with this viewpoint based on the fact that passive voice OBJECT-VERB-SUBJECT order is derived from swapping the OBJECT in the SUBJECT-VERB-OBJECT active voice structure to the SUBJECT position in the passive voice. [Fowler \(1977\)](#) cited in [Homan 1989](#)) sees that this viewpoint holds true for SHORT PASSIVE where BY-AGENT is omitted. [Fowler](#) states that syntactical structures have the ability to guide the reader into a particular cognitive orientation toward sentence content. In regard to TRUNCATED PASSIVE, [Fowler](#) continues, AGENT deletion permits a “discreet silence” about the performer of the action ([1986](#)), and that the impression would be given of a “central participant” to whom things happened as opposed to who had things done to him ([1977](#)).

This SUBJECT-FOCUS viewpoint led by the omission of BY-AGENT generates a subtle sense of “intentional ambiguity” that downplays the responsibility of the DOER, who performs (most of the time, malicious) actions, and shifts the FOCUS to the RECIPIENT of the action instead. [Homan \(1989\)](#) analogizes television newscasts to the situations where the information is presented rapidly in comparison to newspapers where readers have time to contemplate the content. [Homan](#) uses this analogy to demonstrate the necessity for the audience to critically comprehend the complexity of information. Part of that is to recognize the absence of BY-AGENT in PASSIVE clauses and what the “consequential effects” it brings.

In the context of violence against women (VAW), [Katz \(2006\)](#) believes that even in FULL PASSIVE, BY-AGENT gains less attention than the SUBJECT itself. [Katz](#) proposes that in PASSIVE sentences that do not end with a VERB, an emphasis is put on the SUBJECT. A common example in this context is:

(37) A woman is raped by a man.

According to [Katz](#), the emphasis of this sentence is on SUBJECT, *a woman*, rather than the AGENT, *a man*.

Ferreira (2021) also finds that the emphasis of a sentence is on the HUMAN SUBJECT when used with a SPECIAL VERB as in *I was impressed by the results*.

The agency connotation of GET PASSIVE splits the interpretation of this group onto two layers as GET PASSIVE does not depict GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT as an INNOCENT VICTIM, but an entity with a certain level of AGENCY or CONTROL over the end result.

2.8 Usage

The usage of passive voice can serve five main purposes: linking actions, handling unknown, irrelevant, or self-evident subjects, maintaining tact, emphasizing objects, and enhancing sentence structure and cohesion. The first four points are based on Jespersen's model (1933 cited in Homan), and the last point is mentioned by Connatser (2004), Baratta (2009), and Ferreira (2021).

2.8.1 Linking sentences

The first usage of passive voice is to connect two actions. This is similar to CONJOINED or COMPOUND passive type mentioned earlier in Section 2.2 where both PAST PARTICIPLES linked with a CONJUNCTION are in passive voice. This usage is more general in that it connects two actions regardless of voice.

(38) John *woke up* and was called to breakfast by his mother.

In this example, the PASSIVE *was called* is used to effectively pack the information within one sentence while managing to maintain the differentiation that *John* is a LOGICAL SUBJECT for the VERB *to wake* (as he woke up by himself) but a LOGICAL OBJECT for *to call*. If *John* is the LOGICAL OBJECT for both actions, a COMPOUND PASSIVE can come in handy.

(39) John was woken up and called to breakfast by his mother.

2.8.2 Handling unknown, irrelevant, or self-evident logical subjects

Another primary usage of passive voice is when the AGENT is unknown, insignificant, or self-evident (Svartvik 1966; Anisfeld & Klenbort 1973; Connatser 2004; Zúñiga & Kittilä 2019: 90). Palmer (1965: 65) even states that this usage of passive voice is “the only one obvious and clear reason”. Jenkins (2003) uses an opposite scenario to endorse this view stating writers often use the ACTIVE voice when the identity of the LOGICAL SUBJECT is “known”.

(40) He was killed while on holiday.

The example above presumes that the speaker or writer “does not know” who *the killer* is.

A subcategory under this usage is where the LOGICAL SUBJECT is self-evident from the context, making it unnecessary to explicitly state it.

(41) She was elected president of the club.

[Example 41](#) assumes that the context provides sufficient information about the AGENT. This usage is explained by [Poutsma \(1926\)](#) and [Evans & Evans \(1957\)](#), who argue that the AGENT can be omitted without losing essential information. [Homan \(1989\)](#) also concludes that the primary use of the passive voice is to avoid the difficulty of COLLECTIVE AGENTS.

2.8.3 Maintaining tact

Passive voice can also be employed out of TACT or DELICACY, omitting the AGENT to avoid sensitive issues or to maintain politeness.

(42) The secret was revealed.

It is obvious that mentioning the AGENT in this example might be undesirable. This usage is highlighted by [Zandvoort \(1972: 53\)](#), [Evans & Evans \(1957\)](#), and [Comrie \(1977\)](#), who note that passive constructions can help to “conceal the agent’s identity” for various reasons.

[Zúñiga & Kittilä \(2019: 90\)](#) note that POLITENESS also involves strategies to avoid face-threatening situations, which can include avoiding DIRECT REFERENCE to the AGENT to prevent implicating or offending them. See [Example 43](#) below.

- (43) a. You forgot to send the report. [ACTIVE VOICE]
b. The report was not sent. [PASSIVE VOICE]

2.8.4 Emphasizing logical objects

Passive voice is often used when the LOGICAL OBJECT attracts greater attention than the LOGICAL SUBJECT.

(44) The killer was sentenced by the court.

In [Example 44](#), *the killer* is emphasized over *the court*. [Homan \(1989\)](#) further analyzes this scenario and mentions this usage may be motivated by the fact that...

- i) the speaker finds the LOGICAL OBJECT more interesting than the LOGICAL SUBJECT,
- ii) the speaker wishes the listener to focus on the LOGICAL OBJECT, or
- iii) both.

Anisfeld & Klenbort (1973) and Connatser (2004) also support this usage, noting that passive voice can enhance the “prominence” of the LOGICAL OBJECT.

2.8.5 Enhancing sentence structure and cohesion

Additional guidelines for using passive voice involve SENTENCE STRUCTURE AND COHESION. The scholars who endorse this usage group see passive voice as a tool to “manipulate sentence structure” to achieve a more cohesive discourse or a desirable flow of information that helps guide the reader to follow the text from one idea to another.

Connatser (2004) suggests three scenarios where passive voice should be used:

- i) when the ACTION is more significant than the AGENT,
- ii) when the repetitive mention of the actor must be “avoided” to help maintain the reader’s “focus” and prevent distraction, and
- iii) to create a smoother sentence structure, avoiding cumbersome left-branching series that place too much information between SUBJECT and VERB.

To illustrate the first scenario where ACTION is more important than AGENT, see the following example:

(45) A decision was made to proceed.

In Example 45, the focus is on ACTION that something “was decided” rather than “who did it”. This aligns with the “focus” on verb view mentioned earlier.

For the second scenario where repetitive mention of the actor must be “avoided” to maintain the reader’s “focus” and prevent distraction, the example could be:

(46) The researchers conducted the experiment, the researchers analyzed the results, and the researchers published the findings.

Using passive voice can streamline the text as follows:

(47) The experiment was conducted, the results were analyzed, and the findings were published.

The second sentence, without the repetitive mention of the researchers, is more concise and focused. In fact, a more “logical” solution would be to simply remove unnecessary mention of the AGENT, instead of changing voice unnecessarily as shown below.

- (48) The researchers conducted the experiment, analyzed the results, and published the findings.

Using passive voice in the second scenario has a more prominent effect than avoiding distraction; passive voice deviates the focus to the LOGICAL OBJECT, *the experiment*, *the results*, and *the findings*. This redundant-actor-removal purpose may not be the strongest reason to use passive voice as the desirable result can be (more logically) achieved using active voice as well.

The last scenario proposed by [Connatser](#) is to use passive voice to avoid cumbersome left-branching series that place too much information between the SUBJECT and the VERB. Take the two sentences below as an example:

- (49) a. The team [with extensive experience and numerous successful projects] made a decision. [ACTIVE VOICE]
b. A decision was made [by the team with extensive experience and numerous successful projects]. [PASSIVE VOICE]

[Example 49a](#) in active voice is heavily left-branching with the SUBJECT *team* being modified with a long prepositional phrase *with extensive...projects*. This adds a distance between SUBJECT and VERB and makes it difficult to read. [Example 49b](#) employs passive voice to shift the long logical subject and its modifier *the team with...projects* to the BY-PHRASE at the end of the sentence while maintaining the same content and keeping the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT *a decision* and VERB closer to each other. This structural adjustment results in a more easy-to-understand discourse.

[Ferreira \(2021\)](#) mentions an additional scenario where passive voice facilitates CONCEPTUAL ACCESSIBILITY or referred to as the EASY-FIRST STRATEGY by [MacDonald \(2013\)](#). [Ferreira](#) exemplifies this point with an experiment; when participants were primed with the word *worship*, they were more likely to produce the PASSIVE sentence *A church is being struck by lightning*, rather than the ACTIVE *Lightning struck the church*. [Ferreira](#) further notes that syntactic structure of passive voice can also enforce the GIVEN-NEW INFORMATION STRATEGY ([Haviland & Clark 1974](#)), enhancing clarity by following a “logical” information flow.

- (50) The management introduced the new policy last week. It was met with enthusiasm by the employees.

In this example, passive voice is used so that the first element in the second sentence *it* links to the last element of the first sentence *the new policy*. The pronoun *it* constitutes a GIVEN INFOR-

MATION, which is logically placed before a NEW INFORMATION. In this case, the NEW INFORMATION is the rest that comes after. This GIVEN-NEW INFORMATION STRATEGY is similar to the FOCUS-PRESUPPOSITION PRINCIPLE mentioned in [Halliday & Matthiessen \(2013\)](#) and [Chomsky \(1972\)](#), as well as the THEME AND RHEME PRINCIPLE in [Baratta \(2009\)](#), where PRESUPPOSITION or THEME represent GIVEN INFORMATION and precede FOCUS or RHEME.

Although these principles are a powerful tool to achieve an easy-to-follow discourse, in real usage, it is not always possible to follow “logical” arrangement of information in this manner where GIVEN INFORMATION always comes first followed by NEW INFORMATION, and the focus of a sentence is not always on the NEW INFORMATION. There are many factors that govern how the information is encoded into a discourse. The mobility of FOCUS within a sentence explained in [Section 2.7](#) supports this argument well.

2.9 Trend

Similar to the social acceptability of GET PASSIVE explained earlier, PASSIVE VOICE itself went through highs and lows. It can be observed from the previously mentioned literature that the complex analysis of PASSIVE VOICE did not emerge until the mid-20th century, which is the same period when GET-PASSIVE began to be examined more critically. However, this can only serve as a speculative indicator of the change in perspective. This section is specifically dedicated to investigating the attitudes towards PASSIVE VOICE throughout history based on explicit statements.

The usage of PASSIVE VOICE in academia did not become popular until the 18th century. Before that, active voice was used together with FIRST PERSON PRONOUN to give a feeling of “credibility” to the early “gentleman- scientists” ([Atkinson 1996](#) cited in [Dumin 2010](#)). At that time, scientists shared their knowledge and ideas in the form of circulating letters among a small group of people, and it was important to emphasize they conducted the experiments and discovered the results themselves. In the 18th century, scientific text began to change; language became more simplified, and PASSIVE VOICE was used more often ([Atkinson 1996](#); [Montgomery 1996](#) cited in [Dumin 2010](#)).

Continuing to the end of the 20th century and the early 21st century, the opinion towards PASSIVE VOICE diverged. [Seoane & Loureiro-Porto \(2005\)](#) suggest the usage declined throughout the 20th century while [Homan \(1989\)](#) points out that PASSIVE VOICE is substantially acceptable in academic work to express objectivity. Some scholars heavily criticize PASSIVE VOICE for its ambiguity, emotionally demoting effect, downplay of agency and responsibility, and in the worst case, concealment of truth and distortion of justice. Others, on the other hand, attempt to defend PASSIVE VOICE and suggest a more critical and mindful usage.

Although the work of [Seoane & Loureiro-Porto \(2005\)](#) provide a useful framework to analyze the usage of PASSIVE VOICE, the size of corpus is limited to only 110k each across the three time periods (1905-1925, 1960-1975, and 1985-1990), and the texts are sampled from scientific articles only. [Seoane & Loureiro-Porto](#) note that the decline might be rooted in events and dynamics that are sociolinguistic in nature.

Within the last of the three periods of interest in [Seoane & Loureiro-Porto's \(2005\)](#) work, [Homan \(1989\)](#) mentions that PASSIVE VOICE is an accepted form used in academic writing and also for other purposes to achieve a neutral and objective tone. [Homan](#) states that in general, people used PASSIVE VOICE without asking a question; although there were some critical analyses on the topic of AGENT omission, there was no clear opposition.

Not for too long after [Homan's](#) study, there are many accusations of PASSIVE VOICE that discourage its usage. Some see PASSIVE VOICE as a tool that makes the situations “less severe” than they actually are, “increases perception of victim responsibility”, and “decreases perception of perpetrator responsibility” ([Abramski et al. 2024](#) citing [Bohner 2001](#); [Henley et al. 1995](#); [Northcutt et al. 2019](#)). Studies in the context of violence against women (VAW) (see [Katz 2006](#)) point out that PASSIVE VOICE is used to ‘exclude the the culprits’ and to ‘emotionally distance the readers’ away from the events. Apart from the “reader” side, [Reilly et al. \(2005: 191\)](#) state that such AGENTLESS actions also distance the “writer or speaker” from the text. [Kahn \(1992\)](#) also refers to PASSIVE VOICE as a “soulless” voice. [Bohner \(2001\)](#) criticizes the use of PASSIVE VOICE as an indicator of responsibility attribution to the victim and considers other mechanisms like nominalizations or paraphrases to be more reliable.

Outside of academia, this trend is also prevalent. There are many posts on online platforms asking for suggestions to avoid using PASSIVE VOICE or to gauge the opinions why people dislike it. In Reddit (<https://www.reddit.com/>), for example, these topics are commonly found in r/writing, r/grammar, and r/ENGLISH channels.

Around the same period of time in the late 19th century and early 20th century, some scholars made a statement to defend PASSIVE VOICE. This opposite force of opposition can be observed as early as 1969 in [DeVito's \(1969\)](#) work. [DeVito](#) states that to recommend that PASSIVE be avoided because they are more difficult to understand is a “gross simplification” of the facts. [Ferreira \(2021\)](#) also writes an article *In Defense of the Passive Voice* to point out the necessity and advantages of PASSIVE VOICE and eloquently addresses each accusation made towards PASSIVE VOICE. This defensive wave is also reflected through more balanced views that encourage the use of PASSIVE VOICE as appropriate and with a critical mind ([Gilpin & Patchet-Golubev 2000](#); [Williams & Rivers 1983](#)).

3 Datasets

3.1 Three main corpora

Three corpora are used to analyze passive constructions; Ukraine War corpus, the Leipzig corpora, and the Russian News corpora.

3.1.1 Ukraine War corpus

The Ukraine War corpus is a web-crawled corpus compiled by SketchEngine (Kilgarriff et al. 2014) with the following keywords: Russian-Ukrainian War, Russo-Ukrainian War, Ukraine War, and Russias War in Ukraine. Before the compilation, certain parameters are set to ensure a maximum size of the corpus: Size and relevance set to larger size and Max document size and Max cleaned document size set to the maximum of 15000 kB. After the compilation, the corpus is cleaned by removing the HTML snippet `<p>` and `</p>`, as well as irrelevant numbers and symbols, such as [20][21][22] mixing in the texts and ^ in front of the lines ending up with around 170k words.

Table 1: Statistics of Ukraine War corpus

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.
Ukraine War	5,269	170,834	32.42

3.1.2 Leipzig corpora

Leipzig corpora (2014-2020, 2023) (Quasthoff et al. 2012) are downloaded from the Leipzig corpora collection website in the category News. Because the years 2014 and 2022 mark the start and the major escalation of the Ukraine war, respectively, but news for the year 2022 is not available on the repository website, only news from the years 2014 and 2023 are collected. In the Leipzig corpus, line numbers, lines with less than 10 words and more than 4 numerical digits, as well as lines with a double quotation mark (direct speech) are removed. This leaves 12 and 13 million words in the Leipzig 2014 and 2023 corpora, respectively. The statistics of the Leipzig corpora utilized as datasets are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Statistics of Leipzig corpora

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.
Leipzig_2014	756,346	16,859,714	22.29
Leipzig_2015	765,565	17,199,603	22.47
Leipzig_2016	841,467	18,425,587	21.90
Leipzig_2017	836,561	17,910,042	21.41
Leipzig_2018	839,051	17,951,766	21.40
Leipzig_2019	845,091	18,128,565	21.45
Leipzig_2020	846,917	18,342,325	21.66
Leipzig_2023	854,997	18,498,430	21.64
Average	826,347	17,829,303	21.82

3.1.3 Russian sources

Three English-speaking Russian news media are used to build Russian news corpora.

- TASS (<https://tass.com/>)
- the Arctic (<https://arctic.ru/>)
- The Moscow Times (<https://www.themoscowtimes.com/>)

The three websites are used in SketchEngine (Kilgarriff et al. 2014), a web-crawling tool, to compile language corpora. The compilation method in SketchEngine is different from the Ukraine War corpus because this time the search is based on web URLs, instead of sets of keywords. Other parameters remain the same: to set the maximum size of the corpora to the largest. The statistics of the three Russian News corpora are in Table 33 below.

Table 3: Statistics of Russian news corpora

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.	#All Passive Pair	#Filtered Passive Pair
Arctic	4,705	203,785	43.31	1,614	47
TASS	6,866	219,684	32.00	1,663	30
The Moscow Times	5,571	206,742	37.11	1,695	30
Average	5,714	210,737	37.47	1,657	36

4 Methods

4.1 NLP methods

4.1.1 Parser

Dependency parsing is an approach to automatic syntactic analysis of natural language inspired by the theoretical linguistic tradition of dependency grammar (Kübler et al. 2009). Syntactic structure is expressed as directed dependencies between words. Dependencies are labeled with relations, such as subject `nsubj` or direct object `dobj`. Dependency relations are represented by arrows pointing from the head to the dependent. Words can also be tagged with part-of-speech (POS) underneath them. The goal of a dependency parser is to induce this kind of structure for a given utterance; it is typically required that a sentence be tokenized, POS-tagged, and lemmatized (Sohn et al. 2012).

SpaCy (Honnibal & Montani 2017) was developed in 2015. It is a state-of-art text parser that enables a simple yet efficient extraction process of linguistic structures. Relying on an arc-eager transition-based system, SpaCy's dependency parsing algorithm uses parsing transitions to draw a dependency tree from an input sentence. The transition-based system, although may suffer from error propagation (an incorrect prediction of a tag affecting the following ones), performs better than the graph-based system thanks to its rich feature representation leading to more accuracy in frequently occurring relations like subject and object dependents (Kübler et al. 2009). The transformer architecture in SpaCy's currently largest language model `en_core_web_trf` provides high-accuracy dependency parsing.

The identification of passive voice subject-verb pairs is based on the dependency tag `nsubjpass` readily available in SpaCy parser (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Dependency tagging in spaCy

Other extractions involve additional dependency tags; for example, AGENTIVE BY PHRASE relies on agent tag and MODIFIER is captured with amod and compound tags. The extraction methods are explained in details in the responsible sections.

4.1.2 Topic modeling

Topic models are algorithms for discovering the main themes that pervade a large and otherwise unstructured collection of documents. The simplest topic model is Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei 2012). LDA is a traditional statistical probabilistic model based on the probability distributions of words over a corpus (Ylä-Anttila et al. 2022). It is considered a STATIC language model as it is trained to learn “one” fixed embedding for each word in a corpus.

Another type of language models is a CONTEXTUAL language model, such as BERTopic employed in this study. The CONTEXTUAL language models have a clear advantage over STATIC models in their capabilities in understanding the SEMANTICS of the same word occurring in different contexts, leading to more coherent and meaningful results.

There are many studies that use topic modelling with the texts a specific focus; for example, public policy (Isoaho, Karoliina and Gritsenko, Daria and Mäkelä, Eetu 2021), parliament debate (Magnusson et al. 2018), and climate change (Ylä-Anttila et al. 2022). The use of topic modeling in this study is to find out a variety of topics within general news reports (the Leipzig corpora). By doing this, a specific “topic” in mind is “the Ukraine War”, and the goal is to find out how popular or significant this topic is compared to others.

4.1.3 Semantic map

In this project, a semantic map is used to aid in the categorization of words.¹ A STATIC word embedding model, specifically Word2Vec, is selected due to its clear representations of word

¹The code to generate a semantic map is adapted from Natural Language Processing Demystified (Parker 2022)

meanings. This approach involves creating a visual representation of words based on their semantic similarities.

The semantic maps are created using a pre-trained STATIC embedding model, Word2Vec, in the Gensim library. The model is trained on the Google News Corpus (around 3 billion words).

STATIC word embedding models like Word2Vec generate semantic scatter plots where each word is represented by a fixed vector based on its meaning. These vectors are plotted in a multidimensional semantic space, with words of similar meanings positioned closer together. Because these models create semantic scattered plots based on fixed meanings for each word [Jurafsky & Martin \(2023: 120\)](#), they can return inaccurate coordinates of words on a semantic map. For instance, words with multiple parts-of-speech like *place*, *list*, *target*, and *sentence* may be inaccurately plotted according to their more common usage as a NOUN without taken into account their contextual meanings that can also be VERB. Despite its limitations, this method remains useful for illustrating semantic clusters.

An alternative to STATIC embedding is a CONTEXTUAL embedding model, such as BERT. While CONTEXTUAL embedding models provide more accurate representations of words within specific contexts, the resulting semantic plots can be challenging to interpret for categorization purposes. This complexity arises because BERT handles NAME and PROPER NOUN differently, often causing NAME to dominate the plot area and other words to cluster together. Therefore, the Word2Vec model in the Gensim library is used. The model's ability to clearly illustrate semantic clusters makes it an effective tool for categorizing words based on their meanings.

4.2 Corpus linguistics methods

This project employs various corpus linguistic approaches to assess the association of passive subject-verb collocates. These statistical methods sequentially build upon observed (*O*) and expected (*E*) frequencies derived from a contingency table leading to the calculation of chi-squared test score, Fisher's exact test score, and t-score, culminating in p-values. The p-values from the chi-squared test, Fisher's exact test, and t-score are compared, and after testing, the p-value of the t-score is used as a main measure to assess the collocational significance in this project due to their balanced distributions. The utilization of these measures for studying word pair occurrence frequencies is inspired by [Evert \(2004\)](#).

4.2.1 Collocation analysis

Collocation is the co-occurrence of two words. A stronger collocate means that the pair tends to occur together more often. This relationship is called the collocational strength. This section covers the methods to derive observed and expected frequencies using a contingency table.

Observed frequencies are the actual or raw counts of the occurrences whereas expected frequencies are the occurrences that are expected to occur. Expected frequencies are calculated using a contingency table. A contingency table is a table that represents the cross-classification of the collocational scenarios of subject-verb pairs.

Four collocational scenarios are counted in the corpus:

- i) Subject and verb co-occur.
- ii) Subject is present without verb.
- iii) Verb is present without subject.
- iv) Neither subject nor verb is present.

The contingency table for each subject-verb pair has a 2-row-and-2-column dimension. Table 4 below is the contingency table for the subject-verb pair *sovereignty_threatened* from the Ukraine War corpus, with expected frequencies in parentheses:

Table 4: Contingency table for "*sovereignty_threatened*"

	Threatened (Present)	Threatened (Absent)	Row Total
Sovereignty (Present)	4 (0.015)	0 (3.985)	4
Sovereignty (Absent)	1 (94.511)	1325 (1162.489)	1326
Column Total	5	1325	1330

Expected frequencies are calculated by multiplying the sum of the row with the sum of the column and dividing by the total occurrences of all pairs in the corpus. For instance, the expected frequency where both subject "*sovereignty*" and verb "*threatened*" occur together is 0.015, calculated as $\frac{(4+0)*(4+1)}{1330}$.

The expected frequency $E(O)$ of the scenario i (in blue) where both subject and verb co-occur is calculated by multiplying the sum of the row with the sum of the column and dividing with total occurrences of all passive pairs in the corpus. For instance, the expected frequency where both subject *sovereignty* and verb *threatened* occur together is 0.015, calculated from $(4+0)*(4+1)/1330$. The same calculation applies to the other three scenarios.

4.2.2 Association measures

Evert et al. (2008) defines association scores as a quantitative measure of the attraction between words. The association measures employed in this study is t-score. However, this section also covers the Chi-squared test score and Fisher's test score in comparison with t-score. The comparison shows that t-score is the most appropriate measure providing a more balanced assessment.

The calculation of association measure continues from the expected frequencies and the observed frequencies. The first association measure of collocation is chi-squared test score. Chi-squared

test score measures goodness-of-fit for the observed frequencies against expected frequencies. A recommended standard version of the chi-squared test score for co-occurrence data (Evert 2004) can be calculated by squaring the difference between observed frequency and expected frequency $(4-0.015)^2=15.88$, multiplying with a total occurrences ($N=1330$), and dividing with the multiplication of the expected frequency of scenario i and ix ($0.015*1162.489=17.44$), which is 1211.03. The calculation formula of the standard chi-squared test score is shown below.

$$\text{Chi-squared Test} = \frac{(\text{Observed freq. of } i - \text{Expected freq. of } i)^2 * N}{\text{Expected freq. of } i * \text{Expected freq. of } ix}$$

A larger Chi-squared score indicates a greater deviation from expected frequencies, signifying statistical significance, often assessed using a p-value. P-value represents the probability of observing a chi-squared test score in the extreme tail of Chi-squared distribution. Given a Chi-squared score and a degree of freedom (df), which is 1 for each individual pair, p-value can be calculated based on the chi-squared distribution table, or in this study, by using the `stats.chi2.sf` function from SciPy module (Virtanen et al. 2001) in Python. When a p-value is less than a certain significance level, which is typically 0.05, the frequency difference is statistically significant.

Canning (2014) mentions the limitations of the chi-squared test scores including the fact that this statistical score may not be applicable with a small sample size. Canning provides a rough definition of the small sample size that is when more than 20% of the cells return expected values below 5. In the case of a small sample, the p-value of Fisher's exact test is often used. Fisher's Exact Test computes an exact p-value rather than an approximation that is only valid for large samples (Evert 2004). The calculation of Fisher's exact test score concerns all four occurrence scenarios in the contingency table and is done using the `stats.fisher_exact` function in the SciPy module (Virtanen et al. 2001) in Python.

To assess if the current sample size (the observed co-occurrence of a pair) is adequate for the chi-squared test score to have enough power, Cohen's w (Cohen 1988) and Power Analysis are applied. Cohen's w is a measure of the effect size of the chi-squares score. The computation of Cohen's w in the context of a contingency table is done by square-rooting the division of the sum of the Chi-square components (of all four scenarios) with total occurrences. The formula of Cohen's w calculation is shown below.

$$w = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i-ix} \frac{(\text{Observed freq.} - \text{Expected freq.})^2}{\text{Expected freq.}}}{N}}$$

After that, Cohen's w is used as an effect size parameter in the POWER ANALYSIS to obtain a necessary sample size. Other parameters include the significance level, which is 0.05, and the

power level (to correctly reject null hypothesis), which is typically 0.8. POWER ANALYSIS is conducted in Python using the power module, as well as the solve_power function from the GofChiSquarePower class (Seabold & Perktold 2010).

Another common association measure used to interpret the significance of co-occurrences is the t-score. The t-score is a measure used in hypothesis testing. To calculate a t-score, the difference between the observed and the expected frequency of scenario i is divided by the square root of the expected frequency of scenario i . The calculation formula of t-score is shown below.

$$t = \frac{\text{Observed freq. of } i - \text{Expected freq. of } i}{\sqrt{\text{Expected freq. of } i}}$$

After the three approaches were tested and compared in this project, it was found that the p-value of the t-score is a more appropriate measure to assess the significance of co-occurrences. A vast majority of the p-values of the chi-squared test tends to be very low ($p < 0.01$) while the p-value of the t-score is more evenly distributed. Fisher's exact test score returns a less drastic distribution of p-value than the chi-squared test score, but the distribution is still highly skewed towards the lower range (negative or left skewed). This uneven distribution results from the fact that the chi-squared test and the Fisher's exact test take in the occurrence statistics from all four scenarios where a large portion of observations fall into scenario ix where neither subject nor verb is present. This returns a high frequency of unusually large chi-squared test scores and extremely low p-values, which might not be representative of meaningful co-occurrences. The t-score, on the other hand, only focuses on scenario i , where both subject and verb co-occur, so it provides a more evenly distributed p-value indicating a more balanced assessment of significance. This aligns with Dennis (1965 cited in Evert 2004), who suggests that t-score is more useful than chi-squared test for extracting significant co-occurrences, Lijffijt et al. (2016) who recommend the use of the t-test for comparing word frequencies across corpora, and Evert et al. (2008), whose experiments show that t-score is the best indicator for lexical prepositional-phrases-and-verbs collocations among all association measures. Kilgarriff (2005) concerns that application of the chi-squared test leads to finding spurious results.

Table 5 and Figure 2 below reflect the skewness of p-value distributions across three measures and three corpora. The table shows the percentage of subject-verb pairs with p-values falling within the first standard deviation from zero $[0, STD]$ as highlighted in yellow in the histogram, as well as the skewness coefficients. The more positive the skewness coefficient, the more skewed the histogram towards the left side, signifying low values. The comparison of the p-value distributions from the three measures can be found in Figure 19.

Table 5: The skewness of association score distributions

Corpus	[0, STD]			skewness		
	t-score	Chi sq. test	Fisher's exact	t-score	Chi sq. test	Fisher's exact
Ukraine War	75.97%	97.08%	92.74%	4.16	9.94	8.41
Leipzig 2014	75.45%	91.79%	87.41%	2.48	4.17	4.04
Leipzig 2023	75.54%	92.28%	87.61%	2.57	4.40	4.20
Average	75.65%	93.72%	89.25%	3.07	6.17	5.55

Figure 2: The histogram of the p-value of t-score in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

5 Results and Analyses

5.1 Comparative studies: Ukraine War corpus VS Leipzig corpora

5.1.1 Civilian, violence, and restrictions: Significant pairs and categories

Subject and verb categories are made based on the Ukraine War corpus, as well as the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora. A comparison between the three corpora is conducted.

For the Ukraine War corpus, taking only the subject-verb pairs with more than 2 occurrences and $p < 0.05$ into account, there are 28 pairs left. The first 10 pairs are shown below (O =observed frequency, E =expected frequency).

Table 6: Top 10 pairs in the Ukraine War corpus

Subject_Verb_Pairs	O(s_v)	E(s_v)	t-score	p-value
people_killed	37	5.4887218	13.4503	0.0472
russians_swept	22	0.39699248	34.2865	0.0186
others_wounded	6	0.14210526	15.5395	0.0409
dozens_wounded	6	0.14210526	15.5395	0.0409
refineries_targeted	5	0.05789474	20.5396	0.0310
reference_invoked	4	0.01203008	36.3595	0.0175
sovereignty_threatened	4	0.01503759	32.4964	0.0196
areas_drawn	4	0.02631579	24.4954	0.0260
operations_stopped	4	0.03157895	22.3316	0.0285
claim_verified	4	0.05263158	17.2062	0.0370

5.1.1.1 Subjects and verbs categorization (Ukraine War corpus)

To see the categorical meanings of these words, a semantic map is created. [Figure 3](#) is a semantic map displaying the most frequently occurring passive subjects and verbs in the Ukraine War corpus. The words in each category are grouped within the same color. If there are less than 3 words in a category, they are plotted as separated dots.

Figure 3: Semantic categories of passive subjects and verbs in the Ukraine War corpus

According to the semantic map, two main groups can be observed: one for verbs located on the left side and another for subjects on the right. Nine categories of subjects (*Civilian*, *Military*, *Death and Danger*, *Location*, *Name*, *Communication*, *Law and Governance*, *Nominalization*, *Neutral Entities*) and seven categories of verbs (*Harmful Actions*, *Restrictive Actions*, *General Actions*, *Motion*, *Law and Rule Actions*, *Communication Actions*, *Perception Actions*) are detected. Past participle form of verbs is kept to prevent confusion with subjects, e.g. wound and sentence can be mistaken as subjects if not in a past participle form. Note that since the categories with less than 2 member words do not form a triangle on the semantic map, they are plotted as spots, and the names of those categories are not listed in the plot legend. The full list can be found in the table below. The descriptions of each category are as follow:

Subjects Categories

1. **Civilian:** Refers to non-combatant individuals or groups.
2. **Military:** Refers to military personnel and related entities.
3. **Death and Danger:** Refers to entities associated with lethal events or hazardous situations.
4. **Location:** Refers to specific geographic or man-made locations.
5. **Name:** Refers to proper names of individuals.
6. **Communication:** Refers to mediums or acts of conveying information.
7. **Law and Governance:** Refers to entities related to legal and governance frameworks.
8. **Nominalization:** Refers to abstract nouns derived from verbs or adjectives.
9. **Neutral Entities:** Refers to neutral or miscellaneous entities not fitting other categories.

Verb Categories

1. **Harmful Actions:** Refers to actions causing harm or injury.
2. **Restrictive Actions:** Refers to actions imposing limitations or constraints.
3. **General Actions:** Refers to broad, non-specific actions.
4. **Motion:** Refers to actions involving movement.
5. **Law and Rule Actions:** Refers to actions related to legal or regulatory processes.
6. **Communication Actions:** Refers to actions involving the exchange of information.
7. **Perception Actions:** Refers to actions involving sensory or cognitive perception.

The proportion of the categorisation of subjects and verbs is summed up in [Table 7](#). The categorical weights are calculated based on the observed frequencies of a word in the passive voice context.

Table 7: Proportion of subject and verb categories in the Ukraine War corpus

	Category	Word	%
Subjects_Ukr	Civilian	russians, people, others, dozens	56.16
	Military	operations, drones, commander	6.88
	Death and Danger	explosions, evacuation	3.72
	Location	refineries, areas, camp, city, building, plant, units	16.33
	Name	Kamardin, Shtovba, Volkov, Urey, Petrova	6.59
	Communication	claim, story, articles	6.02
	Law and Governance	sovereignty	1.15
	Nominalization	production	0.86
	Neutral Entities	reference, electricity	2.29
Total			100
Verbs_Ukr	Harmful Actions	killed, swept, wounded, threatened, shot, attacked	56.01
	Restrictive Actions	stopped, halted, disrupted, thwarted, shut, captured	13.61
	General Actions	targeted, haunted, given, established, liberated	12.97
	Motion	drawn, surrounded, struck	6.33
	Law and Rule Actions	verified, invoked, sentenced	8.23

Continued on next page

	Category	Word	%
	Communication Actions	listed	1.58
	Perception Actions	heard	1.27
Total			100

According to the category table, passive subjects in the Ukraine War corpus are dominated by words related to civilians whereas passive verbs mainly signify violence. The most frequently occurring category of subjects is *Civilian* (56.16%) followed by *Locations* (16.33%). *Military*, *Name*, and *Communication* subjects appear almost equally frequently (6.88%, 6.59%, and 6.02%, respectively) Less frequently found are subjects related to *Death and Danger* (3.72%), *Neutral Entities* (2.29%), *Law and Governance* (1.15%), and *Nominalization* (0.86%). For verbs, the most dominant category is *Harmful verbs* (56.01%) followed by *Restrictive verbs* (13.61%) and *General verbs* (12.97%). *Law and Rule verbs* account for 8.23%, and it is 6.33% for *Motion verbs*. *Communication* and *Perception verbs* are almost equally identified at only 1.58% and 1.27%, respectively.

5.1.1.2 Subjects and verbs categorization (Leipzig corpora)

The categories of passive words in the Leipzig corpora are made with the same categorization framework with the help of a semantic map. Due to a larger number of words, subjects and verbs are presented in a separate semantic map. The pairs are filtered with the $f > 15$ and $p < 0.05$ condition, and the frequencies of the word in each category are combined to calculate the percentage weight. The proportion of subject and verb categories is shown in the following sections.

5.1.1.2.1 Leipzig 2014: Subjects

In the Leipzig corpora, five new categories of subjects emerge as follow:

1. **Media, Entertainment, Technology:** Terms related to digital media, entertainment industry, and technology.
2. **Commute:** Terms related to transportation and travel.
3. **Research and Academia:** Terms related to academic research, studies, and scholarly findings.
4. **Monetary and Business:** Terms related to financial transactions, business entities, and economic activities.
5. **Disease:** Terms related to diseases and health conditions. This category emerges following the outbreak of Ebola virus in South Africa in 2014.

Table 8: Proportion of subject categories in the 2014 Leipzig corpus

Category	Subjects_Lz14	%
Civilian	people, civilian, man, woman	22.23
Neutral Entities	link, demand, cause, suit, date, name, step, service, material, nothing, ceremony, something, temperature, event, storm, member	13.06
Law and Governance	right, charge, warrant, lawsuit, case, suspect, election, trial	10.35
Death and Danger	shot, body, damage, death, victim, funeral, remain	8.66
Media, Entertainment, Tech.	file, comment, video, photo, technology, picture, game	7.56
Communication	talkback, message, report, story, warning, ban, question, meet, change	7.36
Authority	official, soldier, police, militant, officer	7.10
Research and Academia	study, finding, work, progress, detail, research, result	6.29
Location	field, hospital, school, home	4.43
Commute	flight, rocket, lane, plane, driver	4.37
Monetary and Business	money, deal, fund	4.13
Nominalization	requirement, decision	2.59
Disease	Ebola, virus	0.99
Name	Brown	0.87
Total		100.00

According to [Figure 18](#) (in the Appendix) and [Table 8](#), *Civilian* subjects occupy the largest proportion (22.23%) followed by *Neutral-* (13.06%) and *Law and Governance*-related subjects (10.35). *Death and Danger*, *Media, Entertainment, and Technology*, *Communication*, and *Authority* categories, are found almost equally frequently (8.66%, 7.56%, 7.36%, and 7.10%, respectively). *Research and Academia* category accounts for around 6.29%, and around 4% for *Location*, *Commute*, and *Monetary and Business* categories. *Nominalization*, *Disease*, and *Names* are minimally found at only 2.59%, 0.99%, and 0.87%, respectively.

5.1.1.2.2 Leipzig 2014: Verbs

The semantic map of Leipzig 2014 verbs can be found in [Figure 20](#) in the Appendix.

Table 9: Proportion of verb categories in the 2014 Leipzig corpus

Category	Verbs_Lz14	%
General Actions	met, canceled, returned, determined, found, spent, made, set, done, released, discovered, conducted, taken, sent, needed, resolved, completed, expected, used, scheduled	47.10
Restrictive Actions	closed, held, arrested, charged	13.60

Continued on next page

Category	Verbs_Lz14	%
Harmful Actions	fired, killed, shot, destroyed, injured, wounded, struck, displaced	12.75
Communication Actions	issued, published, pronounced, reported, described, asked, called, said, announced	11.10
Law and Rule Actions	violated, required, authorized, signed, filed, submitted	4.08
Perception Actions	viewed, heard, known	3.82
Motion	laid, lifted, dropped, reached, transported, brought	3.73
Media, Entert., Tech-related Actions	posted, played, moderated	2.79
Disease-related Actions	transmitted, spread, recovered	1.03
Total		100.00

The percentage weights indicate that verbs in the 2014 Leipzig corpus are largely occupied by *General Action* verbs (47.10%) followed by *Restrictive* verbs (13.60%) and *Harmful* verbs (12.75%). *Communicative* verbs account for 11.10%, and 4.08% for *Law and Rule*-related verbs. The next portions are *Perception* and *Motion* verbs at 3.82% and 3.73%, respectively. Verbs related to *Media, Entertainment, and Technology* verbs are found at only 2.79%. The least occurring verbs are the *Disease*-related ones at 1.03%.

5.1.1.2.3 Leipzig 2023: Subjects

The semantic map of Leipzig 2014 verbs can be found in [Figure 21](#) in the Appendix.

Table 10: Proportion of subject categories in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

Category	Subjects_Lz23	%
Neutral Entities	voice, concern, what, step, ticket, event, nothing, project, service, date, rain, thing, change, name, effort, ceremony	24.01
Civilian	man, body, people, crew, baby, civilian	21.38
Media, Entertainment, Tech.	game, trailer, game, winner, film, fan, technology	9.83
Law and Governance	warrant, lawsuit, justice, offense, court, charge, case, election, suspect	8.95
Monetary and Business	dividend, deal, money, shareholder, stockholder, company, fund, payment	8.60
Death and Danger	shot, death, damage, remains, body	5.12
Authority	police, soldier, officer	4.59
Research and Academia	work, progress, research, detail	4.30
Nominalization	decision, permission, donation	4.14
Commute	road, driver	3.67
Communication	warning, story, meeting	2.78
Location	home	1.71
Name	Trump	0.91

Continued on next page

Category	Subjects_Lz23	%
Total		100.00

Table 10 shows that subjects in the 2023 Leipzig corpus gradually descend by 1-3% off categorical weights with no major occupants. The top categories are Neutral and Civilian (18.54% and 16.36%, respectively) closely followed by the new category Monetary and Business (12.55%), as well as Law (10.02%). Media, Entertainment, and Technology are found at a little more than 2% than Communication and Death and Danger (8.96%, 6.72%, and 6.23%, consecutively). Nominalizations, as well as Authority, Commute, and Research and Academic account for 5.82%, 4.17%, 3.94%, and 3.86%, respectively. The least identified categories are Location (1.85%) and Names (0.98%).

5.1.1.2.4 Leipzig 2023: Verbs

The semantic map of Leipzig 2014 verbs can be found in Figure 22 in the Appendix.

Table 11: Proportion of verb categories in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

Category	Verbs_Lz23	%
General Actions	used, granted, served, led, given, found, updated, founded, made, discovered, happened, released, done, taken, needed, expected, born, attended, set, hosted, built, completed	53.01
Communication Actions	issued, told, called, announced, confirmed, revealed, described, reported, said	13.86
Restrictive Actions	closed, arrested, held, charged	11.39
Harmful Actions	fired, killed, injured, displaced, stabbed, shot	6.20
Motion	raised, reached, dropped, directed, carried, left	5.32
Perception Actions	heard, known	4.06
Monetary and Business Act.	paid, sold, funded, spent	3.32
Law and Rule Actions	indicted, filed, registered, sentenced	2.05
Media, Entertainment, Tech-related Actions	played	0.79
Total		100.00

Table 11 shows the percentage of verbs in the Leipzig 2023 corpus. There is a new group of verbs related to *Monetary and Business* identified in the 2023 Leipzig corpus whereas *Disease*-related verbs are not present. A majority of verbs are *General Action* verbs (53.01%). *Communicative* verbs come in second place at 13.86%. *Restrictive* verbs account for 11.39% and 6.20% for *Harmful* verbs. *Motion* verbs and *Perception* verbs are found at 5.32% and 4.06%, respectively. Verbs related to *Monetary and Business* account for 3.32% while verbs related to *Law and Rules* occupy only 2.05%. Lastly, *Media, Entertainment, and Technology* verbs are the least commonly identified ones at 0.79%.

5.1.1.3 Comparison of the passive subject and verb proportion

By comparing subjects and verbs between the three corpora, a couple of interesting observations can be made.

5.1.1.3.1 Subjects

Figure 4: The comparison of passive subject categories

Figure 4 demonstrates the proportion of different passive subject categories in the Ukraine War corpus compared to the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora. The Ukraine War corpus, being a specific corpus about the war, is distinct with a much higher proportion of subjects in three categories: *Civilians* (56% compared to 22% and 21% in the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora, respectively), *Location* (16% compared to 4% and 2%), and *Name* (7% compared to 1% in both Leipzig corpora). However, the Ukraine War corpus exhibits a low percentage of subjects related to *Law and Governance* (1% compared to 10% and 9% in the 2014 and 2023 Leipzig corpora, respectively) and no significant subjects (0%) in the *Media, Entertainment, and Tech*, *Research and Academia*, *Commute*, *Monetary and Business*, and *Disease* categories. This may be due to the fact that it is a war-specific corpus as well.

5.1.1.3.2 Verbs

Figure 5: The comparison of passive verb categories

In terms of verbs, [Figure 5](#) shows that the Ukraine War corpus has a much higher proportion of *Harmful* verbs when compared to the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora (56% compared to 13% and 6%, respectively). Verbs related to *Law and Rules* are also found more in the Ukraine War corpus (8% compared to 4% and 2% in the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora, respectively). *General* action verbs are used distinctively more in the Leipzig corpora (47% for the 2014 and 53% for the 2023), as only 13% is identified in the Ukraine War corpus. The same phenomenon happens in *Perception* verbs with the occurrence of only 1% in the Ukraine War corpus compared to 4% in both Leipzig corpora. Last but not least, the verb categories that are totally absent in the Ukraine War corpus are *Media, Entertainment, and Tech, Disease, and Monetary and Business*.

5.1.1.3.3 Total categories

To conclude, there are 14 categories of subjects and 10 categories of verbs detected as follow:

Subjects:

1. Civilian
2. Neutral Entities
3. Law and Governance
4. Death and Danger
5. Media, Entertainment, Technology
6. Communication
7. Authority
8. Research and Academia
9. Location
10. Commute
11. Monetary and Business
12. Nominalization
13. Disease
14. Name

Verbs:

1. General Actions
2. Restrictive Actions
3. Harmful Actions
4. Communication Actions
5. Law and Rule Actions
6. Perception Actions
7. Motion
8. Media, Entertainment, Technology-related Actions
9. Disease-related Actions
10. Monetary and Business

Overall, the Ukraine War corpus demonstrates unique patterns of passive subject and verb categories as it is a war-specific corpus compared to general news corpora like the Leipzig ones. The main characteristics include a higher usage of *Civilian*, *Location*, and *Name* subjects, as well as verbs related to *Harm* and *Law and Rules*. Moreover, the Leipzig corpora exhibit a higher diversity of categories having words related to *Media*, *Entertainment*, and *Tech*, *Research and Academic*, *Commute*, *Monetary and Business*, as well as *Disease*, that are not present in the Ukraine War corpus. The last noticeable trend is that subjects related to *Media*, *Entertainment*, and *Technology*, as well as *Monetary and Business*, start to rise in their usage in 2023.

This overview of how subject and verb categories behave in the Ukraine War corpus compared to news media in general must be taken with a caution that it only represents the filtered subject-verb pairs based on their significance scores and frequencies, not all the words in the corpus. What seems to matter here may be less about subjects and verbs but more about the “individuals” represented in the news media. Consequently, we will divert our focus to analyze the names or proper nouns related to the Ukraine War in the Leipzig corpora during the years 2014-2020 and 2023.

5.1.2 Russia as a bad guy: Proper noun representations

Proper noun subjects in the corpus can signify different perspectives related to the conflict. There are five names that show up in the list: *Kamardin*, *Shtovba*, *Volkov*, *Urey*, and *Petrova*. The news lines in which the names of individuals appear are in [Table 12](#) below. The close-reading analysis indicates that the representations of these individuals reflect a malevolent image of Russia in political, cultural, humanitarian, and international aspects.

Table 12: Proper noun representations in the Ukraine War corpus

Subject_Verb_Pairs	News Line
Kamardin_given	Artyom Kamardin was given a 7-year prison sentence Thursday for reciting verses against Russias war in Ukraine, a tough punishment that comes during a relentless Kremlin crackdown on dissent.
Shtovba_sentenced	Yegor Shtovba, who participated in the event and recited Kamardins verses, was sentenced to 5 1/2 years on the same charges.
Petrova_arrested	Petrova was arrested in May 2022 and placed in pretrial detention over a post on Russian social network VK, in which she criticized Russian officials for what the Kremlin insists on calling a special military operation in Ukraine, the lawyer told Russian independent news site Mediazona.
Petrova_committed	Petrova was committed to a psychiatric facility.
Petrova_declared	These evaluations are common but in a rare turn, Petrova was declared mentally incompetent.
Petrova_escorted	Viktoria Petrova is escorted by police for a hearing in a court in St. Petersburg, Russia, Friday, March 3, 2023.
Petrova_sentenced	Petrova was sentenced to involuntary treatment in a psychiatric facility after she condemned Russian officials for sending troops into Ukraine on social media.
Volkov_attacked	Leonid Volkov, the former chief of staff for Navalny, who died in a Russian penal colony in February, was attacked with a hammer in the Lithuanian capital of Vilnius on Tuesday.
Urey_captured	Paul Urey and Dylan Healy, two British aid workers, were captured by Russian forces. Aid worker Paul Urey was captured by Russian forces on 29 April 2022 and died in detention on 15 July 2022. Truss said Urey "was captured while undertaking humanitarian work" and that he was in Ukraine "to try and help the Ukrainian people in the face of the unprovoked Russian invasion."
Urey_diagnosed	Urey had been diagnosed with a number of chronic diseases, the statement added.

These news texts imply that the acts of Russia are destructive both towards its own citizens like *Artyom Kamardin* and *Yegor Shtovba*, who recited verses against the war, *Viktoria Petrova*, who condemned the violence, *Leonid Volkov*, who is a close ally of the late Russian opposition leader *Alexei Navalny*, and foreign individuals like *Paul Urey*, who tried to provide humanitarian aid during the war.

5.1.2.1 Proper nouns categorization in the Ukraine War corpus

To find out more comprehensively how different important figures are represented in the news media, further investigation is conducted. In total, there are 61 proper nouns identified in the Ukraine War corpus, and they are categorized into four categories: *people*, *locations*, *organizations*, and *terms/concepts*. Table 54 in the Appendix shows the proper nouns, their descriptions, and accompanying verbs. The percentage weight is calculated from the frequencies of the proper

nouns presented in passive voice. The nationalities *Ukrainian* and *Russian* are under the *Locations* category because they relate to the countries or refer to the territories whereas the *People* category only consists of individuals names, not nationalities.

According to Table 54, the most dominant category is *Locations* (50.98%) followed by *People* (41.83%). *Terms/concepts* and *Organization* names appear almost as frequently (3.92% and 3.27%, respectively). *Russia* occupies a large portion in both *location* and *people* categories (30.72% and 28.76%, respectively) while *Ukraine* comes in second place at 16.34% in *location* and 5.88% in *people* category. The *disputed areas* are minimally mentioned at the rate of 1.31%. Other *location* names appear 2.61% of all proper nouns. For the *people* category, apart from the dominant occurrences of *Russia* and *Ukraine*, *British* and *American* citizens are also in the news in passive voice at 3.92% and 1.31% respectively. Other *nationalities* take only 1.96%. Figure 6 below illustrates the proportion of proper noun subjects occurring in passive voice construction.

Figure 6: Proper noun categories in the Ukraine War corpus

5.1.2.2 Who was done what?

Examining verbs that come with proper nouns reveals several interesting points. *British* and *American* citizens appear with *restrictive* verbs (*charged*, *captured*, *interrupted*, *arrested*) while *Ukrainian* and *Russian* subjects occur with a more diverse group of verbs. *Violent* verbs (*killed*, *poisoned*, *attacked*) exclusively being present with *Ukrainian governmental and military officials*, *Russian activists and advocates*, as well as people of other nationalities (except the *UK* and the *US*). The same phenomenon can also be observed in the nationality subcategory. The violent verb *killed* occurs only with *Ukrainians*, but for *Russians*, the euphemism *swept* is used instead. Euphemism is an indirect word or phrase that people often use to refer to something

embarrassing or unpleasant, sometimes to make it seem more acceptable than it really is (*Euphemism* n.d.). Allan & Burrige (2006) analyze the use of euphemisms in discussing death and killing. They indicate that the use of euphemisms to talk about killing serves to distance individuals from the harsh realities of violence, potentially easing moral qualms.

This observation points out that the *Russian governmental and military officials*, the *UK* and the *US citizens*, and *Russian nationality* are exempted from the use of *violent* verbs, whereas *Ukrainians* appear with those verbs and are portrayed as victims. The use of the euphemism *swept* instead of *killed* for *Russians* could be seen as a form of dehumanization. Based on Haslam's (2012) framework, Russians experience mechanistic dehumanization, with the euphemism *swept* that abstracts and sanitizes their deaths, removing emotional and individual recognition. Haslam identifies the common theme of previous studies on dehumanization – delegitimization (Bar-Tal 2000), moral exclusion (Opatow 1990; Kelman 1973), moral disengagement (Bandura 2002), values judgements (Struch & Schwartz 1989), and infra-humanization (Leyens et al. 2001) – and concludes that dehumanization serves motivated functions like relief from moral emotions, self-exoneration, and justification for violence. This finding explains the void of violent verbs. Kahn (1992) examines the use of passive voice in the context of animal research and identifies various euphemisms, such as *dosed* instead of *poisoned* and *processed* instead of *killed*, which is to avoid or even conceal the jarring or unsettling truth of a situation.

In addition, the categories *Activists and Advocates*, as well as *Poets and Artists*, are only present under *Russian nationalities*, but none for *Ukrainians*. Those activists, advocates, poets, and artists are pro-democracy, anti-war, and condemn Russia's invasion into Ukraine. Verbs accompanying these categories signify *harmful* actions (*kill, poison, attack*) and *restrictions* (*arrest, charge, sentence*). This portrays a suppression of creativity and people who call for peace who were mistreated by Russia. The benign image of Russia is further emphasized with a list of international victims including *Healy, Urey, Shapps, Shekharappa, and Guemy*, who were harassed, threatened, and killed. The number of victims including 9 domestic and 5 international ones also reflects the suppressive and dangerous image of Russia towards its opponents regardless of nationalities.

5.1.2.3 Proper noun representations through time

A diachronic analysis is conducted to examine how the proper noun representations in terms of the categories and accompanying verbs change over time in the Leipzig corpora (2014-2020, 2023). Based on the proper nouns found in the Ukraine War corpus, general proper nouns that are not specific to the Ukraine War (e.g. *US, UK, EU, Facebook, Guterres, Biden*), as well as the names that refer to different individuals or entities (e.g. *Urey, Healy, Samara*), are excluded in this analysis. There are 27 proper nouns that do not appear in any of the Leipzig corpora. This

leaves us with 23 proper nouns of interest sorted under four main categories: *people*, *locations*, *terms and concepts*, and *organizations*. The list of proper nouns are in [Table 13](#) below.

Table 13: Proper nouns of interest

Category	Sub-category	Description	Proper Nouns (Leipzig)
People	Russia	Gov./Military Officials	Putin, Medvedev
		Activists and Advocates	Navalny
	Ukraine	Gov./Military Officials	Zelensky, Yushchenko, Yanukovych, Serhiy, Nikulin
	Others	International Victims	Shapps
Locations	Russia	Russian Locations	Russia, Moscow
		Russian Nationality	Russia
	Ukraine	Ukrainian Locations	Ukraine, Kyiv, Donetsk, Donbas, Luhansk
		Ukrainian Nationality	Ukrainian
	Disputed Areas	Crimea	
Terms & Concepts			UAV, PoWs, Neptune
Organizations			Gazprom

5.1.2.3.1 Proper noun categories through time

The categorical shift of the proper noun is investigated in terms of the proportions, which are the normalized occurrences presented as words per million. This is calculated by dividing raw frequencies with total occurrences of proper nouns in the corpus and multiplying with 1 million. The occurrence weights in each category and year are also reported as a percentage.

$$\text{Normalized Proper Noun Occurrences} = \frac{\text{Raw Frequencies}}{\text{Total Passive Subjects}} * 1,000,000$$

[Table 55](#) in the Appendix shows the proportion of the proper nouns related to the Ukraine War in the Leipzig corpora. By categories, *Locations* occupy 60.68% followed by *People* at 37.57%. *Terms and Concepts*, as well as *Organizations* make up for only 1.33% and 0.42%, respectively, of the passive proper noun subjects in the Leipzig corpora. By sub-categories, proper nouns related to *Russia* account for more than half of both *People* and *Locations*. 80.36% of the *People* category has been found to be *Russian Officials*, as well as *Russian Activists and Advocates*, and 62.57% of the *Location* category is dominated by *Russian Locations* and *Nationality*. *Ukrainian* proper nouns, on the other hand, share only 9.56% in the *People* category and 28.96% in the *Location* category. The rest of the *People* category belongs to *International Victims* at 10.07%, and the rest of the *Location* category goes to *Disputed Areas* at 8.46%. Analyzing the proportion of words within sub-categories shows that the main Ukrainian figures are *Zelensky* (the sixth president of Ukraine since 2019 at 58.59%) and *Yanukovych* (the fourth president of Ukraine from

2010 to 2014 at 28.05%). For *Russia*, the most frequently and consistently mentioned individuals are *Putin* (93.99%). In terms of *locations*, *Ukraine* (74.71%), *Kyiv* (11.17%), and *Donetsk* (10.67%), are among the top names for *Ukraine*. For *Russia*, the list includes *Russia* (78.15%) and *Moscow* (21.29%). From the normalized occurrences, *Crimea* is found in the corpora around 50% less frequently than *Ukraine* (222.07 and 481.54 hits, respectively). The comparison of the proper noun categories identified in the Ukraine War corpus and the Leipzig corpora is illustrated in [Figure 6](#) and [Figure 7](#) in the next page.

Figure 12: Proper noun categories in the Ukraine war corpus

Figure 7: Proper noun categories in the Leipzig corpora

Compared to the categorical proportion in the Ukraine War corpus, a similar trend is observed with some minor different details. *Location* category still dominates; however, the weight in the

Leipzig corpora is more prominent at 62.26% compared to 50.98% in the Ukraine War corpus. The more weight of the *Location* proper nouns results from an increase in all sub-categories; *Russian Locations* from 30.72% to 38.30%, *Ukrainian Locations* from 16.34% to 18.75%, and *Disputed Area (Crimea)* from 1.31% to 5.21%. *People* category in the Leipzig corpora shrinks down by 6.77% (from 41.83% to 35.06%). The percentage of sub-categories remains the same where *Russian People Proper Nouns* occupy the largest portion with an increase from 28.76% in the Ukraine War corpus to 30.61% followed by *Ukrainian People* and *Other Nationalities* decreasing from 5.88% to 3.64% and from 1.96% to 0.81%, respectively. The *Names of People* found in the Ukraine War corpus are more diverse with the *British* and the *US* sub-categories being present accounting for 3.92% and 1.31%, respectively. *Terms and Concepts*, as well as *Organizations*, are mentioned sparingly at 2.26% and 0.42%, respectively, decreasing from 3.92% and 3.27% in the Ukraine War corpus.

In summary, when it comes to the Ukraine War situation, news in the Leipzig corpora discusses *Locations* proportionally more often than *People* with the proper nouns related to *Russia* more than *Ukraine* in both categories. In addition, the proper nouns in the Ukraine War corpus show more variety when compared to a general news corpora like the Leipzig ones. The comparison in details is illustrated in [Figure 23](#) in the Appendix.

Moving forward

Up until this point, we extracted passive subject-verb pairs from the Ukraine War corpus and categorize subjects and verbs to build the framework for later analyses. In the following sections, we are about to dive deeper to examine PASSIVE VOICE in the Leipzig corpora in terms of the trend and figure out how popular the topic related to Russia-Ukraine conflict is through the years. We will also analyze how RUSSIA and UKRAINE are represented as ACTOR and PATIENT in passive clauses in the Ukraine War corpus. We then compare the findings from the Western media with the Russian news sources.

5.2 The examination of passive voice in the Leipzig corpora

This section aims to explore the trends and phenomena related to passive voice in Leipzig Corpora, namely the common pairs compared with the Ukraine War corpus, active VS passives, short VS long passives, be- VS get- passives, and the popularity of Ukraine War topic.

5.2.1 In search of the like-minded

5.2.1.1 Lookup datasets and initial comparison

The comparison process concerns the use of passive pairs in the Ukraine War corpus as target pairs and look them up in the Leipzig corpora. The investigation scope is within the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora.

Upon the extraction and the pre-processing, 60,973 and 64,688 passive pairs are remained for the years 2014 and 2023 respectively. As Leipzig corpora are used as a lookup dataset to look for the target subject-verb pairs extracted from the Ukraine War corpus earlier, subject-verb pairs in the Leipzig corpora are not filtered. [Table 14](#) shows the number of words, sentences, and passive pairs, of the Leipzig corpora compared with the Ukraine War corpus, which are used in this analysis.

Table 14: The statistics of the Ukraine War corpus and the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora

Corpus	# Sentence	# Words	# Subject_Verb Pair
Ukraine War	5,269	170,834	1,061
Leipzig 2014	570,512	12,322,647	60,973
Leipzig 2023	625,932	13,224,845	64,688

Before basing the observations solely on the pairs from the Ukraine War corpus, it is sensible to first examine the most significant pairs in the Leipzig corpora.

5.2.1.2 The most significant pairs

To examine the most significant passive pairs in the 2014 and 2023 Leipzig corpora, the pairs are filtered under the conditions of more than 15 occurrences (the same proportion with the minimum of 2 hits in the Ukraine War corpus) and the p-value fewer than 0.05. This gives 127 pairs for the 2014 corpus and 101 pairs for the 2023 corpus. The 10 most significant pairs based on ascending p-value and descending observed frequencies are shown in [Table 15](#) and [Table 16](#) below.

Table 15: Top 10 subject-verb pairs in the 2014 Leipzig corpus

Subject_Verb_Pairs	O(s_v)	E(s_v)	t-score	p-value
people_killed	351	28.35	60.5999	0.0105
body_found	185	7.30	65.7480	0.0097
decision_made	124	4.92	53.6930	0.0119
man_arrested	106	12.06	27.0478	0.0235
people_injured	101	8.46	31.8148	0.0200
field_required	98	0.77	110.8831	0.0057

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Subject_Verb_Pairs	O(s_v)	E(s_v)	t-score	p-value
people_arrested	82	20.93	13.3480	0.0476
talkback_submitted	77	0.14	205.2257	0.0031
bodies_found	75	3.90	36.0249	0.0177
charges_filed	74	0.65	91.1534	0.0070

Table 16: Top 10 subject-verb pairs in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

Subject_Verb_Pairs	O(s_v)	E(s_v)	t-score	p-value
man_arrested	181	11.20	50.7251	0.0125
people_killed	156	9.38	47.8853	0.0133
dividend_paid	118	0.61	149.7230	0.0043
decision_made	111	6.02	42.7770	0.0149
body_found	108	4.61	48.1672	0.0132
man_charged	75	7.62	24.4152	0.0261
people_injured	59	4.69	25.0847	0.0254
police_called	59	1.06	56.3069	0.0113
event_held	57	3.19	30.1166	0.0211
what_known	54	6.64	18.3759	0.0346

By skimming through the list, a couple of interesting observations can be made; even in a general news corpus like the Leipzig news corpora, similar most commonly used pairs that appear in the Ukraine War corpus still show up. *Violent* verbs (*kill* and *injure*), restrictive verbs (*arrest*, *charge*, *hold*, and *close*), and *civilian*-related subjects (*man* and *people*) still appear in the top frequent ranks. Apart from the similar words, the Ukraine War corpus is distinctive in that it has a specific set of words related to the Ukraine war like *Russians*, *Putin*, *Shtovba*, and *Petrova*, which are not present in the top ranks of the Leipzig corpora. To assess the significance of the filtered pairs in the three corpora, the average t-score and p-value are calculated and presented in [Table 17](#) below.

Table 17: Significance scores of the Ukraine War corpus and the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora

Corpus	# Filtered Pairs	Avg. t-score	Avg. p-value
Ukraine War	28	21.03	0.033
Leipzig 2014	127	42.47	0.022
Leipzig 2023	101	35.55	0.023

Based on the average t-score and p-value, the filtered pairs in the Leipzig corpora are more significant than those in the Ukraine War corpus (higher t-score and lower p-value).

It would also be interesting to compare the same pairs within the three corpora. To conduct such an “apples to apples” comparison, we attempt to find the common pairs between the three corpora using all the pairs in the Ukraine War corpus as an anchor point.

5.2.1.3 Overlapping pairs between the Ukraine War corpus and the Leipzig News corpora

Using the 1,061 passive pairs from the Ukraine War corpus as the lookup pairs, there are 177 common pairs among the three corpora, and after the filter ($f > 2$ in the Ukraine War corpus, $f > 15$ in the Leipzig corpora, and $p < 0.05$ in at least one corpus), there are 27 pairs left as shown in Table 56 in the Appendix.

Based on the average t-score and p-value, this investigation of the common pairs returns the same result; the passive subject-verb pairs in the Leipzig corpora are more significant than those in the Ukraine War corpus (t-score of 24.20 and 21.06 in the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora, respectively, compared to 9.74 of the Ukraine War corpus and p-value of 0.07 and 0.04 compared to 0.10, respectively). In addition, the meanings of these common pairs mainly fall into the categories of CIVILIAN and MILITARY for subjects and VIOLENT and RESTRICTION for verbs as observed in the previous steps.

The following sections involves a wider analysis of the Leipzig corpora. The Leipzig corpora from years 2014 - 2020 and 2023 are examined.

5.2.2 Passive voice through time

5.2.2.1 Active VS Passive

This part aims to find out the percentage of passive sentences and verbs in the corpora, as well as their significance scores. Passive sentences are counted from any sentences that contain a passive voice, and passive verbs refer to the frequencies of past participles. Auxiliaries are not counted. The percentage of passive sentences are calculated based on a total number of sentences in a corpus, and a total number of words is used to compute the percentage of passive verbs. The significance is measured with t-scores and p-values and averaged from the passive pairs with $p < 0.05$ and $f > 2$ for the Ukraine War corpus and $p < 0.05$ and $f > 15$ for the Leipzig corpora. The results are in Table 18 below.

Table 18: Active and passive voice sentences and verbs in the Leipzig corpora, as well as the Ukraine War corpus

Corpus	# Sent.	# Word	Avg. t	Avg. p	# Pass. Sent.	% Pass. Sent.	# Act. V	# Pass. V.	% Pass. V.
Leipzig_2014	756,346	16,859,763	42.2690	0.0218	141,353	18.69	839,795	86,172	0.51
Leipzig_2015	765,565	17,199,696	36.5917	0.0244	145,011	18.94	861,801	156,883	0.91
Leipzig_2016	841,467	18,425,414	37.2254	0.0238	147,064	17.48	809,908	123,474	0.67
Leipzig_2017	836,561	17,910,026	36.4439	0.0238	150,622	18.00	817,412	126,258	0.70
Leipzig_2018	839,051	17,951,801	36.7860	0.0232	151,574	18.06	812,864	126,646	0.71
Leipzig_2019	845,091	18,128,872	39.7905	0.0231	149,241	17.66	824,629	125,510	0.69
Leipzig_2020	846,917	18,342,507	37.0290	0.0240	156,139	18.44	839,485	132,617	0.72
Leipzig_2023	854,997	18,498,586	35.5474	0.0227	150,128	17.56	828,103	105,213	0.57
Avg. (Lzg.)	823,249	17,914,583	37.7104	0.0234	148,892	18.10	829,250	122,847	0.69

Continued on next page

Corpus	# Sent.	# Word	Avg. t	Avg. p	# Pass. Sent.	% Pass. Sent.	# Act. V	# Pass. V.	% Pass. V.
Ukraine War	5,269	170,834	21.0319	0.0329	2,268	43.04	8,909	1,473	14.19

The result [Table 18](#) shows that the average percentage of passive sentences in the Leipzig corpora is 18.10%, and the rate climbs up to 43.04% in the Ukraine War corpus. For the passive verbs, the Leipzig corpora contain 12.90% on average, and it is 14.19% for the Ukraine War corpus.

Examining political speeches, [Liu \(2022\)](#) discovers around 2-20% of passive sentences and averagely accounts for 10% of the text. The percentage of passive sentences in the Leipzig corpora of 18.10% falls within the same range that [Liu](#) finds out although the span in Leipzig corpora is much narrower between 17.48-18.94%.

[Di Ferrante \(2023\)](#) analyzes 30 scientific articles and press releases and finds that the number of passive words (auxiliary verbs and past participles) are found at 1.66% of total words in scientific articles and 1.28% in press releases. The percentage of passive verbs in the Leipzig corpora is more than two times lower at 0.69%. Although the corpus that [Di Ferrante](#) utilizes is much smaller, a large gap of percentage may be due to the fact that this calculation in the Leipzig corpora only takes into account past participles, not an entire verbal phrase. Analyzing the 20th century British English texts totaling 320,000 words, [Svartvik \(1966 cited in Anisfeld & Klenbort 1973\)](#) finds a much lower rate at approximately 0.14%.

Regarding the trend, [Seoane & Loureiro-Porto \(2005 cited in Di Ferrante 2023\)](#) analyze texts from scientific articles written in American and British English across three time periods: 1905-1925, 1960-1975, and 1985-1990 and find that the use of passive has been declining over that time, and the reason for such decline might be rooted in events and dynamics that are sociolinguistic in nature. Although the investigation in this section is conducted within a shorter time span of around 10 years, the result shows the same trend as the percentage of both passive sentences and verbs gradually decreased as illustrated in [Figure 8](#).

Figure 8: Percentage of passive sentences and verbs in Leipzig corpora

In terms of the significance, the average t-scores and p-values indicate that the occurrences of passive constructions found in the Ukraine War corpus are less significant (t-score of 21.0319 and p-value of 0.0329 in the Ukraine War corpus compared to 37.7104 and 0.0234, respectively, in the Leipzig corpora).

[Svartvik \(1966: 152-3\)](#) conducts a passive frequency analysis of press news (The Times in 1964 and The Daily Express in 1964 - 5,000 words each) and finds 16.4 passive clauses per 1,000 words on average. Applying the same measurement by multiplying average passive sentences of 148,892 with 1,000 and dividing with a total number of words 17,914,583, the frequency of passives in Leipzig corpora is 8.31 clauses per 1,000 words, which is around half of the [Svartvik's \(1966\)](#) finding. In the Ukraine War corpus, the rate gets closer but still a little lower at 13.28.

Apart from the difference between actives and passives, another interesting aspect widely investigated is the occurrences of agentless and agentive passives, also referred to as short and long passives.

5.2.2.2 Short VS Long passives

There seem to be a consensus among scholars that short passives are more prevalent than long passives.

Among those are [Homan \(1989\)](#), who considers long-passives as a semantic emphasis strategy that directs the FOCUS to the prepositional object by placing BY-AGENT at the end of a sentence. [Homan](#) concludes that this strategy is a rarely-used device as also mentioned in [Fillmore \(1968\)](#) and [Thompson \(1987 cited in Areibi & Al-Mijrab 2012\)](#).

Homan provides some statistics of SHORT PASSIVE according to Jespersen (1933: 254), who finds that over 70% of passives in English are a short form and even more at 80% according to Quirk et al. (1972) and Svartvik (1966). Areibi & Al-Mijrab (2012) also mention Givón & Yang’s (1994) finding of around 80-82% of short passives. Moreover, if the FOCUS of a sentence is at the end position according to what Berry (1975) suggests, then the emphasis of the SHORT PASSIVE is on the process or verb. Homan states that this conclusion may also hold true for those who claim that the FOCUS of PASSIVE is on the NEW INFORMATION at the end of the sentence.

In order to prove this observation, sub-corpora are built and examined. SpaCy parser is employed to extract BY-AGENT constructions with the dependency tag 'agent' and 'pobj', as well as any modifiers with the 'amod' and 'compound' dependency tags to retrieve a full BY-AGENT phrase for a deeper analysis as illustrated in Figure 9 and Figure 10 below.

Figure 9: Dependency parse tree of a by-agent construction with modifier

Figure 10: Dependency parse tree of a by-agent construction with compound word

The statistics of the BY-AGENT sub-corpora and the percentage of BY-AGENT passives are presented in Table 19.

Table 19: Percentage of by-agent or long passives in Leipzig corpora

Corpus	# Sentence	# Word	# Pass. Pair	# By-agent	% Long Pass.	% Short Pass.
Leipzig_2014	756,346	16,859,714	120,683	15,786	13.08	86.92
Leipzig_2015	765,565	17,199,603	125,582	16,433	13.09	86.91
Leipzig_2016	841,467	18,425,587	123,474	16,003	12.96	87.04
Leipzig_2017	836,561	17,910,042	126,257	16,226	12.85	87.15

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Corpus	# Sentence	# Word	# Passive Pair	# By-agent	% Long Passive	% Short Passive
Leipzig_2018	839,051	17,951,766	126,646	16,489	13.02	86.98
Leipzig_2019	845,091	18,128,565	125,510	16,366	13.04	86.96
Leipzig_2020	846,917	18,342,325	132,617	15,876	11.97	88.03
Leipzig_2023	854,997	18,498,430	125,547	16,297	12.98	87.02
Average	823,249	17,914,504	125,790	16,159	12.87	87.13

According to the calculation, BY-AGENT passives account for 12.87% and 87.13% for a short form of passives, which is in accordance with the findings of more than 70% of short passives by [Jespersen \(1933\)](#) and more than 80% by [Svartvik \(1966\)](#).

Figure 11: Percentage of short passive in Leipzig corpora

[Figure 11](#) shows an increase in the usage of SHORT PASSIVE in Leipzig news corpora. Even when the unusually high occurrences of SHORT PASSIVE in the year 2020 (88.03%) are substituted with an average percentage of 86.99%, a rising trend still shows.

5.2.2.3 Be- VS Get-passive

BE and GET are extracted first by identifying passive voice construction with the dependency tag `nsubjpass`. Then, auxiliary verbs are captured through the dependency tag `auxpass`, which stands for auxiliary passive. Auxiliary verbs BE and GET are extracted separately; if `aux == "be"`, the subject-verb pair is put in the BE-PASSIVE list, and if `aux == "get"`, the pairs are appended to the GET-PASSIVE list. The dependency parse trees of BE and GET are illustrated below.

Figure 12: The dependency parse trees of be passive

Figure 13: The dependency parse trees of get passive

After the BE and GET are extracted, a number of BE and GET pairs are counted. The percentage of BE and GET-PASSIVE is calculated based on a number of pairs. The results are reported in the table below.

Table 20: Percentage of be- and get- passives pairs in the Leipzig corpora

Corpus	#Sent.	#Word	#Be Pass.	#Get Pass.	%Be Pass.	%Get Pass.
Leipzig_2014	756,346	16,859,763	118,696	962	99.20	0.80
Leipzig_2015	765,565	17,199,696	123,720	867	99.30	0.70
Leipzig_2016	841,467	18,425,414	121,037	1,038	99.15	0.85
Leipzig_2017	836,561	17,910,026	123,322	1,180	99.05	0.95
Leipzig_2018	839,051	17,951,801	123,499	1,192	99.04	0.96
Leipzig_2019	845,091	18,128,872	122,446	1,159	99.06	0.94
Leipzig_2020	846,917	18,342,507	129,541	1,209	99.08	0.92
Leipzig_2023	854,997	18,498,586	122,675	1,134	99.08	0.92
Avg. (Lzg)	823,249	17,914,583	123,117	1,093	99.12	0.88

The result table shows that GET in the Leipzig corpora account for only 0.88% on average. [Figure 14](#) below shows the percentage of GET-PASSIVE through time in the Leipzig corpora. The trendline indicates a gradual increase of GET-PASSIVE occurrences in news media, which is in accordance with the claim of [Di Ferrante \(2023\)](#). [Di Ferrante](#) conducts a thorough research and notes that several studies have recorded an increase of the use of the GET-PASSIVE constructions

between the end of the 20th century and the first two decades of the 21st century (See [Biber & Gray 2016](#); [Givón & Yang 1994](#); [Mair & Leech 2006](#)).

Figure 14: Percentage of get-passives in the Leipzig corpora

According to different types of connotations that GET PASSIVE convey proposed by [Hatcher \(1949\)](#) and [Lakoff \(1971\)](#), there are only a couple of scenarios where the connotations can be found in this study.

These scenarios are constrained by genre and context of the datasets. Because this analysis focuses on news reports, a certain level of OBJECTIVITY has to be maintained as also mentioned by [Lakoff \(1971\)](#) in [Section 2.3.3.2](#). This puts a limitation on the EMOTIONAL INVOLVEMENT connotation. In other words, the “feelings” of a speaker or a writer cannot be assumed from the news reports. Moreover, in the context of news reports, a speaker or a writer does not talk about themselves, so it is unlikely to reflect if something is good or bad for them. This crosses out the EVALUATIVE ATTITUDE connotation. This leaves us with only SYMPATHY and AGENCY connotations. Take this news report from the 2014 Leipzig corpus for example.

- (51) a. Where Russia gets hit hardest among the sanctions announced Tuesday, the capital restrictions are expected to have the most damaging effect on Russia.
- b. Though the damages awarded fell far short of the amount sought, the ruling was one more blow to Russia which has just been hit with a second, tougher round of U[...]

Implementing [Chappell’s \(1984\)](#) framework on the connotations of GET PASSIVE, in [Example 51a](#), a sense of sympathy for Russia’s experience of adverse effects or hardships due to the sanctions is very clear with the use of GET PASSIVE. The use of SUPERLATIVE comparison *the hardest* and *the most damaging effect* accentuates the INFERENCE to the sufferers. In [Example 51b](#), on the other hand, BE PASSIVE makes the tone sounds declarative, presenting the information

straightforwardly that *the sanctions* are “another challenge” for Russia. There is no heightened emotional or emphatic tone seen in [Example 51a](#).

Regarding the AGENCY, GET PASSIVE in [Example 51a](#) portrays Russia as the subject who possesses some degree of AGENCY in the situation, suggesting although Russia is negatively impacted by the sanctions, Russia is not an “innocent victim” and may have an ability to handle the circumstances leading to the outcome. Conversely, BE PASSIVE in [Example 51b](#) depicts Russia as a purely passive recipient of the sanctions. This connotation is strengthened with the reference to the authority *the ruling*, meaning a decision made by a court or legal authority. In addition, *the amount sought* refers to the damages requested by the plaintiff in the legal case, highlighting the passive position of Russia in receiving the consequences of the ruling. The phrase *one more blow* conveys a cumulative sense of ADVERSITY, further reinforcing Russia’s passive position as a target of “repeated” negative actions.

Another aspect related to GET PASSIVE worth examining in the future study is inspired by the claim of [Zúñiga & Kittilä \(2019: 100\)](#) that GET PASSIVE occurs more frequently with NEGATIVE verbs that imply negative effects on the GRAMMATICAL SUBJECT. This claim is linked to SYMPATHY CONNOTATION in [Section 2.3.3.3](#) where a speaker uses GET PASSIVE to make an INFERENCE of a NEGATIVE nature about the SUBJECT.

Apart from the declining trend of PASSIVE VOICE usage, the rising trend for SHORT PASSIVE and GET PASSIVE against their counterparts, another aspect worth examining is how popular the topic related to the Ukraine War is in Western news media.

5.2.3 Ukraine War is sometimes a big deal: Topics in news reports

To investigate how commonly the Ukraine War has been presented in the news media through time, a topic modeling method is employed to examine popular topics in each year of the Leipzig corpora. Text preprocessing was conducted using spaCys transformer model `en_core_web_trf`. The pretrained language model BERT is chosen due to its capabilities in understanding context and semantics compared to traditional models like Gensims Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) leading to more coherent and meaningful topics. To see all topics of each years corpus, one corpus is processed one at a time. The datasets are sub-corpora that contain only passive voice sentences. The statistics of the corpora are shown in [Table 21](#).

Table 21: Statistics of passive voice sentence sub-corpora

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.
passive_text_leipzig_2014.txt	141,353	3,219,523	22.78
passive_text_leipzig_2015.txt	145,011	3,350,747	23.11
passive_text_leipzig_2016.txt	147,064	3,354,242	22.81

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Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.
passive_text_leipzig_2017.txt	150,622	3,471,914	23.05
passive_text_leipzig_2018.txt	151,574	3,503,306	23.11
passive_text_leipzig_2019.txt	149,241	3,454,805	23.15
passive_text_leipzig_2020.txt	156,139	3,649,509	23.37
passive_text_leipzig_2023.txt	150,128	3,505,583	23.35
Average	148,892	3,438,704	23.09

Only the topics with the significance scores greater than 500 are analyzed. If the topic related to the Ukraine War receives less than 500 significance scores, it is manually appended at the end of the list. This also applies to 8 recurring topics (in the graph below). The significance scores are normalized by dividing with a total number of words in a corpus and multiplying with 1 million.

$$\text{Normalized Significance Score} = \frac{\text{Original Score}}{\text{Corpus Size}} * 1,000,000$$

A topic of each group is derived using ChatGPT-4o to summarize member words in that specific group. [Table 57](#) in the Appendix illustrate the transformation of the top 4 topics in the score report of the 2015 Leipzig corpus (3,350,747 words).

The topics from each year with the significance scores are demonstrated in [Table 58](#) and [Table 59](#) in the Appendix. The rankings of the Russia-Ukraine conflict topic are in the squared brackets. The full summary tables with member words can be found in [Appendix 4](#).

Together with the topic of Russia-Ukraine Conflict, there are 8 recurring topics across the years: *Education, Gun Violence, Firefighting, Music, Film Industry, Parenting, Weather, and Israel-Palestine Conflict*. [Figure 15](#) below shows the significance score of each topic in the Leipzig corpora (years 2014-2020 and 2023).

Figure 15: Popular topics in the Leipzig corpora

Topic modeling method reveals a similar trend with the one of the proper noun categories; topics related to the Russia-Ukraine conflict gained the highest attention in 2014 when the war started and in 2023 when the invasion began. Actually, the significance score of the year 2018 was not so different from in 2023. The years in between showed lower engagement of this topic in the news with a surge in 2017 and 2018.

Figure 15 not only shows a similar evolving representation between the proper nouns and the topics related to the Ukraine War but also demonstrates the rankings of the Russia-Ukraine War topic compared to the other recurring ones presented in passive voice in the news. The rankings indicate that the dominant topics are related to general themes, namely *Education*, *Music*, *Parenting*, and *Fire and Firefighting*, which can be identified in the top10 in almost every year, while themes related to war and violence, such as *Israel-Palestine Conflict*, *Gun Violence*, and *Russia-Ukraine Conflict*, do not receive as much importance. The only exception is in the years 2014 and 2015 where the *Russia-Ukraine War* topic is in a high ranking in the second and fourth place, respectively, as the war began.

The topic modelling method offers an overview of the thematic representations across time, where the popularity trend of the Ukraine War topic is revealed. This utilization represents a different type of application compared to what Ylä-Anttila et al. (2022) refers to as the validation of the outputs, which ensures that “the word clusters actually represent what we think they do”.

Moving forward, a closer look is to be taken with the analysis BY-AGENT in a word level revealing how AGENCY and RESPONSIBILITY are assigned differently in the context of the Russia-Ukraine War.

5.3 Conceal and highlight: By-agent and modifier analysis

5.3.1 By-agent semantic categories

The categorization of BY-AGENTS is conducted on the Ukraine War corpus based on six semantic roles: *agentive*, *instrumental*, *undergoer*, *experiencer*, *recipient*, and *beneficiary*. There are 165 passive subject-verb pairs with BY-AGENTS. The sampled 20 pairs are as follow:

Table 22: The sampled 20 pairs of by-agent phrases with the corresponding subject-verb pairs

Subject_Verb Pairs	By-agent Phrases
attack_captured	by_Baykar_Bayraktar_TB2_drone
attack_claimed	by_hacker_cooperative
attacks_repelled	by_selfless_actions_Russian_military_personnel
attacks_staged	by_Russia
building_hit	by_apparent_rocket_strike
building_struck	by_missile
building_struck	by_drone_Russia
claim_corroborated	by_Ukrainian_parliament_Operational_Command
claim_used	by_President_Vladimir_V_Putin
claims_dismissed	by_international_community
evacuation_thwarted	by_Russian_military
medic_killed	by_second_missile
Petrova_escorted	by_police
story_haunted	by_Meghan_Markle
advance_slowed	by_resistance
advances_limited	by_Ukrainian_defences
areas_controlled	by_installed_leaders
areas_controlled	by_backed_separatists
base_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_artillery
base_plagued	by_corruption

The examination identifies only two semantic roles: AGENTIVE and INSTRUMENTAL. During the categorization process, there are six sentences that contain the thematic role CIRCUMSTANCE in by-phrase. The examples are listed below.

1. The difficulty is accentuated by geography.
2. Russia's present-day war of aggression is refashioned by propaganda...
3. Symbols are sized by the minimum number of days with reports of such attacks.

The by-phrases in these sentences do not fall into any of the six semantic roles. Instead, they describe the context or the condition under which the action occurs. These by-phrases are, therefore, excluded from the analysis. The categorization results are in [Table 23](#). The frequencies of occurrences are placed in the parentheses.

Table 23: Semantic roles of by-agent phrases with frequencies in the parentheses

Semantic Roles	Words	Total	%
Agentive	force (10), russia (8), ukraine (6), drone (6), missile (5), separatist (4), weapon (4), weaponry (3), government (3), president (3), putin (3), resistance (3), actor (2), shelling (2), shell (2), attack (2), committee (2), district (2), fighting (2), leader (2), media (2), military (2), parliament (2), people (2), rebel (2), strike (2), bomb (2), ukrainians (2), agreement, ally, authority, battle, bombardment, centre, cnn, comedian, command, commission, community, conflict, congress, corporation, corruption, country, cut, defence, director, dude, enemy, factor, federation, firm, folk, friend, frontline, gazprom, geography, guard, hacker, inconsistency, institute, intelligence, journal, loss, luhansk, markle, member, nationalist, nazis, object, organization, paratrooper, personnel, police, pravda, press, public, representative, service, shoigu, side, siren, soldier, sound, spokesman, traffic, troop, victory, warship, washington, west, whistleblower, artillery, attack, dioxin, duel, fire, projectile	158	99.37
Instrumental	stretcher	1	0.63
Total		159	100.00

Almost all of the by-phrases are categorized as *agentive* (99.38%) and only 0.62% as *instrumental*. It would be more insightful to further categorize the *agentive* by-phrases. The categories are adapted from subject categories in the Leipzig corpora, and the semantic map [Figure 24](#) is utilized to aid the categorization.

The categories of BY-AGENT in the Ukraine War corpus is shown in the [Table 24](#) below.

Table 24: Categories of by-agent in the Ukraine War corpus

Category	Words	(f)	%
Weapon	drone (6), missile (5), weapon (4), weaponry (3), bomb (2), shelling (2), shell (2), warship, duel, dioxin, artillery	28	17.72
Military and Authority	force (10), military (2), authority, command, frontline, guard, intelligence, defence, paratrooper, personnel, police, service, soldier, troop	24	15.19
Non-military Conflict- ing Parties	separatist (4), resistance (3), actor (2), rebel (2), nationalist, hacker, enemy, ally, Nazis, whistleblower, side	18	11.39
Country and City	Russia (8), Ukraine (6), Luhansk, Washington	16	10.13
Law and Governance	government (3), committee (2), parliament (2), agreement, federation, congress, representative, spokesman, corruption, corporation	14	8.86
Death and Danger	siren, fighting (2), attack (2), conflict, loss, bombardment, battle, projectile, fire, strike (2)	13	8.23
Important Figures	Putin (3), president (3), leader (2), director, Gazprom, Markle, Pravda, Shoigu	13	8.23

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Category	Words	Frequency	%
Civilian	people (2), Ukrainians (2), dude, folk, community, friend, member, public	10	6.33
Location	centre, firm, country, institute, district (2), west	7	4.43
Media, Entertainment, Technology	media (2), CNN, comedian, journal, press	6	3.80
Neutral Entities	object, factor, geography, sound, victory	5	3.16
Monetary and Business	cut, commission	2	1.27
Commute	traffic	1	0.63
Nominalization	inconsistency	1	0.63
Total		158	100.00

After categorization process, it has been found that BY-AGENTS in the Ukraine War corpus are occupied by words related to *weapon* (17.72%), *military and authority* (15.19%), *non-military conflicting parties* (11.39), and *country and city* (10.13%), closely followed by *law and governance* (8.86%), *death and danger* (8.83%), *important figures* (8.23%), and *civilian* (6.33%). *Location*, as well as *media, entertainment and technology* and *neutral entities*, are minimally identified at 4.43%, 3.80%, and 3.16%, respectively. Rarely found at only 0.63% are BY-AGENTS related to *commute* and *nominalized words*.

The results from categorizing BY-AGENTS indicate that AGENCY and RESPONSIBILITY are assigned to *weapons* as *inanimate entities* slightly more than *human entities*, namely *military and authority*, as well as *non-military parties*. In the context of war and conflict, it may be as necessary to specify who causes the action as what kind of weapons does. Taking a closer look at the most frequently used BY-AGENTS from human entities (*force, military, separatist*) and non-human entities (*drone, missile, weapon*) and what kind of actions they perform, a couple of critical observations can be made based on [Table 25](#) and [Table 26](#) below.

Table 25: Human agents in by-agent phrases

Subject_Verb Pairs	Human Agents
bridges_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_forces, by_Russian_troops
conflict_marked	by_artillery_duels, by_special_forces, by_trench
Mykolaiv_shelled	by_Russian_forces
number_reclaimed	by_Ukrainian_forces
town_occupied	by_Russian_forces
Ukrainians_killed	by_Russian_forces
Urey_captured	by_Russian_forces
Center_run	by_Special_Forces
citizen_detained	by_pro_-_Russian_separatists_forces
corridor_thwarted	by_Russian_forces
fighters_held	by_Ukrainian_forces
plant_seized	by_Russian_forces

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attacks_repelled	by_selfless_actions, by_Russian_military_personnel
evacuation_thwarted	by_Russian_military
axis_deployed	by_Western_Military_District, by_eastern
front_opened	by_Southern_Military_District
supply_held	by_Russian_military
areas_controlled	by_backed_separatists
region_run	by_backed_separatists, by_Luhansk_Republic
citizen_detained	by_pro_-_Russian_separatists_forces
territories_controlled	by_backed_separatists

Table 26: Non-human agents in by-agent phrases

Subject_Verb Pairs	Non-human Agents
attack_captured	by_Baykar_Bayraktar_TB2_drone
building_struck	by_drone, by_Russia
craft_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_drone
refinery_attacked	by_drone
strike_attacked	by_Russian_drones
tanker_damaged	by_maritime_drone
building_struck	by_missile
medic_killed	by_second_missile
Explosions_caused	by_long-range_missiles_by_Ukraine, by_United_Kingdom
people_killed	by_Russian_missile_attack, by_southern_Ukrainian_city_Odesa
people_killed	by_missile
enemy_struck	by_aviation_missile
deaths_caused	by_explosive_weapons_by_wide_area_effects
tanks_demolished	by_small_Ukrainian_defensive_units, by_weapons_such_as_Stingers
targets_struck	by_unconfirmed_weaponry
University_hit	by_weapons

Table 25 and Table 26 reflect how agency and responsibility are delegated differently between HUMAN and NON-HUMAN AGENTS. The verbs that occur as actions caused by NON-HUMAN AGENTS are mostly VIOLENT verbs (*destroy, attack, damage, strike, kill, demolish, hit*) at 81.25% (13/16 counts) while the verbs used with HUMAN AGENTS are mainly RESTRICTIVE verbs (*occupy, capture, detain, thwart, hold, seize, control*) at 52.38% (11/21 counts), and VIOLENT verbs associated with HUMAN AGENTS are only found at 14.29% (3/21 counts). This implies that news reports tend to avoid explicitly portraying HUMAN AGENTS to perform VIOLENT actions and assign the VIOLENT actions to NON-HUMAN AGENTS instead. At the same time, LESS VIOLENT actions, i.e. RESTRICTIVE actions, are preferably represented to be caused by human actors.

This finding adds up to the emotionally demoting effect of passive voice when BY-AGENTS are present. The strategy is implemented through the assignment of VIOLENT verbs to NON-HUMAN actors and LESS-VIOLENT verbs to HUMAN actors. The next section further investigates how

Russia and Ukraine are represented in the news. Examining these entities in the modifier of subject, as a subject, and in an agentive phrase is expected to reveal their images in media.

5.3.2 Russia(n) and Ukraine(ian) in three positions: modifier, subject, and agentive phrase

This analysis includes 4 proper nouns: *Russia, Russian, Ukraine, Ukrainian*, in three different positions in a sentence: MODIFIER OF SUBJECT, SUBJECT, and AGENT. The analysis is conducted for two pairs of proper nouns: RUSSIA and RUSSIAN, as well as UKRAINE and UKRAINIAN. Only the pairs with $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ are analyzed. The results are presented in a table, together with a syntactic-semantic schema at the end of each table reflecting sentence structure and meaning of verbs. The schema contains the proper noun in each position and the percentage of verb occurrences categorized based on their semantic meanings. The interpretation of the overall results can be found upon the end of the section.

5.3.2.1 Russia and Russian as modifier

Table 27: Russia and Russian as modifier

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
Russian	advances_limited	by_Ukrainian_defences
Russian_invasion	efforts_frustrated	by_staunch_Ukrainian_resistance
heavy_Russian	force_defeated	by_light_first_century_one
Russian	forces_hindered	by_supply_issues
Russian	invasion_met	by_fierce_Ukrainian_resistance
Russian_class_landing	craft_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_drone
Russian_military	funerals_reported	by_local_authorities
Russian	presence_allowed	by_agreement_Ukraine
Russian_landing	ship_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_rocket_attack
Russian	tanks_demolished	by_small_Ukrainian_defensive_units
Russian_naval	targets_struck	by_unconfirmed_weaponry

- RUSSIAN X + 5 VIOLENT VERBS [45.45%] + BY UKRAINIAN X / *weapon*
- RUSSIAN X + 2 RESTRICTIVE VERBS [18.18%] + BY UKRAINIAN X
- RUSSIAN X + 2 NEUTRAL VERBS [18.18%] (*meet, report*) + BY UKRAINIAN X
- RUSSIAN X + 1 NEGATIVE VERBS [9.09%] (*frustrate*) + BY UKRAINIAN X
- RUSSIAN X + 1 POSITIVE VERBS [9.09%] (*allow*) + BY UKRAINE

5.3.2.2 Russia and Russian as subject

Table 28: Russia and Russian as subject

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
-	Russia_led	by_presidents
-	Russians_thwarted	by_combination_factors

- RUSSIA + LED + BY ...
- RUSSIANS + RESTRICTIVE VERB + BY ...

5.3.2.3 Russia and Russian as agent

Table 29: Russia and Russian as agent

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
-	attacks_repelled	by_selfless_actions_Russian_military_personnel
claimed	attacks_staged	by_Russia
story	building_struck	by_drone_Russia
-	evacuation_thwarted	by_Russian_military
Several	bridges_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_forces_Russian_troops
-	city_battered	by_weeks_Russian_bombardment
-	city_devastated	by_Russian_shelling
-	Mykolaiv_shelled	by_Russian_forces
-	number_captured	by_Russia
-	people_killed	by_Russian_missile_attack_southern_Ukrainian_city_Odesa
-	region_occupied	by_Russian_troops
-	town_occupied	by_Russian_forces
-	Ukrainians_held	by_Russia
-	Ukrainians_killed	by_Russian_forces
worker Paul	Urey_captured	by_Russian_forces
-	agreement_brought	by_representative_Russian_Federation
-	Amvrosiivka_occupied	by_Russian_paratroopers_by_armoured_vehicles_artillery
Ukrainian	boats_seized	by_Russian_warships
American	citizen_detained	by_pro-Russian_separatists_forces
evacuation	corridor_thwarted	by_Russian_forces
EU	countries_affected	by_Russian_gas_supply_cuts
Davis	Cup_won	by_Russia
-	Cyberwarfare_used	by_Russia
storey	house_struck	by_Russian_shells
-	leaders_replaced	by_people_ties_Russian_security_services_Russian_businesses
official	medal_produced	by_Russian_Federation
-	Moldova_attacked	by_Russia
largest_nuclear	plant_seized	by_Russian_forces
-	principle_respected	by_international_actors_Russian_Federation
art	school_destroyed	by_Russian_bombs
Ukrainian	servicemen_held	by_Russia

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Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
vile	strike_attacked	by_Russian_drones
similar	stunt_carried	by_pair_Russian_comedians
food	supply_held	by_Russian_military
Ukrainian	surgeon_captured	by_Russian_soldiers
-	values_discarded	by_Russia
northwestern	village_hit	by_Russian_shells_residential

- SOMETHING + 14 RESTRICTIVE VERBS [40%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- SOMETHING + 12 VIOLENT VERBS [34.29%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- SOMETHING + 4 NEGATIVE VERBS [11.43%] (*repel, stage, use cyberwarfare, discard*) + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- SOMETHING + 3 NEUTRAL VERBS [8.57%] (*carry, bring, replace*) + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- SOMETHING + 2 POSITIVE VERBS [5.71%] (*win, respect*) + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X

5.3.2.4 Ukraine and Ukrainian as modifier

Table 30: Ukraine and Ukrainian as modifier

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
Ukrainian	boats_seized	by_Russian_warships
Ukrainian	servicemen_held	by_Russia
Ukrainian	surgeon_captured	by_Russian_soldiers

- UKRAINIAN X + RESTRICTIVE VERBS + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X

5.3.2.5 Ukraine and Ukrainian as subject

Table 31: Ukraine and Ukrainian as subject

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
-	Ukraine_led	by_presidents
-	Ukraine_ruled	by_Nazi_government
-	Ukrainians_held	by_Russia
-	Ukrainians_killed	by_Russian_forces

- Ukrainian X + restrictive/violent verbs + Russia
- Ukrainian X + repressive verbs + *Nazi government*
- Ukraine + led by + ...

5.3.2.6 Ukraine and Ukrainian as agent

Table 32: Ukraine and Ukrainian as agent

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
-	claim_corroborated	by_Ukrainian_parliament_Operational_Command
Russian	advances_limited	by_Ukrainian_defences
-	base_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_artillery
Several	bridges_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_forces_Russian_troops
-	efforts_complemented	by_private_sector_firms
Russian_invasion	efforts_frustrated	by_staunch_Ukrainian_resistance
-	Explosions_caused	by_long_range_missiles_Ukraine_by_United_Kingdom
Russian	invasion_met	by_fierce_Ukrainian_resistance
-	number_reclaimed	by_Ukrainian_forces
-	one_welcomed	by_most_Ukrainians
-	people_killed	by_Russian_missile_attack
-	poll_taken	by_Ukrainian_biggest_market_research_organization
multiple	towns_hit	by_Ukraine
old	boy_crucified	by_Ukrainian_nationalists
-	campaigns_counteracted	by_Ukraine_social_media_campaigns
-	contest_won	by_Kalush_Orchestra_folk_rap_Ukraine
Russian_class_landing	craft_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_drone
-	documents_provided	by_whistleblower
separatist	fighters_held	by_Ukrainian_forces
Easter	holiday_observed	by_many_Ukrainians
sharp	increase_considered	by_Ukraine
-	Medvedev_described	by_Ukrainian_media
-	move_denounced	by_leaders_Ukraine
-	person_killed	by_Ukrainian_shelling
Russian	presence_allowed	by_agreement_Ukraine
disputed	referendums_recognised	by_Ukraine_other_UN_member
-	Reports_reported	by_Ukrainska_Pravda
Russian_landing	ship_destroyed	by_Ukrainian_rocket_attack
-	statement_regarded	by_Ukrainian_government
Russian	tanks_demolished	by_small_Ukrainian_defensive_units
-	those_released	by_Ukraine
-	withdrawal_confirmed	by_Ukraine

- something + 10 positive verbs [31.25%] (*corroborate, complement, welcome, reclaim, win, allow, recognize, confirm, regard, release*) + by Ukraine/Ukrainian X
- something + 9 violent verbs [28.13%] + by Ukraine/Ukrainian X
- something + 8 neutral verbs [25%] (*cause, meet, take, provide, observe, consider, describe, report*) + by Ukraine/Ukrainian X
- something + 3 negative verbs [9.37%] (*frustrate, counter, denounce*) + by Ukraine/Ukrainian X
- something + 2 restrictive verb [6.25%] (*limit, hold*) + by Ukrainian force/defense

5.3.2.7 Interpretation of the results (Ukraine War corpus)

The interpretation of sentence structure and verb meanings yields three observations. Firstly, *Russia/Russian* are found to be used with *violent*, *restrictive*, and *negative* verbs in both MODIFIER and AGENT positions at a noticeably high rate (72.72% as MODIFIER and 85.72% as AGENT). Secondly, *Ukraine/Ukrainian* as an AGENT are found to be used most often with *positive* and *neutral* verbs at 56.25% while *violent*, *restrictive*, and *negative* verbs are identified much less frequently than with *Russia/Russian* at 43.75%. Lastly, *Ukraine/Ukrainian* are used as a LOGICAL OBJECT or an UNDERGOER and in a MODIFYING PHRASE almost two times less frequently than *Russia/Russian* (7 and 13 occurrences, respectively).

These findings imply that the proper nouns *Russia*, *Russian* are represented more negatively as an AGENT and are portrayed as “victims” (used as a receiver of actions) more frequently than *Ukraine*, *Ukrainian* in Western media.

The next chapter shifts focus to examine Russian news sources, presenting the other side of the coin. The comprehensive comparison of both sides aims to offer a balanced perspective on the portrayals of Russia and Ukraine in international reporting.

5.4 The perspectives from another side: Russian news sources

The datasets for the Russian news sources are gathered from SketchEngine (Kilgarriff et al. 2014). The search method is different from the Ukraine War corpus because this time, the compilation is based on specified web URLs, instead of sets of keywords. The English-speaking Russian news sources include TASS (<https://tass.com/>), the Arctic (<https://arctic.ru/>), and The Moscow Times (<https://www.themoscowtimes.com/>).

The statistics of the three Russian News corpora are in Table 33. The passive pairs are filtered on the basis of frequencies and p-values. The minimum frequencies of the Arctic and TASS corpora are adjusted from 2 to 1 to get a sufficient, comparable, and representative number of pairs because at $f > 2$, only 16 pairs in the Arctic and 7 in TASS corpus remain.

Table 33: Statistics of Russian news corpora

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.	#All Passive Pair	#Filtered Passive Pair
Arctic	4,705	203,785	43.31	1,614	47
TASS	6,866	219,684	32.00	1,663	30
The Moscow Times	5,571	206,742	37.11	1,695	30
Average	5,714	210,737	37.47	1,657	36

An overview of the first 10 subject-verb pairs in the three Russian corpora is in Table 34 below.

Table 34: Top 10 significant pairs in English speaking Russian news sources

#	Arctic	(f)	t-score	p-value	The Moscow Times	(f)	t-score	p-value	TASS	(f)	t-score	p-value
1	rubles_allocated	16	24.69	0.03	decision_made	19	20.57	0.03	homes_flooded	5	25.88	0.03
2	projects_imple- mented	13	14.74	0.04	meeting_held	14	12.76	0.05	episode_recorded	4	34.47	0.02
3	law_submitted	9	17.69	0.04	agreement_ signed	13	15.92	0.04	name_changed	4	22.46	0.03
4	jobs_created	8	17.83	0.04	people_evacu- ated	8	19.24	0.03	deputy_appointed	3	15.82	0.04
5	rubles_invested	7	19.22	0.03	contract_signed	8	15.02	0.04	contest_held	3	15.82	0.04
6	residents_regis- tered	5	23.43	0.03	decision_taken	8	12.77	0.05	law_passed	3	17.80	0.04
7	results_published	5	15.84	0.04	agreement_ reached	7	15.99	0.04	authorities_ required	3	29.85	0.02
8	list_compiled	4	24.60	0.03	sanctions_ imposed	5	24.87	0.03	foreigners_per- plexed	2	34.53	0.02
9	directive_signed	4	19.68	0.03	event_organized	5	18.12	0.04	miners_trapped	2	16.82	0.04
10	contracts_signed	4	15.99	0.04	tickets_sold	4	41.00	0.02	cat_thrown	2	24.37	0.03

After getting the Russian corpus database, it goes through the examinations of popular topics, as well as by-agent and modifier analysis. Popular topic analysis using topic modeling helps to gauge the characteristics of Russian news sources and determine an appropriate news source for the following investigation. By-agent and modifier analysis specifically examines how Russia and Ukraine are represented in the Russian news source, and the interpretative results are compared with the ones of the Ukraine War corpus, representing Western news media.

5.4.1 Popular topics (Russian news sources)

To perform a topic modelling, subcorpora containing only passive voice sentences are created, and only the 15 most significant topics are taken into account. The statistics of the Russian passive subcorpora are in the [Table 35](#) below.

Table 35: Statistics of Russian passive voice sub-corpora

Corpus	#Sentence	#Word	Word/Sent.
passive_text_arctic	1,972	47,555	24.12
passive_text_tass	2,054	51,291	24.97
passive_text_themoscowtimes	2,173	52,643	24.23
Average	2,066	50,496	24.44

Topic keywords and scores from the topic modelling report are transformed and summarized using the same methodologies with the Leipzig corpora. The summary table can be found below.

Table 36: Topic keywords and scores of the Russian news sources

#	Topic_Arctic	Score	Topic_TASS	Score	Topic_TMCM	Score
1	Icebreakers	368.03	Russian Economy	628.18	Crime and Law Enforcement	952.88
2	Ports and Routes	245.36	Arts and Culture	377.82	Middle East Conflict	406.30
3	Budget and Finance	225.73	Climate and Wildfires	332.30	Military and Defense	353.10
4	Polar Wildlife	201.19	Cuisine	304.98	Economic Development	348.26
5	Legal Framework	196.29	Conflict and Casualties	218.50	Ukraine Conflict	237.01
6	Education	196.29	Flooding and Rivers	218.50	Natural Disasters	232.17
7	Government and Development	186.47	Arrests and Trials	213.94	International Treaties	227.34
8	Climate Change	186.47	Environmental Issues	204.84	Sports and Doping	222.50
9	Energy Resources	186.47	Political Appointments	204.84	Space Exploration	183.80
10	Economic Development	181.56	Chechnya and Kadyrov	172.98	Energy Sector	183.80
11	Arctic Council	181.56	Drone Attacks	145.66	Ceasefire Agreements	174.13
12	Future Expectations	181.56	Family and Custody	145.66	Diplomatic Meetings	169.29
13	Arctic Geography	171.75	Georgia and Politics	145.66	Economic Forums	164.46
14	Forums and Events	132.49	Ukraine Conflict	122.90	Presidential Delegations	140.27
15	Indigenous Peoples	117.77	Linguistics	122.90	Soccer Tournaments	130.60

*TMCM = The Moscow Times

Table 36 shows that the topic related to the Ukraine conflict is ranked fourteenth in TASS corpus and fifth in the Moscow Times corpus, and there is no discussion about Ukraine in the Arctic corpus. The full tables with keywords and scores can be found in Table 51 - 53 in the Appendix.

The topics of each corpus reflect clearer characteristics of the Russian news media. Arctic News Media primarily focuses on Arctic-specific issues including *environmental*, *economic*, and *infrastructural* topics, with significant attention to *polar wildlife* and *climate change*. TASS provides comprehensive coverage of *economic* issues, *cultural* events, and *climate*-related topics, with additional focus on *legal* issues and *political* developments. The Moscow Times focuses heavily on *crime and law enforcement*, with significant attention to *international conflicts*, *military* issues, and *economic* development. These results confirm and enhance the findings from the previous section.

With the highest score of the Ukraine conflict topic and the topics related to international conflicts (*Middle East* and *Ukraine*), as well as *military and defense*, it is clear that The Moscow Times (TMCM) has the most international outward-looking outlook. For this reason The Moscow Times corpus is chosen in the by-agent and modifier analysis to examine how Russia and Ukraine are represented.

5.4.2 By-agent and modifier analysis

The same BY-AGENT AND MODIFIER ANALYSIS is conducted to analyze the representations of RUSSIA and UKRAINE in the Russian news corpora (The Moscow Times corpus). Four proper nouns (*Russia, Russian, Ukraine, Ukrainian*) are investigated in pairs and in three positions: MODIFIER OF SUBJECT, SUBJECT, and BY-AGENT. Only the pairs with $p < 0.05$ are analyzed. Since *Ukraine* and the occurrences of *Ukrainian* are low based on the p-value filter (only 1 as a MODIFIER and none for the other two positions), the filter is removed to get adequate data for the analysis. The results are as follow:

5.4.2.1 Russia and Russian as modifier

Table 37: Russia and Russian as modifier

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
Russian	Il-20_shot	by_air_defense
Russian	peacekeepers_deployed	
Russian	peacekeepers_deployed	
Russian	sailors_suspected	
Russian	sailors_suspected	
single_Russian_military	serviceman_left	
Russian	servicemen_activated	

- RUSSIAN + 4 NEUTRAL VERBS (*deploy, leave, activate*) [57.14%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- RUSSIAN + 1 VIOLENT VERB (*shoot*) [14.29%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- RUSSIAN + 2 NEGATIVE VERB (*suspect*) [28.57%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X

5.4.2.2 Russia and Russian as subject

Table 38: Russia and Russian as subject

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
	Russia_represented	by_Deputy_Foreign_Minister_Sergey_Ryabkov
	Russia_represented	by_Russian_Prime_Minister_Dmitry_Medvedev
	Russia_represented	by_Russian_Prime_Minister_Dmitry_Medvedev
	Russia_guided	by_United_documents_Sustainable_Development_them
hosts	Russia_set	
	Russia_stuck	
	Russia_stuck	
	Russia_punished	
	Russia_scheduled	
	Russia_blamed	
	Russia_affected	

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Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
	Russia_set	
	Russia_accused	
	Russian_sent	
	Russian_set	
	Russian_beaten	
	Russians_suspected	
	Russians_suspected	

- RUSSIA + 7 NEGATIVE VERBS (*punish, blame, affect, accuse, beat, suspect*) [38.89%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- RUSSIA + 2 RESTRICTIVE VERB (*stick*) [11.11%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- RUSSIA + 5 NEUTRAL VERBS (*set, send, schedule*) [27.78%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X
- RUSSIA + 4 POSITIVE VERBS (*represent, guide*) [22.22%] + BY RUSSIA/RUSSIAN X

5.4.2.3 Russia and Russian as agent

Table 39: Russia and Russian as agent

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
	agreement_signed	by_General_Serbian_Railways_Infrastructure_Miroljub
	agreement_signed	by_Minister_Construction_Zorana_Director_Russian_Railways_Oleg
roadmap	criteria_fulfilled	by_Russian_side
event	organized	by_Bank_Russia
event	organized	by_Bank_Russia
Princess	accompanied	by_representatives_Saransk_eparchy_Russian_Orthodox_Church
Russia	represented	by_Russian_Prime_Minister_Dmitry_Medvedev
Russia	represented	by_Russian_Prime_Minister_Dmitry_Medvedev

- SOMETHING + 5 POSITIVE VERBS (*represent, fulfill, sign*) [62.5%] + BY RUSSIA
- SOMETHING + 3 NEUTRAL VERBS (*accompany, organize*) [37.5%] + BY RUSSIA

5.4.2.4 Ukraine and Ukrainian as modifier

Table 40: Ukraine and Ukrainian as modifier

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
Ukrainian	citizens_obliged	
Ukrainian_armed	forces_put	by_decision_chief_General_Staff
new_Ukrainian	government_formed	by_members_former_president
Ukrainian_education	law_amended	
Ukrainian_crew	members_arrested	
Ukrainian_crew	members_arrested	
Ukrainian	sailors_detained	

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Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
Ukrainian	servicemen_wounded	
Ukrainian	ships_detained	
Ukrainian	side_gearred	

- UKRAINIAN + 1 HARMFUL VERBS (*wound*) [10%]
- UKRAINIAN + 5 NEUTRAL VERBS (*oblige, put, form, amend, gear*) [50%]
- UKRAINIAN + 4 RESTRICTIVE VERBS (*detain, arrest*) [40%]

5.4.2.5 Ukraine and Ukrainian as subject

Table 41: Ukraine and Ukrainian as subject

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
	Ukraine_crowded	

5.4.2.6 Ukraine and Ukrainian as agent

Table 42: Ukraine and Ukrainian as agent

Modifier	Subject_Verb	Agent
other	broadcasters_placed	by_Council_Ukraine
inauguration	ceremony_attended	by_former_Ukrainian_Presidents
	document_signed	by_Verkhovna_Rada_speaker_Ukraine
	document_signed	by_Verkhovna_Rada_speaker_Ukraine
	total_fired	by_Ukrainian_troops
	total_fired	by_Ukrainian_troops

- SOMETHING + 2 VIOLENT VERB (*fire*) [33.33%] + BY UKRAINE
- SOMETHING + 4 NEUTRAL VERBS (*sign, attend, place*) [66.67%] + BY UKRAINE

5.4.2.7 Interpretation of the results (Russian news corpora)

Based on the SYNTACTIC-SEMANTIC SCHEMAS, RUSSIA and RUSSIAN behave differently in each position, taking on HARMFUL and NEGATIVE verbs at the MODIFIER position (42.86%), NEGATIVE and RESTRICTIVE verbs as a SUBJECT (50%), and only POSITIVE and NEUTRAL as AGENT (100%) while UKRAINE and UKRAINIAN are found with RESTRICTIVE and HARMFUL verbs as a MODIFIER (50%) and VIOLENT verbs as AGENT (33.33%). Both UKRAINE and RUSSIA are often used with NEGATIVE verbs including HARMFUL and RESTRICTIVE verbs as a MODIFIER; for example, *Russian_sailors_suspected* and *Ukrainian_crew_members_arrested*. As an AGENT, on the other hand, RUSSIA and UKRAINE are represented differently; RUSSIA are associated with only POSITIVE and NEUTRAL verbs while UKRAINE is found with VIOLENT verbs.

5.4.2.8 Comparison with the analysis from the Ukraine War corpus

In summary, by comparing the representations of RUSSIA and UKRAINE in the Ukraine War corpus found in [Section 5.3.2.7](#) and the Russian news corpora using the BY-AGENT AND MODIFIER ANALYSIS method, the following findings are identified. RUSSIA is portrayed more negatively often in a context of AGGRESSION, LIMITATION, or NEGATIVITY in the Ukraine War Corpus compared to how it is depicted in Russian news sources, especially in the AGENT position that portrays RUSSIA as acting in a positive or neutral manner. UKRAINE is depicted more positively in the Ukraine War Corpus, especially as an AGENT, compared to the more adversarial representation in Russian news sources. The frequency of VIOLENT verbs associated with UKRAINE in both corpora indicates a focus on conflict-related actions, while Russia's association with POSITIVE verbs in the Russian news sources contrasts with its more NEGATIVE portrayal in the Ukraine War Corpus.

6 Conclusion

The extensive analysis presented in this study provides a comprehensive view of passive subject-verb pairs, proper nouns, and passive voice in general. The examination is conducted in the Ukraine War corpus, representing a specific corpus, Leipzig corpora, representing a general corpus, and Russian news corpora, representing news reports from the opposition stand point. A combination of NLP and Corpus Linguistics methods helps to reveal agency and responsibility, representations, as well as trends over time. The main tools are spaCy parser used to extract passive pairs, as well as t-score and p-value, used as the measure of collocational strength and the filter of the significant pairs. Semantic map aids with the categorization of subjects and verbs, and topic modeling shows the popularity of topic related to the Ukraine War in news across the years.

The analyses start from building a framework based on the Ukraine War corpus including subject and verb categories, important figures, and proper noun representation. These findings are then compared with more general news reports like the Leipzig corpora. Leipzig corpora, with the datasets expanding for almost a decade, allow for diachronic analyses, namely active and passive voice, short and long passives, as well as be- and get- passives. By-agent and modifier analysis further reveals how Russia and Ukraine are portrayed. The study would not have been completed without taking into consideration the Russian viewpoint. Using the Russian news sources, topic modeling and by-agent analysis are conducted. Harnessing the NLP and Corpus Linguistics methods applied on three different corpora, the results reveal how the agency and responsibility are delegated, how Russia and Ukraine are represented, and in a broader picture, how the usage of passive voice evolves over time.

Subject and verb categorization in the Ukraine War corpus in [Section 5.1.1.3.3](#) provides a framework for later analyses. The comparison of passive subject-verb pairs between the Ukraine War corpus and the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora in [Section 5.2.1.3](#) shows an interesting finding. Although the Leipzig corpora are non-specific news corpora, they shares similar passive pairs with the Ukraine War corpus, emphasizing civilian and military subjects, as well as violent and restrictive verbs.

Proper noun representations of Russia- and Ukraine-related entities in the Ukraine War corpus differ significantly (see [Section 5.1.2](#)). Russian entities are depicted using the euphemism signaling mechanistic dehumanization, reducing emotional impact and individual recognition. In

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contrast, Ukrainians are often portrayed as victims through the use of violent verbs. Additionally, activists, advocates, poets, and artists appear more frequently under Russian nationalities, emphasizing the malevolent image of Russia who suppresses the dissent and creative expressions of their own citizens. This malicious portrayal of Russia also extends to the foreign citizens since international victims are identified.

The analysis of proper nouns over time in [Section 5.1.2.3](#) reveals that the usage of proper nouns related to the conflict follows a U-shaped pattern, peaking in 2014 and 2023, corresponding to significant events like the annexation of Crimea and the 2023 invasion. Topic modeling in [Section 5.2.3](#) indicates similar trends, with high attention to the Russia-Ukraine conflict in 2014 and 2023, interspersed with fluctuations reflecting ongoing diplomatic and cyber-attack events. The diachronic analysis of passive voice in [Section 5.2.2](#) also indicates that the usage of short passives and get passives increases over time, but the usage of passive voice in general gradually decreases.

The by-agent and modifier analysis in [Section 5.3](#) indicates that agency and responsibility are more frequently assigned to non-human entities like weapons, which are associated with violent actions. Human agents are more often linked with restrictive actions, suggesting a narrative strategy that distances human actors from direct violence. Furthermore, Russia is depicted negatively in the Ukraine War corpus, especially in agent roles, whereas in Russian news sources in [Section 5.4.2.7](#), it is associated with positive or neutral actions. Ukraine, conversely, is portrayed more positively as an agent in the Ukraine War corpus but is associated with conflict-related actions in Russian news sources.

7 Discussions

This project provides a nuanced analysis of how passive voice constructions in news media shape the portrayal of Russia and Ukraine, highlighting significant differences between Western and Russian media. It also underscores the importance of contextual and comprehensive analysis when interpreting passive voice usage and news media. This study also introduces further considerations regarding the biases inherent in media sources, opens up for the implications for future research, and raises critical limitations related to computational tools used.

A critical insight of this study is that passive voice constructions alone may not fully capture how responsibility and agency are portrayed. Both victim blaming (Bohner 2001) or culprit hiding (Katz 2006) need to be understood within the broader context of the entire news report. While TV news once dictated the pace of information consumption (Homan 1989), online news now allows readers to control their reading time. This shift allows for the examination of an entire article and their broader context.

The study shows that passive voice serves various purposes beyond obscuring the actor or minimizing wrongdoing. While it can distance readers from the actor, it also serves stylistic or narrative functions. This complexity necessitates a nuanced perspective towards passive constructions within the context of news reporting and in general.

The U-shaped pattern in proper noun representation and fluctuations in Leipzig corpora during significant events reflect both the importance of these events and the media's tendency to perpetuate situations to attract attention from the audience. The media's role in amplifying the significance of events through continuous reporting and reprinting highlights the need for a critical viewpoint to understanding media narratives. In addition, the increasing use of short passives and get passives, alongside a general decline in passive voice, suggests evolving narrative strategies and possible changes in media consumption habits.

The dominance of Anglo-Saxon media sources in the web-crawled Ukraine War corpus, constituting 78.99% of the data (Table 60), introduces significant bias into the analysis. This Western dominance raises questions about the objectivity and fairness of media reporting. Mahbubani (2022) argues that simplistic black-and-white perspectives from major Western outlets like THE ECONOMIST and THE NEW YORK TIMES often fail to capture the full complexity of geopolitical issues, particularly concerning countries like China and Russia. Future research should compare

findings with non-Western and non-English-speaking news sources to provide a more balanced view and better understand how different media systems represent global events.

This study encourages further exploration of linguistic phenomena using authentic language, large datasets, and usage-based methods. Most importantly, it highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to media analysis that considers the full context of news reports from all angles, as well as the synchronic and diachronic analysis. Future research should build on this project by investigating how different representations of agency and responsibility impact the audience's perceptions and attitudes across different cultures and languages.

Last but not least, this project employs several computational tools, namely spaCy parser and static word embedding model, which come with obvious benefits but also limitations that can or cannot be mitigated.

7.1 Limitations of spaCy parser and static embedding models

Although spaCy text parser offers the simplicity of use with robust algorithms through a simple pipeline, further configurations on the code are needed for certain purposes to achieve a deeper analysis, as well as comprehensive and insightful results. In addition, a smaller language model equipped in spaCy, while offering time and resource efficiency, may produce incorrect parsing results.

One notable limitation of spaCy is its inability to handle referential dependencies beyond the sentence level. This issue includes identifying pronouns or numbers referring to entities in different sentences, or dealing with semantically inherent passive constructions, which [Lehmann & Schneider \(2009\)](#) term as NON-LOCAL subjects and objects. For instance, in the sentence *He was released on 28 October 2022, and reached Ukrainian-controlled territory by 14 December*, the PRONOUN *He* refers back to *An American citizen* from the previous sentence. This connection is beyond spaCys dependency boundary.

Additionally, spaCy struggles with NUMERICAL SUBJECT without HEAD NOUN and INHERENT PASSIVE CONSTRUCTION. For example, in the sentence *December 2022, of which 13 died and 50 were wounded between 1 January and 25 February 2022*, phrases like *4,163 killed* and *17,329 wounded* are shortened forms of *4,163 who were killed* and *17,329 who were wounded*. These constructions are tagged with `acl` (adjectival clause) rather than reflecting a passive voice relationship.

Similarly, it is cumbersome to count the frequencies of compound structures, or what [Kübler et al. \(2009\)](#) call COORDINATION. For example, the counting of subjects and verbs in the sentence *Paul Urey and Dylan Healy were charged with mercenarism and captured by Russian forces.*

may require tedious manual process as the compound subjects and verbs need to be segregated, resulting in four pairs: *Urey_charged*, *Urey_captured*, *Healy_charged*, and *Healy_captured*.

Last but not least, spaCy offers different NLP models with difference levels of performance ([Available trained pipelines for English 2023](#)) accommodating various task requirements from a small model *en_core_web_sm* opt for a fast parsing with less accuracy (90-92% for parser) to the currently largest model with transformer architecture *en_core_web_trf* returning the most accurate results (94-95% for parser) but slower processing time and higher computational resource consumption. While the performance gap is minimal, a small model can cause inaccurate results as demonstrated in [Figure 16](#) and [Figure 17](#) below. The small model *en_core_web_sm* mistakenly tags *areas* as the head noun of the relative clause *of whom 208 had been located* whereas the transformer model *en_core_web_trf* correctly identifies *civilians* as the head noun. Using the small model can lead to an incorrect dependency parsing and compromise the accuracy.

Figure 16: Parsed text by a small model, en_core_web_sm

Figure 17: Parsed text by a transformer model, en_core_web_trf

For static embedding models like Word2Vec, while they are simple and fast, the training algorithms allow them to learn only one fixed embedding for each word in a corpus used for training [Jurafsky & Martin \(2023: 120\)](#), so they cannot plot a coordinate on a semantic map based on the new context in which the word occurs. However for the categorization purpose in this study, the static embedding model offers clearer groupings as mentioned in [Section 4.1.3](#).

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Corpora

1. [Ukraine corpus](#)
2. [Leipzig corpora](#)
3. **Russian news corpora**
 - 3.1 [Arctic](#)
 - 3.2 [TASS](#)
 - 3.3 [The Moscow Times](#)

Appendix 2: Source codes

All source codes are stored in the [Github repository](#).¹ Within the repository, the following codes can be found:

1. **Extractions for a master data**
 - 1.1 [Passive pairs](#)
 - 1.2 [Frequencies of passive pairs](#)
 - 1.2.1 [Frequencies among the passive pairs](#)
 - 1.2.2 [Frequencies from an entire corpus](#)
 - 1.3 [Observed frequencies \(for the contingency table\)](#)²
 - 1.4 [Passive texts](#)
2. **Other extractions and visualizations**
 - 2.1 [Proper noun](#)

¹Please contact n.sanitdee@gmail.com for any inquiries.

²Data arrangement of the input file has to be in 4 columns: 1. Subject_Verb_Pairs 2. s 3. v 4. O(sy_vy) where Subject_Verb_Pairs = the pairs in subject_verb format, s = Subjects, v = Verbs, O(sy_vy) = Occurrences of the pairs.

- 2.2 Semantic map³
- 2.3 By-agents and modifiers
- 2.4 Active voice constructions
- 2.5 Be- and get-passives
- 2.6 Topic modeling
- 3. **Statistical calculations**
 - 3.1 Power analysis
 - 3.2 p-values
 - 3.2.1 p-value of t-score
 - 3.2.2 p-value of Chi-squared test score
 - 3.2.3 p-value of Fisher's test score

Appendix 3: News links from SketchEngine

SketchEngine looks at 3 keywords at a time. Therefore, there are 3 sets of news links as follow:

1. Russo-Ukrainian War, Ukraine War, Russia's war in Ukraine (33/33 selected)

apnews.com/article/russia-dissent-crackdown-ordinary-people-c102c4f4f4fa7d11e5d3587257ecd864
apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-what-you-need-to-know-2f94db1fa8cb96c47d7885efafbf4e79
en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russian_invasion_of_Ukraine
en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russo-Ukrainian_War
news.sky.com/story/russia-ukraine-war-latest-putin-election-live-updates-sky-news-blog-12541713
theconversation.com/no-the-west-is-not-to-blame-for-russias-war-in-ukraine-why-this-myth-and-others-are-so-difficult-to-dispel-226306
aljazeera.com/news/2022/2/28/russia-ukraine-crisis-in-maps-and-charts-live-news-interactive
aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/16/russia-ukraine-war-list-of-key-events-day-752
bbc.com/news/war-in-ukraine
bbc.com/news/world-europe-60506682
bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-03-17/putin-takes-record-election-win-to-press-russia-s-war-in-ukraine
cnbc.com/2024/03/14/ukraine-war-live-updates-latest-news-on-russia-and-the-war-in-ukraine.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-04-23-22/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-06-24-22/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-07-15-22/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-2-5-23-intl/index.html
cnn.com/world/europe/ukraine
ft.com/content/4351d5b0-0888-4b47-9368-6bc4dfbccbf5
iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2023/01/strategic-survey-2022-russias-war-in-ukraine/
nbcnews.com/news/world/farmers-protests-india-europe-ukraine-war-grain-prices-rcna143816
nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMp2207415
npr.org/2023/02/22/1157106172/ukraine-russia-war-refugees-food-prices
nytimes.com/article/ukraine-russia-war-timeline.html
nytimes.com/live/2022/03/01/world/ukraine-russia-war
nytimes.com/live/2022/05/20/world/russia-ukraine-war
nytimes.com/news-event/ukraine-russia
rand.org/latest/russia-ukraine.html

³This code is adapted from Parker (2022). Replace the code in https://colab.research.google.com/github/futuremojo/nlp-demystified/blob/main/notebooks/nlpdemystified_word_vectors.ipynb in the section where the Principal Components Analysis (PCA) is implemented.

reuters.com/world/europe/blood-billions-cost-russias-war-ukraine-2023-08-23/
 reuters.com/world/ukraine-russia-war/
 theguardian.com/world/live/2024/mar/15/russia-ukraine-war-russia-election-putin-macron-zelenskiy-belgorod-moscow-live-updates
 theguardian.com/world/series/ukraine-live/latest
 vox.com/22970918/russia-war-in-ukraine-explained
 washingtonpost.com/world/2024/03/20/czech-republic-slovakia-split-prague-russia-ukraine/

2. Russo-Ukrainian War, Russia-Ukraine war, Russia's war in Ukraine (31/31 selected)

apnews.com/article/russia-dissent-crackdown-ordinary-people-c102c4f4f4fa7d11e5d3587257ecd864
 apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-putin-nuclear-weapons-82ced2419d93ae733161b56fbd9b477d
 apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-what-you-need-to-know-2f94db1fa8cb96c47d7885efafbf4e79
 en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russo-Ukrainian_War
 foreignpolicy.com/2024/03/19/technology-ai-drones-stalemate-ukraine-russia-manpower/
 news.sky.com/story/russia-ukraine-war-latest-putin-election-live-updates-sky-news-blog-12541713
 aljazeera.com/news/2022/2/28/russia-ukraine-crisis-in-maps-and-charts-live-news-interactive
 aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/16/russia-ukraine-war-list-of-key-events-day-752
 bbc.com/news/war-in-ukraine
 bbc.com/news/world-europe-60506682
 bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-03-17/putin-takes-record-election-win-to-press-russia-s-war-in-ukraine
 cnbc.com/2024/03/14/ukraine-war-live-updates-latest-news-on-russia-and-the-war-in-ukraine.html
 cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-04-23-22/index.html
 cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-07-15-22/index.html
 cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-2-5-23-intl/index.html
 cnn.com/world/europe/ukraine
 dw.com/en/russias-war-in-ukraine/t-60931789
 iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2023/01/strategic-survey-2022-russias-war-in-ukraine/
 nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMp2207415
 npr.org/2023/02/22/1157106172/ukraine-russia-war-refugees-food-prices
 nytimes.com/article/ukraine-russia-war-timeline.html
 nytimes.com/live/2022/03/01/world/ukraine-russia-war
 nytimes.com/news-event/ukraine-russia
 rand.org/latest/russia-ukraine.html
 reuters.com/world/europe/blood-billions-cost-russias-war-ukraine-2023-08-23/
 reuters.com/world/ukraine-russia-war/
 theguardian.com/world/2024/feb/18/russia-ukraine-war-at-a-glance-what-we-know-on-day-725
 theguardian.com/world/live/2024/mar/15/russia-ukraine-war-russia-election-putin-macron-zelenskiy-belgorod-moscow-live-updates
 theguardian.com/world/series/ukraine-live/latest
 vox.com/2022/2/23/22948534/russia-ukraine-war-putin-explosions-invasion-explained
 vox.com/22970918/russia-war-in-ukraine-explained

Russo-Ukrainian War, Russia-Ukraine war, Ukraine War (37/37 selected)

apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-drone-attack-f0e717ace1b9a4c286fe1d2e112d74fe
 apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-putin-nuclear-weapons-82ced2419d93ae733161b56fbd9b477d
 en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Casualties_of_the_Russo-Ukrainian_War
 en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outline_of_the_Russo-Ukrainian_War
 en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russo-Ukrainian_War
 news.sky.com/video/ukraine-missile-attacks-hit-kyiv-after-ukrainian-rockets-hit-400-miles-inside-russia-ukraine-war-13099401
 warontherocks.com/understanding-the-russo-ukrainian-war-a-guide-from-war-on-the-rocks/
 aljazeera.com/news/2022/2/28/russia-ukraine-crisis-in-maps-and-charts-live-news-interactive
 aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/16/russia-ukraine-war-list-of-key-events-day-752
 aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/18/russia-ukraine-war-list-of-key-events-day-753
 aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/18/ukraine-debates-mobilising-more-men-to-fight-russia-after-two-years-of-war
 bbc.com/news/explainers-62902029

bbc.com/news/war-in-ukraine
bbc.com/news/world-europe-60504334
bbc.com/news/world-europe-60506682
bbc.com/news/world-europe-68590088
bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-03-17/putin-takes-record-election-win-to-press-russia-s-war-in-ukraine
cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/conflict-ukraine
cnbc.com/2024/03/15/russia-ukraine-live-updates.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-2-5-23-intl/index.html
cnn.com/world/europe/ukraine
cnn.com/world/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-12-29-23/index.html
ft.com/content/4351d5b0-0888-4b47-9368-6bc4dfbccbf5
irishtimes.com/world/europe/2024/03/20/russia-ukraine-war-latest/
nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_192648.htm
nato.int/docu/review/articles/2022/07/07/the-consequences-of-russias-invasion-of-ukraine-for-international-security-nato-and-beyond/index.html
nytimes.com/2023/08/18/us/politics/ukraine-russia-war-casualties.html
nytimes.com/2024/03/05/world/europe/ukraine-war-russia-planes.html
nytimes.com/2024/03/12/world/europe/ukraine-drone-russia-jamming.html
nytimes.com/article/ukraine-russia-war-timeline.html
nytimes.com/interactive/2022/world/europe/ukraine-maps.html
nytimes.com/news-event/ukraine-russia
rand.org/latest/russia-ukraine.html
theguardian.com/world/2024/mar/14/ukraine-russia-war-update-today-aid-putin-zelenskiy
theguardian.com/world/live/2024/mar/13/ukraine-russia-war-live-vladimir-putin-volodymyr-zelenskiy-nato
theguardian.com/world/series/ukraine-live/latest
vox.com/2022/2/23/22948534/russia-ukraine-war-putin-explosions-invasion-explained

3. Russia-Ukraine war, Ukraine War, Russia's war in Ukraine (37/37 selected)

apnews.com/article/russia-dissent-crackdown-ordinary-people-c102c4f4f4fa7d11e5d3587257ecd864
apnews.com/article/russia-ukraine-war-drone-attack-f0e717ace1b9a4c286fe1d2e112d74fe
foreignpolicy.com/2024/03/19/technology-ai-drones-stalemate-ukraine-russia-manpower/
news.sky.com/story/ukraine-russia-war-news-putin-zelenskyy-latest-live-updates-12541713?wpmobileexternal=true
aljazeera.com/news/2022/2/28/russia-ukraine-crisis-in-maps-and-charts-live-news-interactive
aljazeera.com/news/2022/8/24/timeline-six-months-of-russias-war-in-ukraine
aljazeera.com/news/2024/3/20/russia-ukraine-war-list-of-key-events-day-755
atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/six-months-twenty-three-lessons-what-the-world-has-learned-from-russias-war-in-ukraine/
bbc.com/news/war-in-ukraine
bbc.com/news/world-europe-60506682
bbc.com/news/world-europe-68573646
bbc.com/news/world-europe-68590088
bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-03-17/putin-takes-record-election-win-to-press-russia-s-war-in-ukraine
cnbc.com/2024/03/13/ukraine-war-live-updates-latest-news-on-russia-and-the-war-in-ukraine.html
cnbc.com/2024/03/14/ukraine-war-live-updates-latest-news-on-russia-and-the-war-in-ukraine.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-04-23-22/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-04-29-23/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-06-24-22/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-08-06-23/index.html
cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-2-5-23-intl/index.html
cnn.com/world/europe/ukraine
iea.org/topics/russias-war-on-ukraine
iiss.org/online-analysis/online-analysis/2023/01/strategic-survey-2022-russias-war-in-ukraine/
nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMp2207415
nytimes.com/2024/03/05/world/europe/ukraine-war-russia-planes.html
nytimes.com/article/ukraine-russia-war-timeline.html
nytimes.com/news-event/ukraine-russia

pbs.org/newshour/world/1-year-after-the-invasion-began-a-timeline-of-russias-war-in-ukraine
 rand.org/latest/russia-ukraine.html
 reuters.com/world/europe/blood-billions-cost-russias-war-ukraine-2023-08-23/
 theguardian.com/world/2022/mar/17/russias-war-in-ukraine-complete-guide-in-maps-video-and-pictures
 theguardian.com/world/2024/mar/15/ukraine-war-briefing-russian-forces-fending-off-attacks-by-pro-kyiv-fighters
 usip.org/publications/2024/03/ukraine-war-takes-toll-russia
 vox.com/2022/2/23/22948534/russia-ukraine-war-putin-explosions-invasion-explained
 vox.com/22970918/russia-war-in-ukraine-explained
 vox.com/22989379/russia-ukraine-war-putin-zelenskyy-us-nato-explainer-questions
 washingtonpost.com/world/2024/03/20/czech-republic-slovakia-split-prague-russia-ukraine/

Appendix 4: Topic keywords and scores

Leipzig corpora

Table 43: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2014

Topic_Lpz_14	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Education	1920	596.36	school, student, teacher, education, college, class, teach, grade, exam, district
Russia-Ukraine Conflict	1789	555.67	ukraine, russia, russian, ukrainian, putin, crimea, moscow, kiev, separatist, donetsk
Israel-Palestine Conflict	1619	502.87	israel, israeli, gaza, palestinian, hamas, palestinians, jewish, rocket, jerusalem, israelis
Gun Violence	1479	459.38	gun, shoot, shooting, firearm, officer, wound, gunshot, bullet, knife, kill
Film Industry	1249	387.95	film, movie, actor, nominate, oscar, star, comedy, episode, actress, drama
Medical Emergencies	1199	372.42	hospital, ambulance, injury, stable, condition, transport, take, airlift, critical, medical
China Relations	1163	361.23	china, chinese, beijing, hong, kong, taiwan, japan, abe, japanese, zhou
Music	965	299.73	music, song, album, band, dance, grammy, singer, artist, guitar, musical
Fire and Firefighting	927	287.93	fire, firefighter, blaze, flame, burn, extinguish, wildfire, crew, arson, destroy
Space Exploration	741	230.16	space, mars, moon, nasa, earth, spacecraft, comet, planet, orbit, rover
Parenting	732	227.36	bear, daughter, baby, son, father, grizzly, live, mother, raise, kan
Weather and Natural Dis.	649	201.58	snow, temperature, wind, rain, storm, forecast, weather, hurricane, inch, snowfall
Sexual Violence	595	184.81	sexual, rape, assault, sexually, sex, abuse, indecent, count, girl, offender
Soccer	593	184.19	goalkeeper, brazil, goal, cup, striker, footed, penalty, minute, madrid, shot
Pets	587	182.33	dog, animal, pet, cat, cruelty, puppy, owner, humane, euthanize, kennel
Ebola Outbreak	586	182.01	ebola, outbreak, virus, africa, leone, liberia, infect, sierra, patient, guinea
Smartphones	561	174.25	iphone, apple, android, tablet, samsung, smartphone, ipad, device, galaxy, blackberry
Protests	536	166.48	protest, protester, demonstration, demonstrator, rally, activist, arrest, peaceful, riot

Table 44: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2015

Topic_Lpz_15	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Education	1724	514.51	school, student, teacher, education, college, university, class, grade, teach, scholarship
Gun Violence	1447	431.84	gun, shooting, shoot, gunshot, shot, gunfire, officer, fatally, firearm, bullet
Fire and Firefighting	1201	358.43	fire, firefighter, flame, wildfire, blaze, burn, extinguish, engulf, firework, crew
Russia-Ukraine Conflict	1186	353.95	ukraine, russia, russian, ukrainian, putin, moscow, donetsk, minsk, vladimir, crimea
Space Exploration	1073	320.23	mars, nasa, earth, moon, pluto, space, planet, spacecraft, comet, rover
Middle East Conflict	940	280.53	syria, iraq, isis, syrian, iraqi, islamic, assad, al, ramadi, sunni
Religion	767	228.90	pope, church, francis, vatican, faith, religion, catholic, priest, bishop, religious
Sexual Violence	754	225.02	sexual, rape, sexually, sex, assault, abuse, pornography, offender, child, prostitution

Continued on next page

APPENDIX

Topic_Lpz_15	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Parenting	707	211.00	bear, baby, son, daughter, child, mrs, birth, congenital, mother, raise
China Relations	661	197.27	china, chinese, taiwan, beijing, hong, xi, kong, communist, taiwanese, wang
Greek Crisis	627	187.12	greece, greek, bailout, tsipras, euro, athens, eurozone, creditor, debt, imf
Israel-Palestine Conflict	613	182.94	israeli, palestinian, israel, palestinians, israelis, gaza, jerusalem, hamas, jewish, stabbing
Paris Attacks	591	176.38	paris, french, france, belgium, belgian, attack, brussels, abaaoud, terror, raid
Crime	568	169.51	arrest, theft, warrant, burglary, charge, felony, mischief, shoplifting, misdemeanor, county
Cybersecurity	514	153.40	password, hacker, hack, encrypt, encryption, malware, privacy, breach, vulnerability
Weather & Nat. Dis.	496	148.03	snow, rain, temperature, weather, wind, forecast, storm, expect, inch, centimetre
Music	491	146.53	album, song, band, music, jazz, lyric, guitar, singer, musician, perform
Film Industry	151	45.06	film, movie, sequel, filmmaker, documentary, cinema, murray, quentin, lovefilm, elstree

Table 45: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2016

Topic_Lpz_16	Score	Norm. Sc.	Keywords
Education and Schooling	3544	1056.57	school, student, teacher, college, scholarship, university, grade, graduate, elementary
Parenting	2039	607.89	bear, daughter, late, son, baby, july, raise, mrs, mary, sr
Legal and Court Matters	1707	508.91	court, trial, jury, appeal, judge, case, attorney, guilty, lawyer, supreme
Religion and Clergy	1409	420.07	god, pope, faith, jesus, bishop, priest, church, christ, religious, pastor
Fire and Firefighting	1150	342.85	fire, firefighter, burn, wildfire, firework, blaze, flame, smoke, department, extinguish
Music	1042	310.65	music, song, album, band, guitar, musician, musical, orchestra, rock, jazz
Art and Museums	898	267.72	art, artist, museum, painting, paint, gallery, exhibit, exhibition, artwork, mural
Death and Obituaries	792	236.12	precede, death, brother, sister, parent, husband, son, predecease, grandson, father
Sports and Games	782	233.14	yard, touchdown, goal, foul, penalty, ball, quarterback, shot, defensive, score
Journalism and Publishing	734	218.83	newspaper, news, editor, publish, journalism, reporter, magazine, story, print, article
Cooking and Food	706	210.48	sauce, dish, fry, cheese, bread, cook, recipe, grill, slice, meat
Weather and Natural Dis.	648	193.19	weather, temperature, rain, hurricane, storm, forecast, snow, wind, winter, tornado
Film Industry	616	183.65	film, movie, actor, screen, festival, star, cinema, filmmaker, documentary, hollywood
Medical and Emergency	571	170.23	hospital, ambulance, injury, transport, airlift, treat, medical, emergency, rush, treatment
Charity and Volunteering	559	166.65	donation, volunteer, donate, charitable, charity, fundraising, nonprofit, donor, organization
Funerals and Memorial	556	165.76	funeral, officiate, chapel, rev, service, hold, church, baptist, home, pastor
Fashion and Clothing	535	159.50	dress, wear, shoe, costume, fashion, clothing, shirt, clothe, fabric, leather
Fishing and Wildlife	526	156.82	fish, fishing, fishery, salmon, bait, trout, catch, angler, fisherman, wildlife
Alcohol and Beverages	523	155.92	wine, beer, bottle, brewery, winery, liquor, grape, drink, brew, beverage
Pets and Animals	508	151.45	dog, pet, animal, cat, puppy, leash, shelter, owner, pup, breed
Agriculture and Farming	486	144.89	farmer, crop, agriculture, seed, corn, agricultural, plant, farming, farm, fertilizer
Israel-Palestine Conflict	425	126.71	israel, israeli, palestinian, gaza, hamas, israelis, netanyahu, jerusalem, palestine
Russia-Ukraine Conflict	164	48.89	russia, putin, russian, soviet, ukraine, moscow, kremlin, vladimir, minsk, russians
Gun Violence	62	18.48	gun, nra, firearm, control, violence, law, federal, restricted, rifle, outlaw

Table 46: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2017

Topic_Lpz_17	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Music	1910	550.21	music, song, album, band, dance, musician, musical, concert, singer, perform
Education	1802	518.98	school, teacher, student, education, college, university, scholarship, graduate, class, program
Film Industry	1790	515.55	film, movie, actor, star, wars, marvel, character, batman, role, cinema
Gun Violence	1090	314.05	shoot, shooting, gun, firearm, ammunition, kill, rifle, fatally, wound, shot
Medical Emergencies	966	278.19	hospital, injury, ambulance, rush, transport, condition, critical, threaten, medical, take
Fire and Firefighting	905	260.67	fire, firefighter, blaze, wildfire, flame, burn, extinguish, firework, crew, damage
Parenting	852	245.43	bear, daughter, late, baby, son, july, grizzly, sr, mae, april
Weather and Natural Dis.	647	186.35	hurricane, wind, storm, rain, irma, weather, temperature, snow, mph, forecast
Obituaries	639	184.05	precede, sister, brother, survive, grandchild, death, parent, husband, daughter, niece

Continued on next page

Topic_Lpz_17	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Art	637	183.48	art, museum, painting, artist, exhibit, paint, artwork, gallery, exhibition, sculpture
Gender Issues	609	175.37	gender, transgender, gay, woman, lgbt, lgbtq, female, sex, male, feminist
Pets	575	165.63	dog, animal, pet, cat, rescue, shelter, owner, puppy, humane, cruelty
Culinary	554	159.64	dish, sauce, cook, cheese, chicken, flavor, fry, chef, ingredient, salad
Prison	521	150.06	prison, sentence, inmate, parole, jail, probation, imprisonment, prisoner, convict, serve
Israel-Palestine Conflict	344	99.08	israel, israeli, palestinian, palestinians, jerusalem, netanyahu, hamas, gaza, palestine, israelis
Russia-Ukr. Confl.	340	97.89	russia, putin, moscow, ukraine, russians, vladimir, trump, crimea, election

Table 47: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2018

Topic_Lpz_18	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Weather and Natural Dis.	2290	653.67	water, rain, snow, flood, hurricane, storm, weather, wind, flooding, temperature
Food and Dining	2250	642.25	food, restaurant, beer, meal, wine, dish, drink, menu, coffee, eat
Music	2101	599.72	music, song, album, band, dance, singer, perform, musical, concert, musician
Education and Schooling	1875	535.21	school, student, scholarship, education, teacher, college, exam, university, academic
Soccer and Sports	1421	405.62	chelsea, goal, arsenal, league, manchester, mourinho, liverpool, penalty, referee, midfielder
American Football	1206	344.25	quarterback, coach, draft, nfl, yard, defensive, offensive, pick, brady, qb
Fire and Firefighting	1203	343.39	fire, firefighter, flame, burn, wildfire, blaze, smoke, firework, crew, extinguish
Parenting	1069	305.14	bear, daughter, late, son, baby, april, cub, raise, william, july
Israel-Palestine Conflict	1006	287.16	israel, israeli, gaza, jews, jewish, palestinian, palestinians, hamas, netanyahu, jerusalem
Elections and Voting	944	269.46	voter, ballot, election, vote, voting, polling, republican, poll, candidate, democrats
Religion and Clergy	913	260.61	church, god, priest, bishop, pope, diocese, catholic, jesus, vatican, archbishop
Nigerian Politics	861	245.77	apc, buhari, nigeria, pdp, muhammadu, nigerians, president, governor, chairman, atiku
Energy and Resources	783	223.50	oil, gas, pipeline, energy, coal, solar, mining, fuel, crude, electricity
Russia-Ukr. Confl.	666	190.11	russia, putin, moscow, skripal, vladimir, ukraine, novichok, agent, sergei
Film Industry	606	172.98	film, movie, actor, cast, theater, director, script, filmmaker, sequel, direct
Prisons and Sentencing	574	163.85	prison, sentence, jail, inmate, parole, probation, prisoner, imprisonment, convict, serve
Drugs and Addiction	525	149.86	drug, opioid, prescription, overdose, addiction, fentanyl, substance, fda, medication
Pets and Animals	513	146.43	dog, animal, pet, cat, puppy, cruelty, leash, vet, shelter, kitten
China and Trade	503	143.58	china, tariff, chinese, trade, beijing, xi, huawei, steel, meng, jinping
Gun Violence	309	88.20	shoot, shooting, fatally, wound, gunfire, gunshot, man, officer, kill, chicago

Table 48: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2019

Topic_Lpz_19	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
American Football	2487	719.87	quarterback, game, yard, nfl, season, coach, draft, injury, touchdown, defensive
Music	2155	623.77	music, song, album, band, dance, singer, musical, concert, sing, musician
Education	2020	584.69	school, teacher, student, education, college, university, exam, scholarship, class, grade
Cryptocurrency	1402	405.81	cryptocurrency, btc, exchange, token, coin, purchase, idex, buy, following, cryptopia
Housing Market	1197	346.47	housing, rent, building, property, lease, demolish, apartment, land, rental, build
Social Media	1050	303.92	facebook, twitter, media, social, news, tweet, publish, article, journalist, editor
Fire and Firefighting	1006	291.19	fire, firefighter, burn, blaze, wildfire, flame, extinguish, firework, crew, smoke
Transportation	994	287.72	bridge, traffic, bus, road, lane, route, reopen, highway, close, train
Culinary Arts	957	277.01	chef, dish, menu, restaurant, fry, cook, chicken, dinner, flavor, food
Brexit	915	264.85	brexit, eu, corbyn, johnson, labour, boris, tory, britain, referendum, backstop
Parenting	900	260.51	bear, baby, late, son, daughter, mae, ruth, william, april, helen
Medical Emergencies	659	190.75	hospital, injury, ambulance, transport, threaten, condition, airlift, medical, paramedic, take
Police Investigations	626	181.20	police, information, stopper, contact, crime, detective, anonymously, incident, whereabouts
Obituaries	604	174.83	precede, brother, sister, survive, grandchild, parent, death, husband, daughter, predecease
Pets	543	157.17	dog, pet, animal, cat, cruelty, puppy, kitten, shelter, owner, rescue
Religion	532	153.99	priest, church, god, catholic, bishop, pope, diocese, vatican, faith, pastor

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Topic_Lpz_19	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Middle East Conflict	513	148.49	syria, kurdish, turkish, turkey, syrian, baghdadi, isis, al, erdogan, fighter
Weather and Nat. Dis.	440	127.36	wind, snow, temperature, rain, forecast, weather, storm, shower, mph, thunderstorm
Gun Violence	347	100.44	shoot, shooting, gunshot, wound, fatally, kill, bullet, gunman, chicago, officer
Israel-Palestine Conflict	306	88.57	israel, palestinian, gaza, israeli, palestinians, hamas, israelis, jerusalem, palestine, jihad
Film Industry	248	71.78	film, kapoor, khan, directorial, actor, salman, starrer, bollywood, ranveer, films
Russia-Ukr. Confl.	198	57.31	ukraine, giuliani, ukrainian, yovanovitch, zelensky, biden, trump, volodymyr, rudy, aid

Table 49: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2020

Topic_Lpz_20	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
US Election	6396	1752.56	election, ballot, vote, voter, biden, trump, elect, president, party, candidate
Education	2899	794.35	school, student, education, teacher, learning, class, college, exam, university, grade
Sanity Measures	1636	448.28	mask, wear, face, covering, glove, disinfect, distancing, sanitize, sanitizer, clean
Gun Violence	1356	371.56	arrest, shoot, shooting, firearm, gunshot, wound, robbery, gun, charge, man
Music	1223	335.11	song, album, music, singer, band, rapper, musician, musical, lyric, artist
Fire and Firefighting	1168	320.04	fire, firefighter, burn, bushfire, flame, wildfire, blaze, smoke, extinguish, destroy
Coronavirus	1058	289.90	coronavirus, novel, infect, case, confirm, test, patient, positive, outbreak, infection
Weather and Natural Dis.	975	267.16	rain, storm, flood, weather, hurricane, snow, flooding, wind, temperature, forecast
Court	965	264.42	court, appeal, trial, judge, lawsuit, supreme, lawyer, hearing, attorney, jury
Parenting	799	218.93	bear, baby, son, daughter, late, father, raise, helen, mother, cub
Quarantine	738	202.22	quarantine, hotel, arrival, self, traveller, mandatory, contact, isolation, positive, day
Middle East Conflict	721	197.56	iran, iranian, iraq, soleimani, tehran, syria, baghdad, iraqi, syrian, turkish
Fashion	660	180.85	dress, hair, shirt, wear, shoe, fashion, clothe, clothing, leather, jacket
Vaccine	655	179.48	vaccine, vaccinate, vaccination, dose, pfizer, moderna, trial, develop, administer, biontech
Religion	627	171.80	church, jesus, god, prayer, worship, religious, faith, bishop, pope, pastor
Pets	619	169.61	dog, animal, pet, zoo, cat, elephant, tiger, puppy, veterinary, owner
Soccer	613	167.97	arsenal, liverpool, manchester, midfielder, chelsea, goal, penalty, barcelona, madrid, league
Virus	568	155.64	virus, infect, spread, symptom, test, transmission, positive, expose, infected, contagious
Gaming	567	155.36	game, console, xbox, playstation, nintendo, sony, gaming, pc, release, gamer
Cryptocurrency	564	154.54	btc, cryptocurrency, exchange, token, coin, purchase, buy, idex, following, coinexchange
Traffic	554	151.80	road, traffic, lane, street, parking, highway, park, motorist, avenue, intersection
Lockdown	549	150.43	lockdown, lift, restriction, impose, ease, lock, shutdown, partial, strict, extend
American Football	548	150.16	draft, quarterback, yard, nfl, touchdown, brady, patriots, pick, defensive, cornerback
Racism	534	146.32	racism, black, racial, slavery, racist, slave, white, color, discrimination, african
Israel-Palestine Conflict	370	101.38	israel, palestinian, israeli, netanyahu, gaza, palestinians, hamas, arab, gantz, israelis
Film Industry	259	70.97	khan, film, actor, salman, bollywood, hindi, kapoor, hai, telugu, vijay
Russia-Ukr. Confl.	70	19.18	putin, russia, russian, moscow, vladimir, kgb, ukraine, soviet, sergey, crimea

Table 50: Topic keywords and scores in the Leipzig corpus 2023

Topic_Lpz_23	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Music	1889	538.85	music, song, album, band, concert, musical, dance, perform, singer, artist
Education	1629	464.69	school, education, student, teacher, college, exam, university, pupil, teach, primary
Israel and Palestine	1608	458.70	israel, gaza, israeli, hamas, palestinian, palestinians, jewish, hostage, netanyahu, jews
Sports (Soccer)	1188	338.89	league, chelsea, manchester, club, arsenal, premier, united, midfielder, liverpool, newcastle
Crime	1018	290.39	arrest, murder, charge, suspicion, suspect, warrant, connection, custody, man, assault
Food and Beverage	849	242.19	sauce, cheese, dish, cook, meal, bread, menu, flavor, pie, onion
Fire and Firefighting	812	231.63	fire, firefighter, wildfire, blaze, crew, extinguish, flame, firework, burn, rescue
Water and Weather	807	230.20	water, flood, flooding, river, dam, sewage, rain, sewer, storm, reservoir
Economic Growth	803	229.06	growth, revenue, stock, margin, offset, undervalue, market, index, valuation, portfolio
Weather Conditions	717	204.53	rain, temperature, weather, forecast, wind, snow, storm, warning, thunderstorm, expect

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Topic_Lpz_23	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Pets and Animals	686	195.69	dog, pet, animal, cat, breed, puppy, owner, cruelty, vet, kennel
Events and Festivals	679	193.69	event, festival, invite, celebration, celebrate, hold, anniversary, attend, host, annual
Ukr.-Russia Confl.	597	170.30	ukraine, russian, putin, russia, ukrainian, moscow, invasion, wagner, war, vladimir
NFL Football	589	168.02	draft, quarterback, yard, nfl, pick, touchdown, steelers, receiver, defensive, offensive
Drug-related Activities	576	164.31	cannabis, drug, cocaine, marijuana, possession, seize, methamphetamine, heroin, substance
Maritime Activities	558	159.17	vessel, ship, boat, lifeboat, sea, coastguard, submarine, coast, rescue, maritime
Art and Museums	541	154.33	museum, artist, art, painting, paint, gallery, exhibition, artwork, exhibit, sculpture
Religion and Church	538	153.47	church, god, pope, bishop, priest, vatican, jesus, holy, prayer, francis
Movies and Cinema	525	149.76	film, movie, theater, actor, festival, cinema, cast, release, role, filmmaker
Fashion and Clothing	512	146.05	wear, dress, shoe, shirt, jacket, black, fabric, pant, fashion, pair
Parenting	497	141.77	bear, raise, daughter, son, late, william, mae, mary, york, twin

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Russian news corpora

Table 51: Topic keywords and scores in the Arctic corpus

Topic_Arctic	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Icebreakers	75	368.03	icebreaker, ice, platform, nuclear, floe, ship, resistant, helicopter, shipyard, petersburg
Ports and Routes	50	245.36	port, route, sea, cargo, ton, northern, ship, terminal, transport, million
Budget and Finance	46	225.73	ruble, billion, allocate, million, budget, investment, purpose, federal, estimate, total
Polar Wildlife	41	201.19	bear, polar, island, animal, find, mammoth, count, scientist, species, walrus
Legal Framework	40	196.29	law, draft, land, submit, дума, plot, relevant, adopt, house, state
Education	40	196.29	student, teacher, university, institution, school, profession, educational, training, research
Gov. & Dev.	38	186.47	east, far, ministry, development, russian, arctic, corporation, share, agency, minister
Climate Change	38	186.47	climate, temperature, ice, change, melt, greenland, record, lake, glacier, coast
Energy Resources	38	186.47	gas, deposit, oil, lng, produce, mineral, production, fuel, coal, promising
Economic Development	37	181.56	economic, development, job, arctic, socioeconomic, worker, zone, far, economy, human
Arctic Council	37	181.56	council, foreign, arctic, ministerial, cooperation, russia, secretary, reykjavik, denmark
Future Expectations	37	181.56	expect, step, time, accept, vilyuisky, august, end, population, complete, applicant
Arctic Geography	35	171.75	island, archipelago, zemlya, novaya, franz, josef, geographical, land, find, admiral
Forums and Events	27	132.49	forum, hold, event, international, petersburg, st, tourist, festival, break, arctic
Indigenous Peoples	24	117.77	indigenous, people, language, ethnic, small, cultural, group, culture, linguistic, forum

Table 52: Topic keywords and scores in TASS corpus

Topic_TASS	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Russian Economy	138	628.18	russia, tax, economy, sanction, sell, income, north, russian, payment, spending
Arts and Culture	83	377.82	film, director, theater, artist, museum, soviet, book, life, dance, performance
Climate and Wildfires	73	332.30	fire, wildfire, climate, forest, region, temperature, arctic, change, year, degree
Cuisine	67	304.98	meat, dish, porridge, macaroni, serve, cream, guryev, cook, fish, oven
Conflict and Casualties	48	218.50	injure, kill, wound, shelling, people, gladkov, shrapnel, die, say, region
Flooding and Rivers	48	218.50	flood, river, orenburg, dam, water, orsk, ural, level, home, flooding
Arrests and Trials	47	213.94	arrest, charge, sentence, year, prison, trial, detention, favorskaya, detain, evan
Environmental Issues	45	204.84	fuel, submarine, waste, uranium, mineral, extraction, reactor, environmental, project, coal
Political Appointments	45	204.84	minister, appoint, putin, governor, deputy, term, presidential, replace, president, new
Chechnya and Kadyrov	38	172.98	kadyrov, chechnya, ramzan, chechen, kadyrovtsy, akhmat, appoint, alaudinov, assassinate
Drone Attacks	32	145.66	drone, target, region, attack, destroy, defense, ukrainian, ministry, say, strike

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Topic_TASS	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Family and Custody	32	145.66	child, marriage, custody, couple, marry, family, victim, parent, mother, germany
Georgia and Politics	32	145.66	georgia, georgian, dream, bill, foreign, law, party, rally, parliament, tbilisi
Ukraine Conflict	27	122.90	ukraine, support, ukrainian, kyiv, defeat, troop, western, catastrophic, european, fascist
Linguistics	27	122.90	call, word, ear, verb, kind, particle, earbud, different, case, way

Table 53: Topic keywords and scores in the Moscow Times corpus

Topic_TMCT	Score	Norm. Score	Keywords
Crime & Law	197	952.88	criminal, arrest, detain, moscow, police, case, charge, russian, court, crime
Middle East Conflict	84	406.30	syria, syrian, israel, zone, idlib, escalation, turkey, de, israeli, turkish
Military and Defense	73	353.10	missile, system, tank, sea, naval, launch, vehicle, defense, cruise, aircraft
Economic Development	72	348.26	project, development, company, energy, estimate, wind, industry, farm, murmansk, budget
Ukrainian Politics	49	237.01	election, rada, law, ukrainian, verkhovna, zelensky, ukraine, parliament, language, bill
Natural Disasters	48	232.17	flood, people, evacuate, water, emergency, river, damage, region, house, child
International Treaties	47	227.34	treaty, inf, soviet, union, washington, ryabkov, russia, deputy, moscow, russian
Sports and Doping	46	222.50	doping, anti, wada, sport, hockey, rusada, athlete, paralympic, olympic, games
Space Exploration	38	183.80	soyuz, spacecraft, launch, satellite, rocket, space, iss, robot, baikonur, orbit
Energy Sector	38	183.80	gas, pipeline, oil, stream, european, commission, consultation, fuel, russia, trilateral
Ceasefire Agreements	36	174.13	ceasefire, donbass, status, minsk, contact, agreement, grant, settlement, conflict, azerbaijan
Diplomatic Meetings	35	169.29	meeting, talk, ministerial, draft, committee, hold, joint, monitoring, discussion, future
Economic Forums	34	164.46	forum, economic, hold, conference, china, attend, eastern, petersburg, mongolia, st
Presidential Delegations	29	140.27	president, delegation, meeting, putin, japanese, ambassador, accompany, visit, hold, summit
Soccer Tournaments	27	130.60	match, play, cup, stadium, city, fifa, world, july, sochi, england

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Appendix 5: Tables and figures

Figure 18: Semantic categories of passive subjects in the 2014 Leipzig corpus

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Figure 19: The histogram of the p-value of t-score, the p-value of chi-squared test score, and the p-value of Fisher's exact test score in the Ukraine War corpus and the 2014 and the 2023 Leipzig corpora

Figure 20: Semantic categories of passive verbs in the 2014 Leipzig corpus

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Figure 21: Semantic categories of passive subjects in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

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Figure 22: Semantic categories of passive verbs in the 2023 Leipzig corpus

[Return to [Section 5.1.1.2.4 Leipzig 2023: Verbs](#)]

Table 54: Proper nouns in the Ukraine War corpus

Category	Sub-cat_1	Sub-cat_2	Proper Noun Subject	Verbs	%
People	Ukrainian	Government and Military Officials	- Yanukovich (Former President), Serhiy (Luhansk regional military administration), Nikulin (police officer), Savluchenko (head of the Department of Youth and Sports of Kherson), Zelensky (Current President), Yushchenko (Former President), Budanov (military leader)	lined, killed, released, declared, removed, poisoned, born, discussed, expected	5.23%
		Athlete	- Svitolina (Wimbledon semi-finalist)	ranked	0.65%
	Russian	Government and Military Officials	- Putin (Current President), Medvedev (Former President), Ordash (Russian charge d' affaires in Warsaw), Nadezhdin (liberal politician)	expected, fixated, held, interviewed, isolated, removed, tried, trusted, described, handed, barred	8.50%
		Activists and Advocates	- Petrova (anti-war activist), Rummyantsev (anti-war activist), Navalny (Russia opposition), Volkov (Chief of Staff of Anti-Corruption Foundation), Dugina (pro-war pundit)	arrested, committed, declared, escorted, sentenced, attacked, taken, charged, known, poisoned, treated, killed	15.03%
		Poets and Artists	- Kamardin (poet), Shtovba (poet), Gergiev (conductor)	given, sentenced	4.58%
		Athlete	- Mazepin (F1 driver)	allowed	0.65%
	American		- Biden (President), McCann (reporter and graphics editor)	interrupted, arrested	1.31%
	British		- Healy (humanitarian volunteer), Urey (humanitarian volunteer), Shapps (British Defense Secretary)	charged, warned, captured, diagnosed	3.92%
	Others		- Shekharappa (Indian student), Guemy (French street artist), Guterres (UN Secretary-General from Portugal)	known, expected, received, killed	1.96%
	Locations	Ukraine	City	Dnieper, Donbas, Bucha, Kyiv, Luhansk, Severodonetsk, Donetsk, Kherson, Mykolaiv, Amvrosiivka, Vinnytsia, Lysychansk	occupied, subjected, cut, considered, plagued, liberated, hit, left, stretched, hit, shelled, abandoned, attacked
Country			Ukraine	allowed, led, met, ruled, spared, undertaken	
Nationality			Ukrainian	displaced, held, killed, released	
Russia		City	Samara, Moscow	believed, focused, mired, designed	30.72%
		Country	Russia	absorbed, allowed, believed, bound, brought, designated, expected, forced, held, led, offended, prepared, recognized, reported, represented, required, stripped, thought	
		Nationality	Russian	arrested, swept, thwarted	
Disputed area			- Abkhazia, Crimea	recognised, invaded	1.31%
Others			- UK, US, Moldova	attacked, launched, expected, founded	2.61%
Organizations			- NATO, Gazprom, Facebook, Arconic	forced, hit, blocked, built, created	3.27%
Terms and Concepts			- Neptune, POWs, SIG, UAV, Bavovna	used, introduced, held, killed, manipulated, damaged, hit	3.92%
Total					100.00

[Return to [Section 5.1.2.1 Proper nouns categorization in the Ukraine War corpus](#)]

Table 55: Proper noun occurrences by years in the Leipzig corpora

Category & Sub-category	Prop. N.	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2023	%word	%sub-cat.	%cat.
People												
Ukrainian Officers	Zelensky						24.40		66.60	58.59		
	Yushchenko		6.41							4.13		
	Yanukovich	14.44	12.83				16.30			28.05		
	Serhiy		6.41							4.13		
	Nikulin					7.93				5.11		
	%sub-category	9.30	16.51			5.11	26.20		42.88	100.00	10.39	
Russian Officers	Putin	324.94	218.90	56.89	95.38	142.65	8.13	53.27	133.10	93.99		
	Medvedev	11.65	12.83	16.25		15.85			9.50	6.01		
	%sub-category	30.62	21.08	6.65	8.68	14.42	0.74	4.85	12.97	100.00	73.52	
Rus. Activists and Advocates	Navalny	58.24	32.72		23.84	31.70	24.40	6.63	28.50			
	%sub-category	28.27	15.88		11.57	15.39	11.84	3.22	13.83	100.00	13.78	
International Victims	Shapps						8.10	7.58	19.00			
	%sub-category						23.36	21.86	54.79	100.00	2.32	
%category		27.37	19.40	4.89	7.97	13.25	5.44	4.51	17.17	100.00	100.00	35.06
Location												
Ukrainian Locations	Ukraine	185.68	64.14	24.38	47.69	23.78	4.70	7.58	123.60	74.71		
	Kyiv	11.65	12.83						47.50	11.17		
	Donetsk	46.42	12.83						9.50	10.67		
	Donbas		6.41			7.93				2.22		
	Luhansk				7.95					1.23		
	%sub-category	37.82	14.93	3.78	8.63	4.92	0.73	1.18	28.02	100.00	24.27	
Ukrainian Nationality	Ukrainian	46.42	6.41	8.13	15.89	15.85	24.40		38.00			
	%sub-category	29.93	4.13	5.24	10.25	10.22	15.73		24.50	100.00	5.84	
Russian Locations	Russia	382.96	44.18	17.66	222.55	31.15	28.35	113.63	275.80	78.59		
	Moscow	127.65	44.91	8.13	7.95	31.70	32.50	22.73	28.50	21.41		
	%sub-category	35.95	6.27	1.82	16.23	4.42	4.28	9.60	21.42	100.00	53.49	
Russian Nationality	Russian	127.65	6.41	8.13		7.93	8.10	7.58	47.50	100.00		
	%sub-category	59.85	3.01	3.81		3.72	3.80	3.55	22.27	100.00	8.03	

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Table 55: Proper noun occurrences by years in the Leipzig corpora

Category & Sub-category	Prop. N.	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2023	%word	%sub-cat.	%cat.
Disputed Areas	Crimea	127.65	44.91	8.13		23.78	8.10		9.50	100.00		
	%sub-category	57.48	20.22	3.66		10.71	3.65		4.28	100.00	8.46	
%category		39.77	9.15	2.81	11.37	5.35	4.00	5.71	21.84	100.00	100.00	62.26
Terms & Concepts	UAV		6.41		7.95			7.58		21.94		
	PoWs	11.65	6.41	16.25	7.95		8.00		9.50	59.76		
	Neptune		6.41	8.13						14.54		
	%sub-cat. & cat.	12.11	19.98	25.33	16.52		8.31	7.88	9.87	100.00	100.00	2.26
Organizations	Gazprom	11.65	6.41							100.00		
	%sub-cat. & cat.	64.51	35.49							100.00	100.00	0.42
%year		34.90	13.10	4.03	10.25	7.98	4.58	5.31	19.84			100.00

[Return to [Section 5.1.2.3.1 Proper noun categories through time](#)]

The Occurrences of the Ukraine War Proper Noun Categories in the Leipzig Corpora

Figure 23: The occurrences of the Ukraine War proper noun categories in the Leipzig corpora

Figure 23 illustrates the categories of the proper nouns summed up per year in the Leipzig corpora. The categories related to *Russia* and *Ukraine* (*Nationality, Locations, Officials, and Activists and Advocates*) are the most consistently identified, being present in almost every year with the absence of *Ukrainian* in 2020, *Russian* in 2017, and *Navalny* in 2016. *Disputed Area (Crimea)* is also discussed almost every year except in 2017 and 2020. *Organizations* and *International Victims* are the least frequently discussed with *Gazprom* being found only in 2014 and 2015, and *Shapps* only in 2019, 2020, and 2023. Last but not least, *Terms and Concepts* are detected every year.

The overall trend in each category seems to be in a U shape where the proper nouns are mentioned most often in the year 2014 before the rate falls down sharply in the following years and surges up again towards 2023. This is in accordance with Russia’s annexation of the Crimean Peninsula in 2014, as well as the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2023. One noticeable fluctuation is the spike in the middle during 2017 and 2018. The close-reading reveals a few possible causes, namely the NotPetya malware outbreak in June 2017 and the increasing diplomatic efforts involving Ukraine, Russia, and Western countries during that period.

[Return to Section 5.1.2.3.1 Proper noun categories through time]

Table 56: Common pairs in the Ukraine War corpus and the 2014 and 2023 Leipzig corpora

Common Pairs	OF_Ukr	EF_Ukr	t_Ukr	p_Ukr	OF_14	EF_Lz14	t_Lz14	p_Lz14	OF_Lz23	EF_Lz23	t_Lpz23	p_Lpz23
people_killed	37	5.49	13.45	0.05	351	28.35	60.60	0.01	156	9.38	47.89	0.01
soldiers_killed	11	1.50	7.74	0.08	68	2.97	37.73	0.02	17	0.49	23.59	0.03
civilians_killed	10	1.80	6.10	0.10	43	1.26	37.19	0.02	19	0.34	32.24	0.02
people_injured	9	0.99	8.06	0.08	101	8.46	31.81	0.02	59	4.69	25.08	0.03
others_wounded	6	0.14	15.54	0.04	22	0.47	31.45	0.02	9	0.14	23.76	0.03
dozens_wounded	6	0.14	15.54	0.04	1	0.20	1.79	0.33	1	0.04	5.04	0.12
people_wounded	6	1.15	4.52	0.14	44	3.52	21.59	0.03	11	0.95	10.32	0.06
claim_verified	4	0.05	17.21	0.04	2	0.01	16.45	0.04	1	0.00	14.62	0.04
people_displaced	4	0.38	5.83	0.11	16	0.82	16.72	0.04	16	0.61	19.78	0.03
explosions_heard	3	0.02	22.20	0.03	10	0.03	55.00	0.01	2	0.02	15.70	0.04
election_held	3	0.06	12.31	0.05	49	1.66	36.70	0.02	14	0.90	13.78	0.05
explosions_reported	3	0.12	8.42	0.08	1	0.08	3.15	0.20	3	0.03	16.41	0.04
others_injured	2	0.12	5.38	0.12	12	1.13	10.24	0.06	30	0.69	35.35	0.02
schools_closed	1	0.00	18.18	0.03	25	0.37	40.63	0.02	9	0.30	15.75	0.04
what_happened	1	0.01	13.71	0.05	6	0.12	17.26	0.04	19	0.22	40.04	0.02
damage_done	1	0.01	12.82	0.05	34	0.45	49.84	0.01	17	0.32	29.67	0.02
woman_arrested	1	0.01	12.82	0.05	22	5.44	7.10	0.09	22	3.67	9.57	0.07
story_told	1	0.01	11.45	0.06	1	0.42	0.90	0.53	19	0.74	21.28	0.03
decision_made	1	0.01	9.64	0.07	124	4.92	53.69	0.01	111	6.02	42.78	0.01
what_described	1	0.02	7.83	0.08	22	1.40	17.39	0.04	31	1.81	21.69	0.03
efforts_made	1	0.02	7.83	0.08	9	1.11	7.48	0.08	21	1.75	14.54	0.04
decision_taken	1	0.03	5.91	0.11	22	4.82	7.82	0.08	42	3.97	19.07	0.03
bodies_found	1	0.03	5.32	0.12	75	3.90	36.02	0.02	27	1.68	19.56	0.03
what_left	1	0.04	5.02	0.13	22	3.28	10.34	0.06	38	5.34	14.14	0.04
man_taken	1	0.04	4.76	0.13	70	12.97	15.84	0.04	47	12.10	10.03	0.06
what_needed	1	0.04	4.67	0.13	32	3.49	15.25	0.04	31	3.47	14.78	0.04
people_arrested	1	0.44	0.85	0.55	82	20.93	13.35	0.05	56	12.71	12.14	0.05
Average			9.74	0.10			24.20	0.07			21.06	0.04

* OF = observed frequency, EF = expected frequency, t = t-score, p = p-value

[Return to [Overlapping pairs between the Ukraine War corpus and the Leipzig News corpora](#)]

Topic 0: Score = 1724

school: 0.02628955032671426
 student: 0.018996113417358643
 teacher: 0.017585613102662018
 education: 0.0172650371087878
 college: 0.010945631308617343
 university: 0.008745676366557315
 class: 0.008725596022172289
 grade: 0.008161995854324689
 teach: 0.007477370054643667
 scholarship: 0.00699409521631468

Topic 2: Score = 1201

fire: 0.043285775166403376
 firefighter: 0.030869865327219984
 flame: 0.015412655694815041
 wildfire: 0.014450898128236446
 blaze: 0.013519608828066723
 burn: 0.013181841112312447
 extinguish: 0.008568419687352372
 engulf: 0.007443015343721647
 firework: 0.006673054347745308
 crew: 0.006521846701161178

Topic 1: Score = 1447

gun: 0.025399912938399702
 shooting: 0.021882691753651977
 shoot: 0.020346913330146616
 gunshot: 0.009902042988908373
 shot: 0.009582867205230366
 gunfire: 0.009459639047856691
 officer: 0.008948877617724088
 fatally: 0.00854381304840883
 firearm: 0.008520968218965171
 bullet: 0.008518714191217682

Topic 3: Score = 1186

ukraine: 0.037800145168949986
 russia: 0.028193685127463418
 russian: 0.02741978510637296
 ukrainian: 0.027019138718817764
 putin: 0.02290869578492455
 moscow: 0.015698758513487236
 donetsk: 0.014202013468567741
 minsk: 0.012878370915669141
 vladimir: 0.012080941741008414
 crimea: 0.01169367170310528

(Top 4 popular topics in the score report of the 2015 Leipzig corpus)

Table 57: The transformation of topic keywords and scores

Topic_Lpz_15	Score	Norm. Sc.	Keyword
Education	1724	514.51	school, student, teacher, education, college, university, class, grade, teach, scholarship
Gun Violence	1447	431.84	gun, shooting, shoot, gunshot, shot, gunfire, officer, fatally, firearm, bullet
Firefighting	1201	358.43	fire, firefighter, flame, wildfire, blaze, burn, extinguish, engulf, firework, crew
Ukraine Conflict	1186	353.95	ukraine, russia, russian, ukrainian, putin, moscow, donetsk, minsk, vladimir, crimea

(This table shows how the topics from the score report are put in a tabular format.)

[Return to [Section 5.2.5 Topics in news reports](#)]

Table 58: Topic keywords and scores (2014-2017)

#	Topic_Lpz_14	Score	Topic_Lpz_15	Score	Topic_Lpz_16	Score	Topic_Lpz_17	Score
1	Education	596.36	Education	514.51	Education & Schooling	1056.5	Music	550.21
2	Rus-Ukr Confl. [2]	555.67	Gun Violence	431.84	Parenting	607.89	Education	518.98
3	Israel-Palestine Confl.	502.87	Fire & Firefighting	358.43	Legal & Court Matters	508.91	Film Industry	515.55
4	Gun Violence	459.38	Rus-Ukr Confl. [4]	353.95	Religion & Clergy	420.07	Gun Violence	314.05
5	Film Industry	387.95	Space Exploration	320.23	Fire & Firefighting	342.85	Medical Emergencies	278.19
6	Medical Emergencies	372.42	Middle East Conflict	280.53	Music	310.65	Fire & Firefighting	260.67
7	China Relations	361.23	Religion	228.90	Art & Museums	267.72	Parenting	245.43
8	Music	299.73	Sexual Violence	225.02	Death & Obituaries	236.12	Weather & Nat. Dis.	186.35
9	Fire & Firefighting	287.93	Parenting	211.00	Sports & Games	233.14	Obituaries	184.05
10	Space Exploration	230.16	China Relations	197.27	Journalism & Publishing	218.83	Art	183.48
11	Parenting	227.36	Greek Crisis	187.12	Cooking & Food	210.48	Gender Issues	175.37
12	Weather & Nat. Dis.	201.58	Israel-Palestine Confl.	182.94	Weather & Nat. Dis.	193.19	Pets	165.63
13	Sexual Violence	184.81	Paris Attacks	176.38	Film Industry	183.65	Culinary	159.64
14	Soccer	184.19	Crime	169.51	Medical Emergencies	170.23	Prison	150.06
15	Pets	182.33	Cybersecurity	153.40	Charity & Volunteering	166.65	Israel-Palestine Confl.	99.08
16	Ebola Outbreak	182.01	Weather & Nat. Dis.	148.03	Funerals & Memorial	165.76	Rus-Ukr Confl. [30]	97.89
17	Smartphones	174.25	Music	146.53	Fashion & Clothing	159.50		
18	Protests	166.48	Film Industry	45.06	Fishing & Wildlife	156.82		
19					Alcohol & Beverages	155.92		
20					Pets & Animals	151.45		
21					Agriculture & Farming	144.89		
22					Israel-Palestine Conflict	126.71		
23					Rus-Ukr Confl. [74]	48.89		
24					Gun Violence	18.48		

*Rus-Ukr Confl. = Russia-Ukraine Conflict

[\[Return to Section 5.2.5 Topics in news reports\]](#)

Table 59: Topic keywords and scores (2018-2023)

#	Topic_Lpz_18	Score	Topic_Lpz_19	Score	Topic_Lpz_20	Score	Topic_Lpz_23	Score
1	Weather & Nat. Dis.	653.67	American Football	719.87	US Election	1752.5	Music	538.85
2	Food & Dining	642.25	Music	623.77	Education	794.35	Education	464.69
3	Music	599.72	Education	584.69	Sanity Measures	448.28	Israel & Palestine	458.70
4	Education	535.21	Cryptocurrency	405.81	Gun Violence	371.56	Sports (Soccer)	338.89
5	Soccer & Sports	405.62	Housing Market	346.47	Music	335.11	Crime	290.39
6	American Football	344.25	Social Media	303.92	Fire & Firefighting	320.04	Food & Beverage	242.19
7	Fire & Firefighting	343.39	Fire & Firefighting	291.19	Coronavirus	289.90	Fire & Firefighting	231.63
8	Parenting	305.14	Transportation	287.72	Weather & Nat. Dis.	267.16	Water & Weather	230.20
9	Israel-Palestine Conflict	287.16	Culinary Arts	277.01	Court	264.42	Economic Growth	229.06
10	Elections & Voting	269.46	Brexit	264.85	Parenting	218.93	Weather Conditions	204.53
11	Religion & Clergy	260.61	Parenting	260.51	Quarantine	202.22	Pets & Animals	195.69
12	Nigerian Politics	245.77	Medical Emergencies	190.75	Middle East Conflict	197.56	Events & Festivals	193.69
13	Energy & Resources	223.50	Police Investigations	181.20	Fashion	180.85	Rus-Ukr Confl. [13]	170.30
14	Rus-Ukr Confl. [14]	190.11	Obituaries	174.83	Vaccine	179.48	NFL Football	168.02
15	Film Industry	172.98	Pets	157.17	Religion	171.80	Drug-related Activities	164.31
16	Prisons & Sentencing	163.85	Religion	153.99	Pets	169.61	Maritime Activities	159.17
17	Drugs & Addiction	149.86	Middle East Conflict	148.49	Soccer	167.97	Art & Museums	154.33
18	Pets & Animals	146.43	Weather & Nat. Dis.	127.36	Virus	155.64	Religion & Church	153.47
19	China & Trade	143.58	Gun Violence	100.44	Gaming	155.36	Movies & Cinema	149.76
20	Gun Violence	88.20	Israel-Palestine Confl.	88.57	Cryptocurrency	154.54	Fashion & Clothing	146.05
21			Film Industry	71.78	Traffic	151.80	Parenting	141.77
22			Rus-Ukr Confl. [88]	57.31	Lockdown	150.43		
23					American Football	150.16		
24					Racism	146.32		
25					Israel-Palestine Confl.	101.38		
26					Film Industry	70.97		
27					Rus-Ukr Confl. [188]	19.18		

*Rus-Ukr Confl. = Russia-Ukraine Conflict

[\[Return to Section 5.2.5 Topics in news reports\]](#)

Figure 24: Semantic categories of agentive by-phrases in the Ukraine War corpus

[\[Return to Section 5.3.1 By-agent semantic categories\]](#)

Table 60: Anglo-Saxon and non Anglo-Saxon media

Website	Frequency	Anglo-Saxon Media	Country	Explanation
aljazeera.com	11	No	Qatar	Al Jazeera is a Qatari news network, not Anglo-Saxon.
en.wikipedia.org	6	No		Wikipedia is an online encyclopedia.
iiss.org	3	No	UK	IISS (International Institute for Strategic Studies) is a think tank.
nejm.org	3	No	USA	NEJM (New England Journal of Medicine) is a medical journal.
nato.int	2	No		NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) is a political-military alliance.
theconversation.com	1	No		The Conversation is an independent academic source.
dw.com	1	No	Germany	Deutsche Welle (DW) is a German public international broadcaster.
warontherocks.com	1	No		War on the Rocks is a platform for analysis and debate.
iea.org	1	No	UK	The Institute of Education (IE) is a research institute.
Non Anglo-Saxon Media	29 (21.01%)			
cnn.com	18	Yes	USA	CNN is an American news network.
nytimes.com	16	Yes	USA	The New York Times is an American newspaper.
bbc.com	13	Yes	UK	BBC is a British public service broadcaster.
theguardian.com	10	Yes	UK	The Guardian is a British newspaper.
apnews.com	9	Yes	USA	Associated Press is an American news agency.
vox.com	7	Yes	USA	Vox is an American news and opinion website.
cnbc.com	5	Yes	USA	CNBC is an American business news channel.
reuters.com	5	Yes	UK	Reuters is a UK-based global news agency.
news.sky.com	4	Yes	UK	Sky News is a British news channel.
bloomberg.com	4	Yes	USA	Bloomberg is an American global financial services provider.
rand.org	4	Yes	USA	RAND Corporation is an American research institution.
npr.org	2	Yes	USA	National Public Radio is an American non-profit media organization.
washingtonpost.com	2	Yes	USA	The Washington Post is an American newspaper.
foreignpolicy.com	2	Yes	USA	Foreign Policy is an American magazine.
ft.com	2	Yes		The Financial Times is a British international business newspaper.
nbcnews.com	1	Yes	USA	NBC News is an American news network.
atlanticcouncil.org	1	Yes	USA	Atlantic Council is an American think tank.
cfr.org	1	Yes	USA	Council on Foreign Relations is an American think tank.
irishtimes.com	1	Yes	Ireland	The Irish Times is an Irish newspaper.

Continued on next page

Website	Frequency	Anglo-Saxon Media	Country	Explanation
pbs.org	1	Yes	USA	PBS is an American public broadcasting network.
usip.org	1	Yes	USA	US Institute of Peace is an American think tank.
Anglo-Saxon Media	109 (78.99%)			
Total	138 (100%)			

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